

HEALTH WORKERS IMPACT BASELINE ANALYSIS

Deliverable 2.10

Health Workers Impact Baseline Analysis

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Table of Contents

List of tables.....	4
List of figures	5
Abbreviations.....	6
Definitions	7
Executive Summary.....	9
1 Introduction.....	12
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	12
1.2 Deviations from the project proposal	12
1.3 Report integration and relation to other deliverables.....	13
2 Background	13
3 Methods.....	16
3.1 Study design.....	16
3.2 Study settings.....	16
3.3 Study components	18
4 Results.....	31
4.1 Description of facilities.....	31
4.2 Theme 1: Dehydration	38
4.3 Theme 2: Psychological and perceived heat strain	44
4.4 Theme 3: Performance and quality of care	57
4.5 Thermal exposure in health facilities	65
4.6 Attitudes towards common adaptation interventions and their feasibility 73	
5 Conclusion	74
6 References.....	79
7 Appendices	82
7.1 Researchers involved in the study.....	82
7.2 Data collection participation and timing.....	84
7.3 Supplementary tables from quantitative analyses	86
7.4 Quality of care analysis using the time-motion study	94
7.5 Healthcare workers' study protocol.....	98

List of tables

Table 1. Description of facilities	17
Table 2. Multivariable analysis of determinants of dehydration (USG \geq 1.020) in South Africa and Zimbabwe	40
Table 3. The impact of average outdoor heat stress temperature (WBGT) on mental health indicators.....	46
Table 4. Aggregated values of the air temperature and WBGT measured in the facilities in South Africa and Sweden	68
Table 5. Accumulated number of hours when the indoor air temperature or the WBGT exceeded recommended thresholds.....	69
Table 6. Aggregated values of the air temperature and WBGT measured during a year in the facilities in Zimbabwe	72
Table 7. Accumulated number of hours when the indoor air temperature or the WBGT exceeded recommended thresholds, Zimbabwe.....	72
Table 8. Map of evidence for adverse heat impact, based on findings from the baseline health worker study.....	75
Table 9. Research team members per study site.....	82
Table 10. Numbers of participants and timing of data collection for the baseline healthcare workers' study	84
Table 11. Sample characteristics, Zimbabwe.....	86
Table 12. Sample characteristics, South Africa.....	89
Table 13. Sample characteristics, Sweden	92
Table 14. Mental health outcomes by country and season	92
Table 15. Outcome definitions	94
Table 16. Delivery sessions sample characteristics by country	95
Table 17. Association between quality of care processes and heat stress (1/2)...	96
Table 18. Association between quality of care processes and heat stress (2/2)...	97

List of figures

Figure 1. Violin plots, showing the distribution of USG values, with individual data points and paired connections between summer and winter for the same participants 39

Figure 2. Heat stress association with changes in mental health indicators..... 45

Figure 3. Heat stress association with perception of four heat strain indicators. 52

Figure 4. Perceived impact of heat stress on quality of care & communication... 58

Figure 5. Association between heat stress and processes of quality of intrapartum care. Crude and adjusted odds ratios 63

Figure 6. Association curves between exposure to outdoor heat stress and absenteeism..... 64

Figure 7. Temperature measured during 2024 in selected rooms in Stanza and Mamelodi clinics and outdoors..... 65

Figure 8. Temperatures measured indoors at Karolinska Hospital, Sweden, and outdoors at the location of the hospital 67

Figure 9. Temperature measured from November 2023 to December 2024 in selected rooms at Mount Darwin Hospital and at Chitse and Dotito rural health centre and outdoors 70

Figure 10. Healthcare workers perception of the feasibility of adaptation interventions..... 73

Figure 11. The links between heat and maternal healthcare workers' wellbeing and quality of care (Lange et al., 2025) 76

Figure 12. Impact of heat on mental health indicators 93

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
ANC	Antenatal clinic
aOR	Adjusted odds ratio
BMI	Body mass index
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHC	Community health centre
CI	Confidence interval
DTU	Technical University of Denmark (Denmark)
EU	European Union
GAD	General Anxiety Disorder
GEE	Generalised estimating equation
FCH	Family Child Health
HCW	Healthcare worker
IDI	In-depth interview
IQR	Interquartile range
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
KII	Key informant interview
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MoHCC	Ministry of Health and Child Care, Zimbabwe
ODK	Open Data Kit
OR	Odds ratio
PHC	Primary healthcare
PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
RH	Relative humidity
UK	United Kingdom
USG	Urine-specific gravity
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
WHO	World Health Organization
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)

Definitions

Term	Definition/Description
Dehydration	Dehydration can be defined broadly as the process of losing body water which leads eventually to hypohydration (EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, 2010).
Heat strain	Heat strain refers to the response of the human body to exposure to heat stress (Coco et al., 2016). The symptoms include increased core body temperature, heart rate, dizziness and headaches, heat exhaustion, and heat stroke. See also: Predicted heat strain.
Heat stress	Heat stress describes the environmental conditions that can increase the heat load on the body, namely air temperature, air flow, radiation heat, humidity and metabolic heat (Coco et al., 2016).
Predicted heat strain	ISO 7933 describes a procedure for analytical evaluation and interpretation of thermal stress experienced by a person in a hot environment (ISO 7933-2023). Based on a comprehensive model of the heat transfer between the body and surroundings, the procedure evaluates thermal strain by excessive core temperature increase or water loss for a standard subject. In addition, the procedure allows determination of the exposure time during which the physiological strain is acceptable. As the procedure predicts physiological strain for standard persons it needs to be adapted if it should be used to assess thermal strain among vulnerable populations. (International Organization for Standardization, 2004)
Thermal comfort	Thermal comfort is the condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment; however, due to large physiological and psychological variations from one person to another, it is difficult to maintain thermal comfort in one given space for all (ASHRAE 2004), whether it be indoors or outdoors. It is crucial for human beings to maintain a constant core body temperature of 37 °C (98 °F). However, the temperature away from the core, such as on the skin and extremities for instance, can vary considerably with environmental and metabolic heat loads. To maintain the core body temperature, heat is exchanged with the environment by respiration (latent and sensible heat fluxes), radiation (longwave and shortwave), evaporation (latent heat flux), conduction (contact with solids), and convection (sensible heat flux) (Jendritzky and de Dear 2009). To this end, the human thermoregulatory system can be separated into active and passive interacting systems. The active system concerns the thermoregulatory response (e.g. shivering or perspiring) and the passive system deals with heat transfers at the body surface. When the body is under thermal comfort conditions, the body is under least strain because the active system is at its lowest activity level. However, increasing discomfort is associated with increasing strain. Research shows that people take action to improve their comfort conditions by modifying

Term	Definition/Description
	<p>their clothing and metabolic rate when outdoors, or by interacting with the building when they are indoors, which are considered actions of adaptation (Nicol and Humphreys 2002). When adaptation opportunity is limited, departure from neutrality causes stress and dissatisfaction (Baker and Standeven 1996). According to Nikolopoulou et al. (2001), intrinsic factors such as past experience, expectations and time of exposure are also important for thermal comfort.(Global heat health information network, n.d.)</p>
<p>Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)</p>	<p>Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) is the most widely used heat index because it is an international standard for heat stress (Budd, 2008; Buzan et al., 2015, ISO 7243-2017). It was originally developed in the 1950s as part of a campaign to lower the risk of heat disorders during the training of US Army and Marine troops (Minard, 1961). Wet bulb globe temperature is calculated using observations from a wet bulb thermometer – a thermometer wrapped in a damp muslin cloth, a globe thermometer to measure incidence of radiation and a dry air thermometer. Or it is approximated using empirical models of these values (Davies-Jones, 2008; Liljegren et al., 2008; Stull, 2011). The equation for an outdoor WBGT is: $WBGT=0.7T_w+0.2T_g+0.1T_d$ The equation for an indoor WBGT is: $WBGT=0.7T_w+0.3T_g$ Where T_w is Wet Bulb Temperature (°C), T_g is Globe Temperature (°C) and T_d is air temperature (°C) (Brimicombe, 2023).</p>

For a more extensive list of terms, please visit HIGH Horizons' heat-health glossary: *HIGH Horizons Consortium. Heat-Health Glossary. Zenodo. HIGH Horizons, 2024.* <https://www.high-horizons.eu/resources/glossary/>.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the first comprehensive baseline assessment of how rising heat affects frontline maternal and child health workers in South Africa, Zimbabwe and, for comparison, in Sweden. The assessment was undertaken within the HIGH Horizons project to generate the evidence needed for designing and evaluating heat-adaptation measures in health facilities in resource-limited settings.

The study employed a mixed-methods approach between 2023 and 2025. Data sources included continuous indoor climate monitoring, a longitudinal health-worker survey with spot urine tests for hydration, wearable monitoring, structured observations of care, in-depth interviews and a bespoke time-motion study of intrapartum care. Two facilities in South Africa, two in Zimbabwe and nine in Sweden were included. While the Swedish component had to be scaled back for cost and logistical reasons, the African sites provided rich data on exposures, wellbeing and care quality.

The findings reveal consistent and concerning patterns. In both South Africa and Zimbabwe, clinical rooms frequently **exceeded safe temperature thresholds**. For example, in South Africa Stanza Bopape community health centre's antenatal unit recorded 4064 hours at 25–32 °C (≈46 % of the year) and 597 hours above 32 °C, while in Zimbabwe Mount Darwin District Hospital's main delivery room logged 4713 hours in the 25–32 °C band and 426 hours above 32 °C between November 2023 and October 2024. By contrast, in Sweden at Karolinska University Hospital in Stockholm only a single patient-room hour exceeded 25 °C and none exceeded 32 °C over the same period.

Heat translated into **poor hydration**: 53 % of South-African staff and 75 % of Zimbabwean staff were dehydrated (urine-specific gravity ≥ 1.020) during the hot season, and working in Zimbabwe carried more than triple the odds of dehydration compared with South Africa (OR = 3.07, 95 % CI 1.25–7.53).

Mental wellbeing and stress also deteriorated with heat; each 1 °C rise in outdoor Wet Bulb Globe Temperature corresponded to a 0.15-point fall in WHO-5 wellbeing scores after adjustment for confounders (effect size = -0.15, 95% CI: -0.29 to -0.02), and an increase of 0.08 on the perceived stress scale (95% CI: 0.01 to 0.15). Staff interviews and observations corroborated these quantitative patterns, describing lapses in concentration, documentation errors, and briefer, sometimes less respectful, patient interactions once indoor temperatures climbed above 30 °C.

Heat compromised several dimensions of **care quality and performance**. Qualitative interviews and quantitative analyses converged on the finding that, when temperatures rose, staff altered their workflows—most notably by rushing key procedures. Consultations became shorter, and midwives more often left women alone during labour. Productivity emerged as a central theme: routine records showed that staff absences increased after exposure to high temperatures two to three days earlier, pointing to a lagged effect of heat on attendance. Both interview data and the time-motion study indicated that heat particularly eroded the interactive elements of care, such as providing health education and emotional support. By contrast, adherence to core clinical tasks—monitoring mothers in labour and delivering newborn care—remained largely intact.

Overall, this baseline study demonstrates that **heat is already a critical occupational-health challenge in maternal and newborn services**. Rising temperatures compromise hydration, wellbeing, respectful care, and staff productivity, with clear implications for patient outcomes. This is the first study to use comprehensive set of tools, with triangulated findings on the impacts of heat in health facilities on healthcare workers and their work across three countries. Based on our findings, we developed a conceptual framework to illustrate the complexity of heat impact on different aspects related to healthcare workers and

quality of care in maternal wards. These results informed the co-design process for the HIGH Horizons interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe, which identified drinking behaviours and facility infrastructural design as key domains for adaptation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This report outlines the findings made under the health worker study, which is part of HIGH Horizons research activities. The aim of the study was to provide a baseline assessment of the impacts of heat on the wellbeing, health, productivity of healthcare workers¹ as well as on the quality care they provide. The assessment was conducted in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden to enable comparative analysis. It also provided data used during the co-design of the climate adaption interventions in selected health facilities in the two African countries and will support its evaluation as a baseline.

1.2 Deviations from the project proposal

The scope of work in Sweden was reduced from the original plan. For instance, the time-motion component was not conducted, as the team from Karolinska Institutet (KI) deemed it logistically unfeasible due to cost considerations and the potential intrusiveness for both patients and providers. In addition, the start of the study in Sweden was delayed due to logistical challenges, and the content of some of the data collection tools (questionnaire) were further adapted to fit a context with different professional terminology and social and environmental protection mechanisms. No physiological data were collected in Sweden to assess the impact of heat. We also did not carry out an investigation of routine data on absenteeism and quality of care in Sweden. In South Africa and Zimbabwe, urine specific gravity was measured, but the monitoring of heart rates, steps, and core temperatures

¹ The terms 'Healthcare worker' and 'health worker' are often used interchangeably. In this study, we use the term healthcare workers to refer to those providing healthcare services in clinical settings (e.g. doctors, nurses, midwives etc). 'Health workers' can be used more broadly to include those working in other fields such as health promotion, public health, household health visits and so on.

was affected by technological difficulties, resulting in incomplete data that are not reported here.

1.3 Report integration and relation to other deliverables

As mentioned above, while the health worker study is a stand-alone output of HIGH Horizons, this report presents findings that also serve as the baseline assessment for the evaluation of the heat adaptation interventions in health facilities in South Africa and Zimbabwe (deliverables D5.5 - Evaluation of experiences and effectiveness of adaptation in health facilities & D5.6 - Analysis of cost-benefits of heat adaptation interventions on workers' health and productivity; both forthcoming). In addition, the findings of the study were used to inform the co-design of interventions (deliverable D3.6 - Report on modelling of alternative adaptation interventions; February 2024). Finally, findings on thermal exposure were also reported in greater details in deliverable D2.8 - Environmental exposures in health facilities (Toftum et al., 2024).

2 Background

The increased intensity and frequency of extreme weather events, such as heatwaves, are posing a growing threat to human health worldwide (Chersich et al., 2020; Ebi et al., 2021; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020). While increasing ambient heat is a global challenge, recent data highlight the scale of the problem in Europe, where the total number of person-days exposed to heatwaves nearly doubled over the past decade – rising by 97% from 650 million (2000-2009) to 1.28 billion (2012-2021) (Van Daalen et al., 2024). This rise reflects both the increase in the number of people considered at high risk and a greater number of heatwaves. Africa has also been significantly impacted by climate change over the past four decades, in part because of its limited adaptive capabilities and

infrastructure (Manyuchi et al., 2022). The African continent experienced a temperature increase of approximately +0.3 °C per decade between 1991 and 2023, slightly exceeding the global average rate of warming (+0.2 °C) (World Meteorological Organization, 2025). Climate extremes (including heat-related) are worsening on the continent, causing annual GDP losses of 2%–5% and forcing some African countries to allocate up to 9% of their budgets for response (World Meteorological Organization, 2025).

As extreme heat becomes more frequent and intense, its effects on frontline workers, including those in health systems, are coming into sharper focus.

Healthcare workers (HCW) are vulnerable to high levels of strain caused by heat exposure (Bonell et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2020). Health facilities in low- and middle-income countries are under-equipped to deliver a comfortable indoor climate for health workers and patients (Wright et al., 2017). Exposure to high heat in healthcare settings has been linked to exhaustion, fatigue, and impaired mental health (Foster et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020). These effects may be particularly pronounced in settings with high workloads and staff shortages, where multiple stressors could compound one another and further impact performance.

The existing literature on occupational heat stress mostly focuses on outdoor workers and athletes, whilst studies on healthcare-specific heat stress has been found to be limited to health workers wearing personal protective equipment in one review (Flouris et al., 2018). Current evidence concerning other occupations and heat exposure includes a systematic review conducted on 111 studies, which shows that 35% of individuals working under environmental heat stress conditions experienced heat strain (i.e., physiological consequences, such as core body temperature >38 °C, ≥1 occupational heat strain symptom, such as serum creatinine concentration of >1,2 mg/dL, heat-associated self-reported nausea or vomiting) and 30% experienced reduced productivity (defined as loss of labour

time, performance, or absence from work due to occupational heat strain) (Flouris et al., 2018).

As high ambient heat and heatwaves are affecting healthcare facilities (Wright et al., 2017), it is imperative to understand the scale and consequences of ambient heat stress in these settings, with a view to improving healthcare preparedness against heat and protect both healthcare workers and patients. This study aims to address this gap as part of the HIGH Horizons research activities.

The **objectives** of this study are:

1. To explore and measure how ambient heat influences HCWs':
 - i. Work performance and productivity
 - ii. Perceived wellbeing
 - iii. Physical health
 - iv. Quality of care
2. To describe current practices for reducing the impact of heat exposure on work productivity, perceived wellbeing, physical health, and quality of care
3. To provide empirical evidence for informing the co-design of climate change facility adaptation interventions and the baseline data for the evaluation of the interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe
4. To explore the feasibility of and attitudes towards interventions commonly used in heat adaptation
5. To quantify thermal exposures in the selected healthcare facilities through observation and continuous monitoring of the indoor thermal environment, and through HCW personal wearables.

3 Methods

This section briefly outlines the methods of each study component. For full methodological details, please refer to the HCWs' study protocol in Appendix 7.5.

3.1 Study design

This is a mixed-method study comprising several quantitative and qualitative components, namely longitudinal measurements, participant observation, in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, a time-motion study and analysis of routine statistics. Each study component is described in detail in 3.3, with details about number of participants and timing of data collection in Appendix 7.2.

3.2 Study settings

The study has been conducted in three countries: Zimbabwe (one hospital and two rural primary care facilities), South Africa (one regional hospital and one community health centre), and Sweden (one hospital, and eight primary healthcare facilities). The study took place in antenatal, labour, postnatal, and neonatal wards or child health clinics. Table 1 provides the description of the study facilities and their service volume.

In **South Africa**, the study health facilities comprise Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre (CHC) in the Tshwane district, Gauteng Province. The hospital's catchment area population is about 334 577. It also serves as a referral centre for patients requiring high level of care such as pregnant women with obstetric emergencies. Stanza Bopape CHC serves a population of 261 989, with about 74 deliveries per month. The hottest months of the year are usually December, January, and February. The temperature ranges between 17 °C and 30 °C, with a mean of 23 °C.

In **Zimbabwe**, the study took place at three public healthcare facilities which are within Mashonaland Central Province, Mt Darwin District, whose population was

240,727 in 2022. The three sites are Mt Darwin District Hospital (urban), and Chitse and Dotito Rural Healthcare centres. The average temperature in the district is 24 °C in summer and 14 °C in winter. Mt Darwin District hospital is a primary care and a referral facility for the district. A range of services are offered which include curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male and female ward, theatre, laboratory, and a pharmacy.

Table 1. Description of facilities

Name of proposed facility sites	Facility level	Number of women attending ANC (first visit) per month (average)	Number of deliveries per month (average)	Number of HCWs employed in antenatal care and delivery units (auxiliary midwives, nurses, midwives, doctors)
South Africa				
Stanza Bopape community health centre	Primary healthcare (PHC) facility	250	74	26 (24 Nurses, 2 Stand-By Doctors)
Mamelodi hospital	District hospital	(High risk cases from PHC)	800-1000	150 (130 Nurses, 20 Doctors)
Zimbabwe				
Mount Darwin District Hospital	District hospital (Primary care and referral for district)	205	164-180	12 midwives, 2 doctors, 14 nurses and 6 nurse aides
Dotito rural healthcare centre	Primary healthcare facility	28	25-30	5 nurses and 1 midwife whole clinic, no doctor.
Chitse rural healthcare centre	Primary healthcare facility	30	18-20	5 nurses and 1 midwife, no doctor whole clinic.
Sweden				
Karolinska University Hospital	Tertiary level	NA (ANC in a primary healthcare centre)	308	Nurses and auxiliary nurses, Midwives and student midwives, medical students, Obstetricians/gynaecologists and specialised doctors (approx. 12-16 Ob/Gyn, 25 midwives and 20 auxiliary nurses)
Antenatal care (n=6)	Primary healthcare facilities	Between 23-120	NA	Midwives, nurses, doctors (approx. 8-15 per facility)
Child health centres (n=2)	Primary healthcare facilities	NA	NA	Nurses and doctors (approx. 8-15 per facility)

In **Sweden**, the observation site selected is in Karolinska University Hospital in the northern part of Stockholm. The hospital is a national referral centre for high-risk pregnancies and deliveries as well as regional referral centre for specialised high-risk pregnancies and deliveries. The volume of deliveries is 3 700 deliveries per month, all of which relate to high-risk pregnancies. Summers in Sweden occur in June-August, with a mean temperature of 23 °C, although on some hot days the temperature can be up to 35 °C. Winter in Sweden starts from November to February.

For interviews, six antenatal midwifery care centres and two child health centres in the greater Stockholm metropolitan area were selected as the site of interviews. The antenatal clinics are staffed by midwives and doctors who provide pregnancy-related care; as well as offer contraceptive advice, testing for sexually transmitted infections, counselling on abortion, ultrasound screenings (at some clinics), parental education classes, and support for birth planning to couples (i.e. courses and information). The child health centres employ child nurses and doctors to monitor children's health from birth to around 6 years; and they track growth and development, provide vaccines (as part of the vaccination programme for Sweden), and provide guidance on breastfeeding to the mother, information and guidance to parents on the child's sleeping habits, nutrition, and illness prevention. The antenatal clinics and child health centres tend to be smaller than hospital wards and may be located within the same building for convenience.

3.3 Study components

3.3.1 Participant observation

Participant observation is a research method commonly used in anthropology and other social sciences. In this approach, researchers immerse themselves in the community or group they are studying, actively participating in their daily activities while also observing and documenting the social and cultural aspects of the

community (Geertz, 2000). The purpose of this component is to (i) understand how heat can influence HCWs' wellbeing, and productivity in the workplace (study objective 1), and (ii) to document the current practices HCWs do to adapt to heat (study objective 2).

In our health worker study, trained nurses and field assistants with experience in health research and clinical settings undertook participant observation at healthcare facilities in the study sites. Observations focused on the working and structural environment, as well as on the activities of individuals in antenatal clinics and in maternal, labour and newborn wards.

Observations were conducted over a period of two or three weeks in each of the hotter and cooler seasons in **Zimbabwe**, with observations completed for the hotter season only in **South Africa**. Data collection of the observations in Zimbabwe began in August until mid-September 2023 in Mt Darwin District Hospital, Dotito rural health centre and Chitse rural health centre. Field assistants observed for 4-6 hours a day (including during night shifts) and kept detailed daily journals documenting their observations. The two research assistants conducted a total of 196 hours of observations over a period of 19 days, with 10 days spent in Mt Darwin, 4 days in Chitse, and 5 days in Dotito. Unfortunately, there were no recordings of ambient temperatures in any of the facilities as the thermal sensors had not yet been installed and were in transit from the manufacturer.

In **South Africa**, observations were carried out in November and December 2023, two of the hottest months of the summer. A total of 158 hours of observation were completed by four trained observers, spread over 18 days in a five-week period. Ambient temperatures for Tshwane were recorded by observers at the start of each observation session, obtained from a widely used local online weather forecasting service. Based on these records, the median temperature on the days of observation was 30 °C (Interquartile range; IQR=8).

In **Sweden**, six observations were conducted at the delivery and postnatal ward at Karolinska University Hospital between the 18th and 30th of June 2025 by a research assistant who was guided by the research team. The six observation sessions were comprised of two day-, two night- and two weekend- sessions. The first observation was used for mapping out both wards, while two others were spent at the delivery department, and three in the postnatal ward. The outside temperature varied depending on observation days between 12 °C with rain to 23 °C with sun. Inside, the temperature system (climate control) was set to 21.5 to 23 °C. Three short informal interviews of HCW complemented the observations. Two of the interviewees originated from generally warmer countries than Sweden, which could have influenced their perception of climate and heat in Sweden. The first interviewee was an auxiliary nurse who had worked at the hospital for three years. The second interviewee was a 25-year-old student finishing their education in nursing who had only been at the hospital for a month. The last interviewee was a 66-year-old woman who had worked as a midwife for 30 years, of which 15 were at the Karolinska Hospital.

Observers took handwritten notes or recorded audio-notes on their phones while in the facilities, and then typed these up and elaborated on them in fieldnotes afterwards. They followed an open-ended observation guide to steer the focus of the observations. The main areas of observation and informal conversations included infrastructure (including mapping the facility), clinical practices and patient care (not observed in Sweden), interpersonal relations amongst staff, relations between staff, patients and companions at the facility, and common strategies to cool down.

In **Zimbabwe**, observation journals and transcripts were preliminarily analysed after the first period of fieldwork, to inform the subsequent period of fieldwork. In **South Africa**, a senior social scientist read the fieldnotes in real time to monitor the quality of notetaking and identify key themes as they were emerging. Feedback

was then provided to all four observers in weekly meetings to ensure that data were robust and study objectives addressed. In **Sweden**, observation notes were written up in the form of a report and a presentation with the wider mixed-methods HCW study researchers took place for discussion of the results.

3.3.2 In-depth interviews

In-depth interviews (IDIs) are a qualitative research method to gather detailed information and insights from individuals about their experiences, beliefs, perspectives, and behaviours. This method involves engaging in one-on-one, open-ended conversations with participants, allowing researchers to explore topics in depth and gain a nuanced understanding of the subject matter. The IDIs offer data that extend across the study objectives of the HCWs study. More specifically, the IDIs help us gain an understanding of how heat affects HCWs' work performance, quality of care, health, and wellbeing (study objective 1); document HCWs' coping mechanisms and heat adaptation behaviour (study objective 2); and provide descriptive findings to inform the co-design of heat adaptation interventions that are appropriate for health facility settings (study objective 3).

In **South Africa** and **Zimbabwe**, health workers in each of the larger clinics and in the smaller clinics were purposively sampled for in-depth interviews (Appendix 7.2). Participants were selected amongst those working in maternal and newborn care, and included a mix of genders, ages, and roles (midwife, doctors, etc.). In South Africa, the IDIs were conducted with HCW on a one-on-one basis in a private setting and in English unless participants were more comfortable in another language (e.g., isiZulu, Sesotho or Shona). In Zimbabwe, the language of data collection was Shona.

These interviews in South Africa and Zimbabwe were informed by the insights from participant observation, as researchers began interviews with health workers only after they had undertaken one or two weeks of observation, first. Participants

had the opportunity to explain their practices regarding heat and their recommendations to improve the conditions related to this topic at work. After obtaining informed consent, interviews were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed (and translated into English if necessary) for analysis.

In **Sweden** interviews were undertaken separately from the observations; they preceded the observations and were conducted at Swedish antenatal maternity care services and child health centres. Interviews were conducted between 29 May and 1 August 2025. All ten participants were registered nurses, one of them had postgraduate education in community health, another in children's health and psychiatric health and two of them had a postgraduate education in midwifery. The participants were all women between 43-56 years old and had been working 1.2-7 years at their current workplace, but had a total of 5.5-32.5 years of experience working as healthcare workers. Their main duty was patient care, and one of them additionally was tasked as the labour union's safety representative at the workplace.

Interviews in all three countries covered the following topics: impact of hotter and cooler temperatures on wellbeing and health; influence of temperatures outside of work (home, commuting); influence of temperatures at work on productivity, wellbeing, and patient care; own adaptations already undertaken to cope with heat (including behavioural and structural adaptations); official measures by organising bodies; and recommendations going forward.

3.3.3 Key informant interviews

The purpose of key informant interviews (KIIs) was to learn the perspective of key informants on the magnitude of heat effect on HCWs (study objective 1) and gather their opinions on the feasibility of future adaptation (study objective 4).

Qualitative key informant interviews were held with individuals in the community and potentially in posts of expertise/authority identified through fieldwork as

being sources of information on adaptation strategies, HCW wellbeing, and quality of care, if interviews with health workers or participant observation indicated that they have additional information that could be useful to responding to our study objectives. The interviews in **South Africa** were conducted in May-August 2024, with 10 key informants, while in **Zimbabwe**, these took place in November-December 2024, with 15 key informants. No KIIs were carried out in Sweden.

3.3.4 Time-motion study

The time-motion study, embedded within the broader HIGH Horizons project, is designed to examine how heat stress affects healthcare workers' adherence to evidence-based intrapartum care processes. It employs a cross-sectional observational approach, with data collected in two public hospitals: (i) Mamelodi hospital in **South Africa** and (ii) Mount Darwin Hospital in **Zimbabwe**. Both settings provide comprehensive emergency obstetric care in resource-limited environments. The full statistical analysis plan for the time-motion study is published on Zenodo (Gon & Fardousi, 2025).

As no validated time-motion tool for intrapartum care existed prior to the study, a bespoke data collection instrument was developed. The tool was informed by WHO guidance and other relevant literature, and refined through two consultations with obstetricians to ensure all possible tasks performed by skilled birth attendants—including those not recommended by WHO—were represented (World Health Organization, 2015, 2018, 2022; World Health Organization et al., 2015). Additional piloting with local midwives in Zimbabwe and South Africa allowed for context-specific adaptations. By the start of formal data collection, the team was satisfied that the tool contained a code for every possible observed task during labour, delivery, and immediate postpartum care.

The study was restricted to intrapartum care, defined as care provided from admission to a labour room through to completion of the third stage of labour

(delivery of the placenta) and immediate newborn care. Prenatal and postnatal care were excluded, as were planned or emergency caesarean sections. While deliveries that developed complications were recorded, the management of these complications was beyond the study's analytical scope. An "observation session" began when a labouring mother was admitted to a labour room and ended with the completion of the third stage of labour, or earlier if data collection became impractical. Contextual differences between sites affected the nature of sessions—for example, in Mt Darwin Hospital, only women in active labour were transferred to the labour cubicle, while those in the latent phase waited elsewhere. Two data collectors were trained in Zimbabwe and South Africa remotely by researchers at LSHTM, with support from the research team in CeSHHAR and Wits RHI. The training involved in-office meetings, and piloting in the Mt Darwin hospital. In the former, the data collectors were introduced to the time-motion method, trained on the tool using staged scenarios, providing immediate feedback by LSHTM. During piloting, double entry observation was conducted by the data collectors and their field manager. After each field visit, the data collectors had a debrief meeting with the trainers, discussing recorded data and other observations. While our tool includes tasks related to the immediate newborn care, in the context of Mt Darwin hospital, it was not feasible to record this as the newborn is usually taken to another cubicle where they are cared for before returning to mother. We therefore focused on care offered to mothers. Similarly, it was not practical to observe and record when midwives took breaks since midwives usually take breaks outside the cubicles.

Data collection took place over two distinct climatic periods—one hot season and one cooler season—between October 2023 and July 2024 in Zimbabwe, and between February and September 2024 in South Africa. Observations were conducted on weekdays, during morning and afternoon shifts, with some night shift sessions in Zimbabwe, but none in South Africa for safety reasons.

Primary outcomes reflected the quality of intrapartum care processes, drawing on WHO Labour Care Guide standards and quality-of-care frameworks. These were divided into:

- **Labour stage-independent outcomes:** Respectful care, effective communication, provision of support, and frequency of breaks.
- **Labour stage-dependent outcomes:** Whether the woman was left alone during active labour; whether foetal or maternal monitoring occurred (*First and second stages of labour*); whether complete newborn care was performed (*third stage and early postpartum*); and whether unrecommended labour-accelerating practices were used (*Late first stage and second stage of labour*).

For full definitions of these outcomes, see Table 15 in Appendix 7.4.

The primary exposure was the mean Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) (International Organization for Standardization, 2004) recorded indoors in the hour preceding delivery. While not presented in this report, sensitivity analyses are planned to explore secondary exposure measures capturing the intensity and duration of heat exposure during shifts, with missing indoor data supplemented from thermally similar rooms or outdoor ERA-5 reanalysis datasets. Descriptive analyses summarised session characteristics, outcomes, and exposures, stratified by country (Table 15 in Appendix 7.4). Mixed-effects regression models with robust standard errors clustered at the midwife level were used to estimate associations between heat stress and quality-of-care outcomes. Model selection was guided by diagnostic tests, and non-linear relationships were explored using Generalised Additive Models where appropriate. Covariates included session length, shift, country, complications, type of birth, parity, workload, hours worked before delivery, years of experience, age, and cadre. Missing data—anticipated mainly from sporadic observer errors—were assumed missing at random. Analyses were

conducted in Stata SE v18 and R, with effect sizes and 95% confidence intervals reported, applying a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$.

3.3.5 Healthcare workers' questionnaire survey

To investigate the impact of heat in the three focus countries (study objective 1), the survey aimed to document perceived mental health and wellbeing indicators, stress and anxiety levels, dehydration, perceived work intensity, and perceived heat stress by HCWs characteristics. Lastly, the survey explores the healthcare workers perspectives on categories of interventions that might be implemented in South Africa and Zimbabwe.

3.3.5.1 Data collection processes

The survey was self-administered electronically using a smart device. Data collection comprised hot (September-November 2023 in Zimbabwe and February-March 2024 in South Africa) and cool season (June- July 2023 in South Africa and Zimbabwe). For exact dates for data collection per country see Table 10 in Appendix 7.2. In Sweden, data collection for the hot season took place between 2nd of June and 16th of July 2025 for the hot season and a further round of survey is planned to start later this year (2025) for the cold season. Responses to the questionnaire, which is available in English, Shona and Swedish, were uploaded to the Open Data Kit (ODK) platform for South Africa and Zimbabwe questionnaires, and to the REDCap platform for Sweden.

Eligible participants included all HCWs and staff working in the antenatal, obstetrics and labour wards, and neonatal wards or clinics in South Africa and Zimbabwe. These included cadres such as nurses, auxiliary nurses, medically trained staff such as obstetricians and paediatricians, junior staff and students, allied healthcare workers. We included participants who were 18 years old and above, and who had consented to participate in the study. In South Africa, research staff used a quota-based convenience sampling approach. They

monitored recruitment to approximate proportional representation across cadres, based on staff count in the MNCH wards of each facility. In Zimbabwe all eligible HCWs were invited to participate. In Sweden, the research team used two recruitment strategies: an announcement on the KI website; emails to different hospitals in Stockholm. In total, we recruited 81 healthcare workers in each season in South Africa out of 190 (82 at Stanza Bopape CHC and 108 at Mamelodi District Hospital), while in Zimbabwe, we collected data from 56 participants out of 62 eligible participants in each season due to being on annual leave or too busy. In Sweden, we recruited 64 participants.

3.3.5.2 Outcome measures

❖ Mental health indicators

To capture the heat impact on mental health outcomes, we used validated tools to collect data on three mental health constructs. First, the WHO Wellbeing Index for Health Workers provides a measure of self-reported mental health status. It includes the same five questions as the WHO-5 Wellbeing Index, which is available in 30 languages (Topp et al., 2015). Psychological status (perceived stress scale; PSS) includes questions on general feelings and thoughts of stress over the past month, with 5 categories of responses: (“never” to “very often”). We used the PSS-4 version (Vallejo et al., 2018). Generalised anxiety disorder (GAD-7) has 7 questions, each with 4 possible response categories (“not at all” to “nearly every day”). Additionally, we included questions to record perceived heat stress, perceived physical intensity at work, and thermal comfort.

❖ Urine-specific gravity

We used urine-specific gravity (USG), an indicator of hydration level as a proxy measure of heat impact on physical health (Flasar, 2008). Each healthcare worker was asked to provide a spot urine sample at the end of her or his work shift on the same day that the survey was administered. These specimens were then analysed to determine urine-specific gravity as an objective biomarker of hydration status.

We classified mild-to-moderate hypovolaemic dehydration as a urine-specific gravity value > 1.020 .

❖ **Perceived heat strain**

Perceived heat strain was defined and measured via four self-reported dimensions, each referring to the participant's experience on the hottest workday in the preceding week. Fatigue was rated on a five-point scale from "I'm not tired at all (0)" through to "I'm so exhausted I desire to have a break (4)". Sweating was captured on an identical 0–4 scale, with 0 indicating no sweat and 4 indicating severe sweat. Thirst was assessed from "I don't get thirsty (0)" to "my mouth and throat get dry... (4)". Thermal comfort was likewise scored from "Comfortable (0)" to "So uncomfortable I want to quit my job (4)".

3.3.5.3 Exposure measures

Mental health indices and perceived heat strain outcomes were analysed against outdoor heat stress data obtained from the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis data (a publicly available global dataset) for each facility's coordinates, with hourly 2 m-air temperature, relative humidity and surface radiation extracted via the Copernicus Climate Data Store (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2025). WBGT was then calculated from these measurements using the ISO 7243 formula.

The calculation and time frame of the heat stress exposure variable were aligned with the questionnaire prompts. For mental health indices, we used the average WBGT at the hour the questionnaire was completed, whereas for perceived heat strain outcomes, we used the maximum WBGT recorded in the seven days preceding participation in the study.

3.3.5.4 Statistical analyses

We conducted descriptive analysis, providing summary statistics for the outcomes of interest as appropriate, showing frequencies and percentages for categorical variable, and means with standard deviation for continuous variables or medians

with interquartile ranges if variables are non-normally distributed (see Tables 11-14 in Appendix 7.3).

Dehydration (defined as USG ≥ 1.020) was analysed against season (hot vs cool) and adjusted for covariates (age, sex, hospital vs clinic, presence of chronic diseases, country, shift length, number of breaks, years of experience) using generalised estimating equations (GEEs) with a logistic link. A binomial distribution was specified for the outcome, and an exchangeable working correlation structure was chosen to account for within-participant clustering of repeated measurements.

We assessed the impact of heat on mental health indices (WHO-5, PSS-4, GAD-7) using generalised estimating equations with a Gaussian family and identity link, accounting for repeated measurements with an exchangeable correlation structure.

For perceived heat strain outcomes (thermal comfort, sweating, thirst, and fatigue), we created binary indicators: 'comfortable' as the reference for thermal comfort; 'I do not feel thirsty' for thirst; 'I do not feel tired' for fatigue; and for sweating, values 1–3 were grouped as "less sweating" and 4–5 as "more sweating." Associations with heat stress were then analysed using GEEs, again correcting for repeated measures. Models were adjusted for age, sex, facility type, health status, and country.

Data management and statistical analyses were conducted using Stata, R and Python.

3.3.6 Time-series analysis of routine data

We retrieved data from three types of routine records: maternal case records, staff attendance registers, and birth registers, covering the years 2019–2023. Data extraction was conducted in our facilities in Zimbabwe (Mount Darwin District Hospital, Chitse Clinic, and Dotito Clinic) and South Africa (Mamelodi Hospital and

Stanza Bopape CHC). These sources provide information on staff availability, service utilisation, and maternal and newborn outcomes.

The analysis aimed to examine the impact of ambient temperature on staff attendance and selected clinical outcomes. Staff attendance, derived from facility registers, serves as a proxy for productivity. In parallel, maternal and newborn health indicators, such as intrapartum stillbirths and delivery outcomes, are evaluated to explore potential effects of heat exposure on quality of care.

For statistical analysis, we apply Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), incorporating a Distributed Lag Non-linear Model (DLNM) to capture both immediate and delayed effects of outdoor heat stress. Ambient temperature is modelled using flexible splines, a B-spline with two degrees of freedom. We controlled for long-term trends and seasonality through smoothing functions (natural spline function with 7 knots for each year). Outcomes include daily staff availability and maternal/newborn indicators, with analyses stratified by facility type where appropriate. A key limitation is that routine records may have incomplete or inconsistently documented data, and reasons for staff absence are not always recorded, which may affect interpretation of results.

This is an ongoing analysis and we present here our preliminary findings on the impact of heat stress on absenteeism, capture through data from staff attendance.

3.3.7 Monitoring of thermal exposures

For study objective 5 thermal exposures in the selected healthcare facilities in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden are measured, through observation and monitoring of the indoor and outdoor thermal environment. Air temperature, air humidity, and globe temperature were logged continuously at 5 to 30 min intervals in selected rooms in all facilities. Instrumentation was deployed in the first rooms in two facilities in Zimbabwe in September 2023 and the remaining facilities

followed between October and December 2023 as more measurement devices became available and in parallel to the initiation of other study components (see Table 10 in Appendix 7.2 for timing). Measurements continue to date. Deliverable D2.8 provides a detailed description of the instrumentation and the measurements, and presents preliminary findings (Toftum et al., 2024). In that report, indoor thermal exposures in Zimbabwe and South Africa were assessed based on the measured temperature and air humidity and the calculated WBGT for a one-year period spanning 1 November 2023 to 31 October in Zimbabwe 2024 and 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024 in South Africa. For comparison, findings from Sweden were also included in the results section (with data from 1 November 2023 – 31 December 2024).

Hourly values of outdoor weather data were retrieved from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2025; Muñoz Sabater, 2019) for the latitudes and longitudes corresponding to the locations of the clinics.

4 Results

This section summarises qualitative findings presented in submitted or unpublished scientific papers (Machingura et al., Unpublished manuscript; Munyewende et al., unpublished manuscript; Sibanda et al., unpublished manuscript), along with original quantitative and qualitative analyses undertaken for this report but not yet written up for peer-reviewed scientific publications.

4.1 Description of facilities

4.1.1 South Africa

In **Stanza Bopape** Community Health Centre, the **antenatal clinic** faces challenges with cramped working spaces, high patient loads, and limited cooling

options. Patients wait in a small, shaded area outside and enter the facility only when called, as there is no space inside the facility to wait. At the time of the study, the facility lacked efficient ventilation, with a broken ceiling fan and small windows located high up that were difficult to open. Hydration options were limited due to inconsistent water availability: water coolers remained empty for long periods of time and a drinking fountain produced only warm water as the sun shined on it for parts of the day.

The **maternity unit** in this facility, which manages low-risk pregnancies, operates with a fast-paced environment. In the reception, at the time of the study, there was an old wall-mounted fan that was not in use and an air conditioner that was seldom switched on – even on hot days. There was neither fan nor air conditioning in the labour rooms and the air conditioner in the postnatal ward was almost never used. Unsurprisingly, the atmosphere in the unit overall was stuffy. Healthcare workers explained their non-reliance on cooling technologies as a strategy to protect the babies (coming for their 3-day postnatal check-up) from cold air or breezes. Observers noted some hygiene concerns, with flies in the unit, possibly related to refuse piling up outside the facility during a municipal workers' strike. Patients used an outside tap for water, and staff often brought their own filled water bottles to work.

In contrast, **Mamelodi Hospital's antenatal clinic** boasted a spacious, well-ventilated waiting area with functioning air conditioners, providing a calm atmosphere and comfortable temperatures even on busy days. There was a functioning water cooler for patients but the water cooler for staff use was unplugged and not in use at the time of our observations.

In the **maternity unit of the hospital**, the small observation cubicles and delivery rooms faced temperature challenges due to power cuts, non-functional ceiling fans, and non-functioning remote controls for the air conditioners. Windows and curtains were opened wide to allow a breeze into the rooms. Privacy screens made with thick cloth that enable multiple patients to be seen simultaneously were perceived to make the already cramped space feel even hotter.

In the **neonatal intensive care unit (NICU)**, air conditioners were switched off for most of the day and there were considerable heating challenges in this space owing to the use of incubators in small cubicles.

In the **postnatal ward**, water coolers were either empty a lot of the time or not used, and air conditioning remained largely switched off, owing to the concern about exposing infants to cold air. Yet, staff and patients alike found the ward uncomfortably warm. From our observation notes:

"I ask a midwife in postnatal as to why they have it off as two of the mothers that are there are fanning themselves due to heat. The postnatal midwife answers, "we are preventing hypothermia [in babies] here". All the babies are dressed in very warm clothes and covered with thick blankets. Their mothers say they are feeling the heat but understand why the air conditioners cannot be used – they need to keep their babies warm." (14 November, Maternity unit)

4.1.2 Zimbabwe

The **antenatal care unit** at **Mt Darwin District Hospital** consists of six working stations, including registration, family planning, antenatal examination room, postnatal consultation room, treatment room, and immunisation (extended programme on immunisation). In an informal conversation held with the nurse in charge, it was revealed that, due to limited space in this department, the staff

decided to decongest the area by moving the registration and family planning stations outside. However, the immunisation station is situated in an island area that lacks proper ventilation, as there are no windows, and the room is poorly lit.

Windows in the **maternity ward** at Mt Darwin District Hospital were always open during the day and night at the time of the observations. They remained open even during delivery because of the hot weather and because of their higher positioning. In the smaller facilities, the windows were closed during deliveries, for privacy. It was noted that all windows at all the working stations at Dotito rural health centre and Chitse rural health centre were opened throughout the day and the curtains were tied up to allow free circulation of air and only closed during deliveries.

Patients were received by a primary care nurse, nurse aide, and student nurse in shade 1 where they went through health education on different topics. Patients were then registered in the electronic register, referred to shade 2 (green shade) for vital signs check (measurement of height, weight and arm circumference and temperature), stamping of health cards. Cards were updated according to the service one requires. Patients were then referred to their respective stations, such as the outpatient department, antenatal care examination room, postnatal care examination room, expanded programme for immunisation station, opportunistic infections department, and HIV testing services centre.

At **Chitse** rural health centre patients initially sat at the outpatient department shed to protect themselves from the direct sun. A nurse aide conducted the weight and temperature checks, while the other nurse aide took down the details in the patient's books. The patients would then move to the benches leading to their respective treatment areas, which were also shaded by the overlapping roofing of the buildings. Usually, the second nurse aide then followed the patients and took in their details in the electronic health register system. Once that had happened, the patients would then proceed to their rooms of assistance. The outside of the

clinic had a small cluster of trees where the patients and vendors utilised the shades to sell their wares. Some rested there regularly to buy refreshments soon after leaving the clinic.

Morning breaks in the Family Child Health (FCH) department (Mt Darwin Hospital) were typically 30 minutes long, but this duration may have varied depending on the patient load. During these breaks, the three midwives, under observation took turns to go for tea. In the afternoon, particularly from 12 pm onwards, the FCH department tends to be less busy. At this time, the staff members, including four midwives and one nurse aide, took a break after lunch, which lasted from 2 pm until 4 pm when they finished their shifts. They usually sat by the veranda during their break, although it should be noted that the veranda could be warm in the afternoon.

It seemed that the healthcare workers in the mentioned health facilities were facing various challenges related to water availability and heat. They initially brought their water bottles from home but had to start buying water from the tuckshop due to water shortages. The **Dotito rural health clinic** faced water challenges and had to refer patients to a nearby borehole. Similarly, at Mt Darwin Hospital, there were water shortages at the time of the observations. In the vicinity of the hospital, there is a borehole located approximately 100 meters away from the hospital gate. In situations when there was no water available, the visitors' toilets were closed, leaving visitors with limited options. Consequently, visitors were compelled to use Blair toilets (a type of pit latrine), which are situated far from the maternity ward. The distance and lack of accessibility to these toilets created challenges for visitors, especially during night-time, as the area was poorly lit.

4.1.3 Sweden

Karolinska University Hospital, inaugurated in 2018, is among the world's top 10 hospitals. With 15,000 employees and 1,340 beds, it employs cutting-edge medical and green technologies, as well as innovative inter-disciplinary management models.

At Karolinska University Hospital, the facilities in both wards observed **(the delivery and postnatal ward)** were well-equipped and in good condition. The outdoor temperature did not exceed 23 °C during the observation period. All rooms, offices, and corridors were air conditioned. The temperature was often put on minimum, or “comfort mode” (21.5 - 22 °C). The indoor

temperature generally felt comfortable, if not slightly cold. There were no observations of overheating, sweating, or use of fans in the offices. Some workers had extra layers and chunky socks on, while others had the standard short-sleeved uniform, suggesting that the perception of temperature varied from person to person. One younger HCW mentioned feeling cold due to tiredness. Showers were available in the changing rooms on the second floor and within the delivery ward. However, no staff mentioned using them and a worker was unaware of their presence.

Warmer areas: One area that was described as noticeably warm was the small glass-walled offices. One interviewee reported that AC and fans were often used in these rooms during warm days. Another explained that colder colleagues could forget to turn the temperature down, making moments like “reporting” warmer, as many workers accumulate in the small office. Another younger HCW reported feeling reluctant to lower the

temperature for their own comfort, to respect other colder colleagues.

Apart from the offices, an interviewee reported turning the temperature down when cleaning rooms, as it is physically demanding. While the temperature was never described or observed as an important source of discomfort, a HCW mentioned the lack of access to fresh air in the ward in an informal conversation. No windows can be opened, and two workers expressed that the air could feel humid.

Exposure to sun light: Another factor that was brought up by HCWs during two interviews was access to sunlight. Indeed, corridors had no windows. Natural light entered mainly through the central glass-walled “atrium” by the café. The ninth floor (delivery ward) received more daylight due to proximity to the top floor, compared to the fifth floor (postnatal).

There were no strong differences in light levels between a sunny and a rainy day. An interviewee confirmed that they were often unaware of the outside weather. Although patient rooms have windows, blinds are frequently used for mothers' and newborns' privacy and comfort. While the break rooms had glass walls, only the light from the atrium entered them, and some workers were observed not putting the lights on in the break room.

Balconies were available opposite to the wards but were not observed to be used. An interviewee said they used to eat lunch outside at the old hospital, but that it was difficult to do that at the new hospital. They reported that the lunch breaks were 30 minutes long, not allowing enough time to go out. Indeed, most breaks were observed to be taken in the ward's break room.

4.2 Theme 1: Dehydration

Dehydration provides a valuable outcome measure for measuring the impact of heat on healthcare workers' physical health as it was assessed objectively through urine specific gravity (USG) in South Africa and Zimbabwe. In this section, we first summarise the quantitative results and then explore the lived experience of dehydration among healthcare workers in the three countries.

4.2.1 Levels and determinants of dehydration

Dehydration was higher in summer in both countries, consistent with greater heat exposure. In South Africa, 53% of participants were dehydrated in summer

compared to 45% in winter (dehydrated if USG ≥ 1.020), with median USG values of 1.021 versus 1.019 ($p = 0.1081$). In Zimbabwe, 75% of participants were dehydrated in summer versus 59% in winter, with median USG of 1.024 versus 1.022 ($p = 0.0477$). The seasonal increase was statistically significant in Zimbabwe but not in South Africa, highlighting potential country-specific differences in hydration patterns. Paired lines in Figure 1 illustrate individual-level variability.

Figure 1. Violin plots, showing the distribution of USG values, with individual data points and paired connections between summer and winter for the same participants

In both univariate and multivariate analyses, working in Zimbabwe was consistently associated with higher odds of dehydration compared with South Africa, with the association remaining statistically significant after adjustment for other factors. Working during winter and taking three or more breaks per shift were both associated with lower odds of dehydration in univariate analysis, and these protective effects persisted in the multivariate model, although the association for winter was borderline significant in the adjusted analysis. Other

factors, including age, sex, shift duration, chronic illness, body mass index (BMI), years of experience, and work environment, were not significantly associated with dehydration in either analysis.

Table 2 shows detailed results of the GEE multivariable analysis. We see that healthcare workers in Zimbabwe had over three times the odds of dehydration compared to those in South Africa (odds ratio; OR = 3.07, 95% CI: 1.25–7.53, $p = 0.01$). Taking three or more breaks during a shift was borderline protective (OR = 0.49, 95% CI: 0.24–1.00, $p = 0.05$). Dehydration tended to be less likely in winter compared to summer (OR = 0.62, $p = 0.06$).

Table 2. Multivariable analysis of determinants of dehydration ($USG \geq 1.020$) in South Africa and Zimbabwe

Variable	Category/Level	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	P-Value
Age	21 to 30 years	Reference	
	Above 30 years	0.67 (0.22-2.09)	0.49
Country	South Africa	Reference	
	Zimbabwe	3.07 (1.25-7.53)*	0.01
Sex	Female	Reference	
	Male	0.45 (0.14-1.47)	0.19
Season	Summer	Reference	
	Winter	0.62 (0.37-1.03)	0.06
Shift duration	Less or Equal to 8 hours	Reference	
	Above 8 hours	1.17 (0.63-2.18)	0.62
Chronic illness	No	Reference	
	Yes	1.32 (0.66-2.63)	0.43
Breaks taken	Less than 3 breaks taken	Reference	
	3 or more breaks	0.49 (0.24-1.00)	0.05
Years of experience	0-10	Reference	
	11-20	1.20 (0.58-2.46)	0.63
	21+	2.30 (0.74-7.13)	0.15
Work environment	Both (Indoor and Outdoor)	Reference	
	Indoor	1.23 (0.53-2.89)	0.63
	Outdoor	1.21 (0.34-4.35)	0.77
BMI	BMI	1.05 (0.98-1.13)	0.13

4.2.2 Perceptions of dehydration and thirst

As noted earlier, dehydration levels were high in both countries, although the seasonal difference was statistically significant only in Zimbabwe. We now turn to the perceptions of heat and its impact on healthcare workers in this section.

➤ South Africa

In the qualitative interviews, HCWs in South Africa described dehydration and thirst as common consequences of extreme heat, exacerbated by the demands of their work, which often prevented regular water breaks. Busy shifts, particularly during high-delivery days, left little opportunity to hydrate:

"Like today, I have not taken any drink. You forget. You forget to drink water." (ZA-02-012)

Inadequate staffing intensified the problem, as workers were unable to pause or take breaks without disrupting patient care:

"...when you don't have enough staff, you can't take breaks... you're hot... you're also not drinking water. So yeah, like you can pass out in theatre..." (ZA-01-046)

Ethnographic observations corroborated these accounts, noting limited access to drinking water – often a single small cooler shared by staff and patients – and that nurses frequently went entire shifts without drinking. Concerns over municipal water safety and the need to avoid bathroom breaks further deterred hydration. As one HCW explained:

"And now I'm scared of drinking water in the tap. We don't even know what they pour in there..." (ZA-01-041)

Overall, extreme heat, high workloads, staffing shortages, and water quality concerns combined to hinder adequate hydration, posing risks to HCWs' health, wellbeing, and performance.

➤ **Zimbabwe**

In Zimbabwe, interviews and observations showed how hydration and dehydration were intimately related to other conditions at work: heat, stagnant air, busy working hours. Perceptions of dehydration were closely linked to these circumstances, which included prolonged standing, inadequate hydration, and high cognitive demands. Respondents told us how these factors combined to make HCWs vulnerable to dizziness, headaches, and difficulty concentrating. Some described feeling physically unstable or mentally “foggy” during hot shifts. Dehydration was considered to be a persistent problem, prompting informal coping strategies such as “water buddy” systems and personal water bottles labelled with names to encourage regular drinking breaks.

➤ **Sweden**

In Sweden, observations showed the availability of water and practices surrounding hydration amongst the staff at Karolinska Hospital. Some tasks are physically demanding such as cleaning rooms, quickly changing sheets for new patients, and walking (or even running) long distances between wards and rooms throughout the day. Several water stations were observed across the facilities of both wards. Water was easily accessible around the centrally located café area, with a water cooler offering sparkling, cold or ambient water. Water could also be obtained from a tap next to the cooler, and the café itself offered water as well as additional refreshments like cordial (“saft”). Moreover, staff bathrooms could also probably be used for water access, though drinking behaviour in the bathrooms (or refilling of water bottles there) could not be observed in these facilities.

Despite easy access to water, the observed use of the water stations was limited. The HCWs often used water stations for patients rather than for themselves. Observed water breaks were usually associated with meals, sometimes only consisting in filling a small glass of water.

HCWs were also frequently seen walking and drinking at the same time. Some staff had personal water bottles but rarely carried them around during shifts. Bottles were seen in the break rooms or left on tables outside of patient rooms.

The three informally interviewed HCWs at Karolinska expressed that they were personally bad at taking time to drink water at work. One confirmed that others had water bottles and that there were sufficient opportunities to drink water in the ward. Another mentioned that water could be accessed from the larger staff room outside the ward (note: this area was not observed due to lack of access), but that it was more convenient to take water from the break room in the ward due to its proximity. They also mentioned that it was easier to plan for water breaks at the postnatal ward, due to shorter tasks and more flexible tasks, whereas working at the delivery ward sometimes requires the HCWs to stay with the patient for longer times. Remembering to bring a water bottle in such situations is necessary. They also noted that it was too heavy to carry a water bottle in a pocket all day, leading to their bottles being left behind and used less frequently.

However, HCWs perceived that their colleagues were understanding if someone needed to take a quick hydration break. Finally, the third interviewee expressed that their mouth felt dry over the day and suspected that coffee consumption could lead to dehydration.

Coffee appeared to be the most consumed beverage, which could be easily accessed in break rooms and often seen in hand while walking in the corridors. Other observed types of beverages were soda or energy drinks in the office and in the break room, although this was not as common.

4.3 Theme 2: Psychological and perceived heat strain

4.3.1 Psychological stress, anxiety and wellbeing

Good mental health is essential for healthcare workers to remain fully focused on their tasks and deliver high quality care. In this section, we first present findings based on validated tools used in South Africa and Zimbabwe. We then examine how healthcare workers describe the impact of heat on their mental health, their coping mechanisms and the repercussions these have in other domains, such as communication.

4.3.1.1 Questionnaire survey results

In South Africa, healthcare workers reported slightly lower WHO-5 Wellbeing Index scores during the hot season compared to the cold season, with the median decreasing from 17.5 [IQR 11.0–21.0] to 16.0 [IQR 10.0–20.0]. Stress levels (PSS-4) were marginally higher in the hot season, with the median remaining at 7.0 but interquartile range shifting from 4.0–8.0 to 6.0–9.0. Similarly, generalised anxiety symptoms were more pronounced in the hot season, rising from a median of 4.0 [IQR 1.0–9.0] to 6.0 [IQR 2.0–10.0]. In Zimbabwe, a similar pattern emerged: wellbeing scores declined from a median of 16.0 [IQR 11.0–18.5] in the cold season to 14.0 [IQR 9.5–19.5] in the hot season, while stress levels slightly increased (median 7.0 [IQR 4.0–8.0] to 7.0 [IQR 5.0–9.0]). Anxiety symptoms also rose with heat, with median scores moving from 3.0 [IQR 0.5–7.0] in the cold season to 5.0 [IQR 0.0–7.0] in the hot season. Despite those differences, crude statistical tests comparing the hot vs cold data showed no significant differences.

When using regression approaches with heat stress WBGT temperature as an exposure (Figure 2), higher outdoor heat stress was associated with lower WHO wellbeing scores and higher perceived stress in crude models, with little evidence of an association with generalised anxiety disorder. After adjusting for age, sex,

health status, country and facility type, the negative association with wellbeing was slightly attenuated but still significant, while estimates for perceived stress and generalised anxiety disorder increased slightly, with little change in confidence interval width. For every increase in temperature by 1 C°, there was a decrease in the wellbeing score by 0.15 and an increase in the perceived stress score by 0.08, both adjusted for confounders. These findings suggest a potential adverse effect of heat on wellbeing and perceived stress, though estimates for anxiety are uncertain when both countries are combined. However, these findings hide differences between the two countries, with the results in South Africa being significantly associated with outdoor heat stress for two instruments and none for Zimbabwe only WHO wellbeing (see Figure 12 in appendix 7.3 for South Africa (left) and Zimbabwe (right)). This may be due to smaller sample if countries analysed separately. In Sweden, the full quantitative analysis is paused until the data for the cold season is available, with descriptive analysis of the responses of the hot season presented in Table 13 in Appendix 7.3.

Figure 2. Heat stress association with changes in mental health indicators

Table 3. The impact of average outdoor heat stress temperature (WBGT) on mental health indicators

	WHO-5 Wellbeing Index		Perceived Stress Score 4		Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7	
	Coefficient [95% CI]	p-value	Coefficient [95% CI]	p-value	Coefficient [95% CI]	p-value
Unadjusted model						
Average outdoor heat stress	-0.16* [-0.29--0.02]	0.0215	0.07 [-0.00- 0.14]	0.0573	0.05 [-0.05- 0.15]	0.3411
Adjusted model						
Average outdoor heat stress	-0.15* [-0.29--0.02]	0.0234	0.08* [0.01- 0.15]	0.0301	0.08 [-0.02- 0.18]	0.1220
Has a medical condition						
No	0.00		0.00		0.00	
Yes	-0.61 [-2.33- 1.11]	0.4867	0.12 [-0.63- 0.87]	0.7566	1.14 [-0.32- 2.61]	0.1265
Q2_2. What is your sex?						
Female	0.00		0.00		0.00	
Male	1.10 [-1.49- 3.70]	0.4037	-0.49 [-1.56- 0.58]	0.3665	-0.18 [-2.36- 1.99]	0.8710
Other	10.15*** [8.48-11.82]	0.0000	1.22** [0.41- 2.02]	0.0031	-4.23*** [-5.38--3.08]	0.0000
Country						
South Africa	0.00		0.00		0.00	
Zimbabwe	-1.14 [-3.26- 0.99]	0.2939	-0.39 [-1.35- 0.57]	0.4207	-2.29** [-3.92--0.65]	0.0061
Facility type						
Hospital	0.00		0.00		0.00	
CHC	-1.14 [-2.88- 0.59]	0.1968	0.11 [-0.67- 0.88]	0.7897	0.13 [-1.35- 1.61]	0.8632
Age category						
1	0.00		0.00		0.00	
2	0.77 [-1.62- 3.17]	0.5265	0.18 [-0.92- 1.27]	0.7529	-0.92 [-2.89- 1.06]	0.3623
3	0.78 [-2.04- 3.60]	0.5867	-0.30 [-1.51- 0.91]	0.6237	-0.09 [-2.30- 2.12]	0.9351
4	1.14 [-1.48- 3.75]	0.3946	-0.29 [-1.36- 0.77]	0.5893	0.36 [-1.76- 2.48]	0.7383
5	2.17 [-0.16- 4.49]	0.0682	-0.36 [-1.48- 0.76]	0.5323	-0.56 [-2.82- 1.71]	0.6303

Note: Estimates from linear regression. *** p<0.001 ** p<0.01 * p<0.05

4.3.1.2 Qualitative findings

➤ South Africa

HCWs in South Africa described extreme heat as having a pronounced impact on their mental and emotional wellbeing. Prolonged exposure left them physically drained and mentally fatigued, creating a sense of being “worn down” over the course of a shift. For some, the strain went beyond momentary discomfort, contributing to feelings of sadness and even depression. As one HCW put it,

“You get exhausted, mentally and physically” (ZA-02-012)

while another described the experience as

“exhaustion and, um, depression... it is just sad, sad, sad... I can't say I'm happy” (ZA-01-004)

The heat often eroded patience and tolerance, making it more difficult to remain calm during interactions with colleagues and patients. Several participants said they became more irritable and easily frustrated when working in hot, poorly ventilated rooms:

“Now this room is too hot... I cannot tolerate working here in this hot temperature” (ZA-02-013)

Another reflected,

“It's because we're irritated as well. It's very hot” (ZA-02-012)

This irritability sometimes spilled over into patient interactions, with one HCW acknowledging that,

“...when it's hot... you end up maybe shouting at the patient” (ZA-01-037)

Reducing communication and minimising socialising were further coping mechanisms. Several HCWs said that as the day progressed, the heat sapped their energy for conversation. Questions that were detailed and expansive in the morning became short and functional by afternoon:

“There would be less communication... in the morning, you were asking long questions, then your questions become shorter during that period” (ZA-02-012)

Some described avoiding interaction altogether,

“I just want to sit. I don't interact with them at all” (ZA-01-006)

or being less polite, though recognising that everyone was similarly

“hot and bothered” (ZA-01-046)

➤ **Zimbabwe**

In Zimbabwe, HCWs described how heat not only drained them physically but also heightened irritability, frustration, and emotional exhaustion, often spilling over into their interactions with patients and colleagues. Several midwives linked intense heat with reduced patience and communication breakdowns. Others described moments of emotional dysregulation:

“You may end up raising your voice... you will need a short rest because you would be hot and tired.” (ZW-MT-07-8)

“Others (colleagues) can get angry to the point of responding to the patients in a loud manner.” (ZW-MT-09-8)

Congested, overheated spaces intensified tensions:

“Due to the heat you get angry, and it also gets irritating when you have a lot of people around you, congesting the place... when I'm trying my best level to make things work.” (ZW-CH-03-6)

Lack of institutional support compounded stress, as one HCW noted:

“There are no policies with working in hot conditions... these things should be easily available for healthcare workers... but there's nothing.” (ZW-CHI-04-8)

Some participants reflected on how heat could subtly erode workplace relationships:

“When it’s hot, at times you cannot feel that you are going the wrong way [being too harsh] but because you are too tired you may end up not communicating nicely with other colleagues.” (ZW-MT-09-8)

Across accounts, heat stress emerged as both a physical and psychological hazard, undermining HCWs’ wellbeing, team cohesion, and patient care.

➤ **Sweden**

In the qualitative work in Sweden, psychological distress from elevated heat manifested itself also in philosophical ways beyond the practical ways involved maternal care. All except one participant said that they experienced the effects of climate change in Stockholm and expressed great general concern about the topic. One participant talked about the existential anxiety she felt during exposure of extreme heat, both in Sweden and abroad. Those who expressed concerns had made private lifestyle adaptations (choosing to use public transport over private vehicles, reducing material consumption, less meat consumption, etc.) to a larger extent, but felt that the government could do better. Some expressed that Region Stockholm (the institution responsible for healthcare in the region) works on reducing the impact of climate change, but there is far more that could be done. Many participants talked from an existential perspective about the extensive use of non-reusable products in healthcare and insufficient waste separation system at some facilities (for recycling). They all agreed that there will be increased demands on the health sector due to future climate change, but also due to the direct effect on people’s health. One example that was mentioned was that even newly built health facilities (Karolinska University Hospital) did not have sufficient ventilation, thus questioning the awareness among those planning for future healthcare.

Some mentioned that the seasonal variations in Swedish climate was a part of their life-worlds. Meaning, that by experiencing reduced seasonal variations due to climate change (the winters not as cold or uniform as previously), they felt

something had been lost the last years and affected them in a negative way. One participant expressed that recent winters were grey (no white snow enlightening the dark season) with mild temperatures, and subsequently traditional winter activities could not be performed like in the past, which affected both physical and psychological health negatively.

4.3.1.3 Summary of mental health findings

Heat negatively affects the mental health of healthcare workers, with survey data from South Africa and Zimbabwe showing that higher outdoor heat stress is associated with lower wellbeing and increased perceived stress, though links with anxiety are less clear. Qualitative findings reveal that extreme heat leads to mostly mental stress which then led to physical exhaustion, irritability, emotional fatigue, and reduced patience, often impairing communication and interpersonal interactions in both countries. In Sweden, heat-related psychological distress also includes existential concerns about climate change, prompting personal adaptations and highlighting perceived gaps in institutional support.

4.3.2 Subtheme: Cognitive-related abilities and focus

4.3.2.1 Qualitative findings

This sub-theme was only explored qualitatively, as no short and relevant scales for measuring cognition could be identified for inclusion in the individual survey questionnaire. Existing instruments are long and are often designed for special studies in older populations.

➤ South Africa

Hot days were seen by HCWs to impair focus, slow task completion, and cause lapses in memory. *"It's just not easy to concentrate in heat"* (ZA-01-039), one participant noted, while another explained that high temperatures could make them *"forget some other aspects"* of their work (ZA-02-012). Such effects were

particularly problematic for tasks requiring precision, such as documentation and patient assessments. As one worker admitted,

*“We get to be slow... especially in our ward... The person who's writing will be slow”
(ZA-01-039).*

➤ **Zimbabwe**

Healthcare workers reported that elevated temperatures have a negative impact on their concentration levels. As a result, this can lead to a decline in the quality of care they are able to deliver to their patients.

“[...] during hot seasons when the patient calls for attention sometimes, I don't immediately go to attend the patient, I ask her questions to make sure that she is now due for delivery before I go to attend to her because when the temperatures are too high, I do not feel like doing anything”. (ZW-MT-08-6)

There is a difference (in service delivery in winter and in summer) because at times when it is hot if you sit down, you can fall asleep due to the heat and concentration at times becomes very low as compared to the cold season.” (ZW-MT-13-1)

Many HCWs described cognitive fog and slower reflexes as particularly hazardous in emergency situations. As one explained:

“Heat makes the brain slow.” (ZW-MT-01-4)

➤ **Sweden**

Interview participants at the health clinics said that a common experience during days of heat exposure was feeling tired, unable to focus and postponing duties. None of the participants had experienced negative communication among colleagues, however, there was a shared experience of being negatively affected by the heat which was frequently spoken about among colleagues during the hot periods.

At the hospital, no cognitive-related or focus difficulties were observed reflecting the controlled temperature.

4.3.2.2 Summary of cognitive related findings

In South Africa and Zimbabwe, healthcare workers consistently reported that heat impaired their concentration, slowed task completion, and in some cases caused lapses in memory or delayed responses to patients, raising concerns for quality of care and safety in emergencies. By contrast, in Sweden, while clinic staff described tiredness and postponing tasks during hot periods, no major difficulties with concentration were reported, and no effects were observed in the hospital setting where temperatures were controlled.

4.3.3 Subtheme: Perceived physical heat strain

4.3.3.1 Questionnaire survey findings

To assess the impact of heat on perceived heat strain, the questionnaire included questions asking participants about their experiences of thermal comfort, thirst, sweating, and fatigue, around the hottest day in the past week. Figure 3 demonstrates the association between maximum Wet Bulb Globe Temperature and perceived heat strain among healthcare workers.

Figure 3. Heat stress association with perception of four heat strain indicators

Increases in WBGT were significantly associated with higher odds of reporting discomfort, thirst, sweating, and fatigue. Specifically:

- *Discomfort:* Higher WBGT was associated with greater odds of reporting feeling uncomfortable (OR = 1.20, 95% CI: 1.09–1.32, $p < 0.001$), indicating a direct impact of heat exposure on perceived physical wellbeing.
- *Thirst:* Elevated WBGT increased the likelihood of reporting thirst (OR = 1.15, 95% CI: 1.02–1.29, $p = 0.023$), consistent with higher dehydration findings reported earlier during periods of heat.
- *Sweating:* Increased WBGT was linked with higher sweating level (OR = 1.33, 95% CI: 1.19–1.47, $p < 0.001$), reflecting thermoregulatory responses to heat exposure.
- *Fatigue:* Workers reported higher odds of feeling tired with increasing WBGT (OR = 1.25, 95% CI: 1.10–1.43, $p < 0.001$), suggesting cumulative effects of heat stress on physical capacity.

Overall, these findings highlight consistent associations between rising WBGT and multiple dimensions of perceived heat strain.

4.3.3.2 Qualitative findings

In all three countries but particularly in South Africa and Zimbabwe, interviews revealed that health workers believed that heat affected certain people with certain health conditions more than others. We heard from healthcare workers who revealed being anaemic and requiring extra rest and time off of work during heatwaves; a midwife's eye problem becoming exacerbated through the heat which affected how patients perceived her; and another midwife describing recurrent heat rashes only experienced during heatwaves, leading to her to take time off of work until they cleared. Other staff spoke about their colleagues who were overweight and suffered from blood pressure spikes during extreme heat. In Sweden this observation restricted itself to post-menopausal women saying

they were now more sensitive to heat and to commenting on overweight as contributing to heat strain.

➤ **South Africa**

HCWs described a wide range of physical effects from working in hot conditions, including fatigue, dizziness, lethargy, dehydration, headaches, skin problems, and general discomfort. These symptoms often slowed their work, reduced comfort, and affected their ability to maintain dignity and professional appearance. Observations confirmed that in the CHC, HCWs struggled to sustain productivity in the heat, yet were often unable to take breaks due to heavy workloads.

"I become sluggish when it is hot." (ZA-01-006)

"...you're just not comfortable with the hot condition in the room." (ZA-01-039)

"...if it's too hot, a person becomes sleepy... [and when I am] in the normal ward, especially admission delivery area, it [becomes] a bit hectic." (ZA-01-001)

In labour wards, protective clothing—particularly plastic aprons—exacerbated discomfort:

"They are very hot [the uniform's plastic aprons] and are good for winter."

(ZA-01-007)

Excessive sweating was a persistent challenge, leaving HCWs feeling physically unwell, self-conscious, and sometimes unable to maintain their preferred appearance:

"Physically, with all the sweating, after some time, maybe afternoon, I feel as if I'm smelling... I wish I can just go and have shower, but I can't because I'm still at work.

Yeah. That's the part that affects me." (ZA-01-042)

"...as time goes by during day even the sweat will tell you that it's very hot..." (ZA-01-039)

"...you can see now that now that one is feeling hot. One, two, three. ... She [the HCW] will be wet and sweating." (ZA-02-013)

"...now and again, I'm wiping. So now I can't even use make-up because it's pointless... I would like to wear make-up stuff but it won't last... I just want to look good... mentally it affects me." (ZA-01-042)

Observations documented visible signs of heat strain, particularly in poorly ventilated labour rooms lacking fans or air conditioning:

"The nurses are really working hard and active on this day especially in the labour rooms, as midwife comes out sweating... The midwife comes out to wipe her face and one can see the annoyance on her face as she chats to her colleagues..."
(EO 09NOV23 CHC, max temperature: 29 °C)

Some HCWs reported dizziness, heat-related aggravation of health conditions such as asthma, sinusitis, and high blood pressure, as well as skin irritations and breakouts linked to sweating:

"...I'm on hormonal medication...I don't have natural hot flashes myself, but because this tablet, I become restless when I am feeling too much heat..." (ZA-01-041)

Many resorted to improvised cooling methods, such as using patient files as fans, to cope with the persistent heat while continuing their duties.

➤ **Zimbabwe**

In Zimbabwe, HCWs, especially midwives in delivery wards, described intense heat as a constant physical strain, most severe during peak afternoon hours. They reported feeling light-headed, exhausted, and slower to respond during emergencies, with some experiencing headaches, loss of coordination, or momentary lapses in documentation. As one senior midwife explained,

"My response to complications during delivery is slower when it's boiling. I become exhausted, I suffer headaches, light-headedness and fatigue and I lose coordination and precision".

The cumulative toll was heightened by long hours on their feet and high cognitive demands, leaving some HCWs claiming to feel drained and physically unstable by the end of their shifts.

➤ **Sweden**

At the antenatal clinics and child health centres, most HCWs interviewed mentioned that in general they physically couldn't stand heat. During heatwaves, in Sweden or abroad, they experienced their bodies swelling, feeling tired, having headache and one participant also mentioned getting nausea. Adaptation to heat was more easily done during non-working hours. Consequently, experiencing heat during work was generally hard (even if infrequent), affecting quality of life during non-working hours as well, as they felt exhausted, had persisting headaches, etc. Participants preferred to have cooler temperatures during work hours than during their leisure time. For the participants, working as HCWs at midwifery clinics or children's health centres, the daily workload is equally heavy during all seasons. All except one participant said that available adaptation possibilities were not sufficient. However, as hot periods generally are short in Sweden they knew from experience there would come a change, and temperatures would fall again. This, they said, is why they did not demand improvements to a larger extent.

Heat strain was not observed in the wards at Karolinska University Hospital.

4.3.3.3 Summary of physical strain findings

Quantitative and qualitative findings consistently show that heat exposure increases discomfort, thirst, sweating, and fatigue among healthcare workers. In South Africa and Zimbabwe, these effects were widespread and often severe, leading to reduced work capacity, visible strain, and in some cases the aggravation of chronic conditions such as anaemia, asthma, hypertension, or skin problems. By contrast, in Sweden, heat strain was reported less frequently and mainly among post-menopausal women and overweight staff, with symptoms perceived as

temporary given the shorter duration of heatwaves. Overall, the evidence highlights both the broad impact of heat on healthcare workers and the unequal distribution of vulnerability across groups and settings.

4.4 Theme 3: Performance and quality of care

4.4.1 Perceived quality of care

4.4.1.1 Impact of latest heatwave on quality of care

Overall, the majority of participants in our questionnaire survey reported they observed a decline in quality of care across several indicators and domains. This perception was most pronounced in decrease of productivity, and increased workload. Also, irritability and poorer communication with patients was also among the domains perceived as adversely impacted during a heatwave. System-level vulnerabilities such as power cuts, equipment faults, supply chain disruptions, and concerns about oxytocin efficacy were also reported, with these being particularly prominent in Zimbabwe. These impacts span key domains of quality—including safety, effectiveness, efficiency, and patient experience—highlighting how extreme heat can compromise both the performance of healthcare workers and the resilience of health systems (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Perceived impact of heat stress on quality of care & communication

4.4.1.2 Qualitative results on the impact of heat on quality of care

➤ South Africa

Beyond emotional strain, heat exposure disrupted HCWs' ability to perform physical care-giving tasks, altered their pace of work, and changed how they prioritised duties. The majority of the HCWs interviewed in South Africa said that the result was that elevated heat contributed to slower task completion, altered workflows, and occasional compromises in care delivery.

Some of the most physically challenging tasks, such as escorting pregnant women 300 metres in the sun from the antenatal clinic to the labour ward, became so taxing in hot weather that HCWs sometimes delegated them to colleagues or sought alternative, less physically demanding assignments.

"...if there are patients that have to be sent to labour ward, I ask my colleague... Can I maybe just have any work that I can sit?" (ZA-01-007)

Even in indoor settings, HCWs noticed a slowdown in routine tasks such as discharging patients or processing paperwork. This drop in pace meant longer waits for patients and a reduced overall throughput.

"I'm not productive [during hot weather]... I'll be holding one file for more than 20 minutes." (ZA-01-006)

To cope, some workers adapted their schedules and routines. They would either rush through consultations to escape the heat or postpone non-urgent, physically close procedures, such as vulva swabbing, until the cooler hours of late afternoon. While these adjustments helped manage personal comfort, they sometimes affected the depth and timing of care.

"...when it's too hot, you just push the production line and it affects quality." (ZA-02-012)

Patient-centred tasks requiring patience and sustained attention, such as health education, were among the first to be skipped when the heat became unbearable.

"All I'm thinking about at that point in time is just to get out of there... I will not even be having that patience to... teach." (ZA-01-004)

Across all facilities where staff worked without the benefit of air conditioning, nurses said that heat made them feel more irritable, which in turn impacted on their overall sense of wellbeing in the facility and negatively affected their interactions with patients. Observers noted, for example:

"As the day gets hotter, there is increased fatigue and irritability as the nurse joins the second midwife during the delivery. She says, "push and don't you dare touch my epaulettes!" Five minutes later, the midwife comes out looking very sweaty. It is their "7th delivery for the day", the second midwife shouts." (9 November 2024, Maternity unit)

➤ **Zimbabwe**

During in-depth interviews in Zimbabwe, some HCWs reported that because of heat stress, they sometimes rush over their work processes to leave the maternity

ward quickly, to get some fresh air outside or to get a drink from the hospital campus shop.

“So when it comes to procedures, yes we do them, but what we are saying is, if you were supposed to observe your patient for about 15 to 30 minutes, you end up shortening the process, because the place you are in, is already hot and the more you move around the more the heat... (raises hand) so you are forced to shorten the process.” (ZW-CH-04-8)

“Yes, it is affected (the quality of care), because sometimes you might miss the care that you want to give. You might miss an important issue for the patient because you will be trying to cut corners so that you get out of the room sooner, and you are just saying as long as I deliver the baby.” (ZW-CH-01-03)

The healthcare workers acknowledged that, as a result of the heat, they occasionally neglected to adhere to the established protocols for personal protective equipment (PPE) during certain procedures. This disregard for proper PPE usage compromises both the quality of care provided and the effectiveness of infection control measures.

“You will be in your gown and gloves, boiling within. You just end up having to remove them so that you can cool down” (ZW--02-6)

High temperatures influenced both how quickly tasks were completed and whether HCWs chose to do them at all. In the heat, activities like patient education were often set aside, as attention turned toward coping with discomfort and finding ways to stay cool.

“...All I'm thinking about at that point in time is just to get out of there. So, some of the things that I need to do, I don't really do... because of how unbearable the heat is, I will not even be having that patience to go there to teach, be patient with her [the pregnant woman]...” (ZA-01-004)

➤ **Sweden**

While overall, in interviews HCWs said that heat did not affect the quality of care they gave, they did share some examples of modified practices that they

attributed to heat on the rare occasions it was hot (generally reported to be under 10 days a year). For example, some HCWs reported that extreme heat sometimes led to shortened appointments. During hot periods, they found it difficult to concentrate, felt exhausted, and avoided discussing issues that were not essential. In some cases, appointments were re-booked to cover missed content, but more often, non-urgent matters were simply omitted. Efforts to improve ventilation – such as opening doors to cooler corridors – were not possible when handling personal or sensitive matters. One participant believed that heat did not affect the quality of care, but acknowledged feeling more exhausted after work, having exerted herself more than usual.

HCWs also described how patients' own exposure and reactions to heat or poor ventilation influenced care. For example, one participant noted that children required to perform development tests during appointments sometimes struggled due to the heat, necessitating re-appointments. While warmer rooms were preferable when examining newborns – protecting them from cold or air currents – adults often found prolonged stays in such environments uncomfortable. Third-trimester pregnant women were seen as particularly susceptible to heat stress, whereas some non-pregnant women undergoing stressful examinations appeared to relax more in a warmer room. Participants also observed that some patients requested to shorten consultations due to heat or poor ventilation, but not in response to cold conditions.

No negative effects on care quality were observed during the study period at Karolinska University Hospital. The temperatures were mild during the observation period, limiting observations of impact of heat on staff performance. However, no interviewee reported that heat impacted their work in any way. Summers stay vulnerable periods for stress due to other factors such as staff shortages.

4.4.1.3 Summary of findings on perceived quality of care

In this section, we observe a consistent pattern across all three countries. Heat affects staff physically, which in turn impacts workload and productivity for themselves and others in the facility—staff may perform less, make mistakes, and sometimes defer tasks. These effects on productivity are evident in both the quantitative and qualitative results and align with findings from the broader literature. The quantitative survey data also highlight specific health system challenges in Zimbabwe. Finally, irritability emerged as a dominant aspect in this section and in the wellbeing section, affecting communication and, consequently, the quality of care.

4.4.2 Performance of healthcare workers according to the time-motion study

Higher indoor heat levels, measured as the average WBGT in the hour preceding observation, were associated with a statistically significant deterioration in selected aspects of intrapartum care (see Figure 5). Each 1 °C increase in WBGT was linked to a 14% reduction in the odds of care that preserved women’s dignity (adjusted odds ratio; aOR = 0.86, 95% CI: 0.77–0.95, $p = 0.004$) and a 9% increase in the odds that women were left alone during active labour (aOR = 1.09, 95% CI: 1.02–1.16, $p = 0.012$). Other care processes, including effective communication (aOR = 0.94, 95% CI: 0.85–1.04, $p = 0.245$), provision of emotional support (aOR = 1.03, 95% CI: 0.94–1.13, $p = 0.558$), essential newborn care (aOR = 1.04, 95% CI: 0.95–1.13, $p = 0.381$), monitoring (aOR = 1.03, 95% CI: 0.89–1.18, $p = 0.701$), and avoidance of unrecommended labour-speeding practices (aOR = 1.03, 95% CI: 0.96–1.11, $p = 0.449$), did not show statistically significant associations with heat exposure. Tables 17 and 18 in Appendix 7.4 present the detailed estimates of the association between the studied quality of care processes and heat stress.

Figure 5. Association between heat stress and processes of quality of intrapartum care. Crude and adjusted odds ratios

Overall, the time-motion findings suggest that heat stress in health facilities is likely to affect quality of care processes related to positive experience of care. In other words, hot conditions are more likely to impact the likelihood of women having a positive experience at the health facility than affecting the midwives' provision of evidence-based clinical processes.

4.4.3 Facility-level effects of temperature on absenteeism (Routine data)

The preliminary findings presented here emerge from the analysis of staff attendance sheets in South Africa across the two study facilities. The aim was to examine the association between exposure to outdoor heat stress and the likelihood of absenteeism, allowing for effects from historical exposure (a lag of up to ten days preceding staff absence). We found evidence that heat stress increased the risk of staff taking leave from day shifts. Risk of absenteeism was most pronounced two days following heat exposure (Figure 6). A cumulative exposure to 23 WBGT °C for ten days was associated with an increased risk of absenteeism by 171% (RR: 2.71; 95%CI : 1.28 to 5.75) relative to an exposure of 14

°C. These estimates are adjusted for facility, number of newborns, day of the week, number of staff allocated, seasonality and long-term trend.

Further analyses are being conducted to evaluate the impact of heat stress on service seeking, and maternal health outcomes, with the findings planned for future publications in peer-reviewed journals.

Figure 6. Association curves between exposure to outdoor heat stress and absenteeism

Note: Association curves between exposure to outdoor heat stress (in WBGT) and absenteeism (left panel) and lag – response curve estimated at WBGT of 23 (right panel) in two South African facilities. The estimates were obtained from a distributed-lag (10 days) nonlinear model. Reference exposure 14 C. Gray shade represents the 95% confidence intervals.

4.4.4 Summary of performance and quality of care findings

We found consistent evidence that heat impacted several aspects of quality of care. Qualitative and Quantitative findings were aligned in that healthcare workers modified their work processes. This was most prominent in healthcare workers rushing procedures (e.g. shorter consultations with patients and more frequently leaving women during childbirth). Productivity loss was among the prominent themes as it was perceived as strongly declined due to heat. This converged with the findings from routine records, which showed staff absences were more frequent following an exposure to high temperature (2-3 day lag). Both interviews

and the time-motion study found adverse impact on interaction with patients, especially in tasks related to providing health education. However, adhering to clinical practices, such as monitoring women in labour and ensuring skin-to-skin contact, remained unaffected.

4.5 Thermal exposure in health facilities

4.5.1 South Africa

Figure 7 shows the temperature variation during the year in the admission and antenatal rooms at Stanza Clinic and in the antenatal, labour, and neonatal rooms and the nurses' station at Mamelodi hospital. For comparison, the outdoor temperature at the location of the two clinics is also shown in the figure. Except in the neonatal room at Mamelodi, the free-running nature (no cooling) of the buildings stands out with clear diurnal and overlaid seasonal temperature swings, particularly at Stanza clinic. In the neonatal room at Mamelodi, the temperature was consistently high around 30°C during the greater part of the year, which could indicate that internal heat gains from utilities or other equipment were high in this room.

Figure 7. Temperature measured during 2024 in selected rooms in Stanza and Mamelodi clinics and outdoors

Note: At Stanza, a measurement device was moved from nurses' station to the labour room in February 2024. Therefore, the figure includes only few measurements from nurses' station.

For comparison, Figure 8 shows that temperatures measured at Karolinska Hospital in Stockholm, Sweden, were very stable in the comfortable temperature range throughout the year, despite large outdoor seasonal temperature swings. Karolinska Hospital is a rather new building (completed in 2018) that is equipped with installations for heating, cooling, and ventilation. Table 4 shows air temperatures and WBGT aggregated for the measurement periods at the three locations.

Figure 8. Temperatures measured indoors at Karolinska Hospital, Sweden, and outdoors at the location of the hospital

Table 4. Aggregated values of the air temperature and WBGT measured in the facilities in South Africa and Sweden

Country	Facility	Room	Air temperature (°C)				WBGT (°C)			Number of records
			Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Max	
South Africa	Mamelodi	Antenatal	24.3	3.0	14.9	31.3	19.1	3.1	25.1	17264
		Neonatal	29.0	1.2	22.7	33.6	21.6	1.7	26.9	17183
		Delivery	24.0	2.5	16.3	30.0	18.4	2.5	23.4	14090
		Nurses' station	26.6	0.8	24.1	30.4	22.0	1.0	25.8	1706
	Stanza	Admission	26.0	2.9	16.6	31.8	19.5	2.7	26.2	17265
		Antenatal	24.9	4.9	11.2	37.2	18.6	4.3	27.6	17519
		Outdoor	19.1	6.7	-1.0	36.1	15.9	6.7	37.2	8760
Sweden	Karolinska University Hospital	Doctor's expedition	23.7	0.6	22.1	27.1	17.4	1.3	22.3	17254
		Nurses rest	23.0	0.3	22.1	26.3	17.3	1.3	21.4	17253
		Patient room	22.1	0.6	20.5	27.4	16.4	1.7	23.3	17254
		Outdoor	6.7	8.1	-16.7	25.2	6.0	8.3	25.2	10224

Note: Measurements at Karolinska hospital cover the period from 1 November 2023 to 31 December 2024.

International guidelines and standards provide recommendations for assessing and mitigating occupational heat stress. One of these is the Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, which integrates temperature, humidity, activity level, and clothing information to estimate physiological heat strain (ISO7243:2017). According to the WBGT, thresholds of 30°C at low activity (180W), of 28 °C at moderate activity (300W), and of 26°C at high activity (415 W) indicate the temperature below which the level of heat stress could be sustained during the total exposure over a working day (ISO7243:2017). WHO recommendations address the general need to keep the indoor temperature of the housing of vulnerable individuals, such as the elderly, infants, sick people and people with disabilities, below 32 °C (WHO 2018). Table 5 shows the accumulated number of hours during the measurement period when the air temperature was in the range 25 °C to 32 °C, when it exceeded 32°C and when the WBGT exceeded 26 °C or 28 °C (hourly means of WBGT did not exceed 30 °C in any facility).

Table 5. Accumulated number of hours when the indoor air temperature or the WBGT exceeded recommended thresholds

Country	Facility	Room	No. of hours		
			Air temperature 25-32°C	Air temperature >32°C	WBGT >26°C
South Africa ¹⁾	Mamelodi	Antenatal	4127	0	0
		Neonatal	8535	7	2
		Delivery	2656	0	0
		Nurses' station	824	0	0
	Stanza	Admission	5439	115	1
		Antenatal	4064	597	79
Sweden ²⁾	Karolinska	Doctor's expedition	676	0	0
		Nurses rest	0	0	0
		Patient room	1	0	0

Notes: 1) In South Africa, the measurement period spans 1 January 2024 to 31 December 2024. 2) In Sweden, the measurement period spans 1 November 2023 to 31 December 2024.

At Mamelodi, air temperatures exceeded what is typically considered comfortable (> 25 °C to 26 °C), but only a few hours with temperatures or WBGT values exceeding recommendations for strong heat stress were observed. At Stanza, hourly means of the air temperature exceeded 32 °C and the WBGT exceeded 26 °C during a substantial part of the year. At Karolinska, there was no risk of heat stress, although the temperatures in the doctors' offices increased beyond the comfortable range during around 7% of the year. This could be caused by a rather large, glazed area in the façade in this room, allowing a high level of solar irradiation, in combination with high internal gains from computers and staff.

4.5.2 Zimbabwe

Figure 9 shows temperatures measured indoors in selected rooms at Mount Darwin Hospital and at Chitse and Dotito rural health centres. As in South Africa, the indoor temperature tracks the variation of the outdoor temperature, although the variation between rooms was smaller than in South Africa. Generally, both the mean and the maximum temperatures were higher than in South Africa (Table 6). Table 7 shows that the number of hours with temperatures and WBGT values

exceeding recommendations was significant in all three facilities, although there were no observations of WBGT that indicated that work could not be sustained at low to moderate activity during a full day (WBGT > 28°C).

Figure 9. Temperature measured from November 2023 to December 2024 in selected rooms at Mount Darwin Hospital and at Chitse and Dotito rural health centre and outdoors

Note: Outdoor temperature is an average of the temperatures at Mount Darwin, Chitse and Dotito rural health centre.

Table 6. Aggregated values of the air temperature and WBGT measured during a year in the facilities in Zimbabwe

Country	Facility	Room	Air temperature (°C)				WBGT (°C)			N
			Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Max	
Zim- babwe	Mount Darwin	Delivery 1	25.9	3.7	13.3	36.6	21.0	3.3	27.2	45538
		Delivery 2	26.4	4.1	13.6	38.8	21.6	3.3	29.0	76741
		Neonatal	26.6	3.3	16.6	35.6	21.4	3.2	27.5	21694
		Postnatal	26.0	4.3	14.6	37.9	21.2	3.7	28.9	78110
		Postnatal vaccination	26.7	4.4	14.5	40.0	21.5	3.6	30.1	62341
		Outdoor	22.1	5.3	7.3	37.0	19.4	5.4	39.6	8784
	Chitse	Delivery	26.1	3.8	15.1	36.1	20.8	3.3	28.1	105407
		Consultation	26.3	4.0	11.1	36.5	21.3	3.5	28.0	67459
		Outdoor	21.6	5.3	6.8	36.7	19.1	5.5	43.7	8784
	Dotito	Delivery	25.3	4.1	13.8	35.2	18.9	3.4	27.6	36471
		Antenatal care	24.7	5.2	12.0	40.5	20.2	4.2	30.6	105408
		Outdoor	22.6	5.4	7.8	37.8	20.0	5.4	43.3	8784

Table 7. Accumulated number of hours when the indoor air temperature or the WBGT exceeded recommended thresholds, Zimbabwe

Country	Facility	Room	No. of hours		
			Air temperature 25-32°C	Air temperature >32°C	WBGT >26°C
Zimbabwe ¹⁾	Mount Darwin	Delivery 1	4713	426	115
		Delivery 2	4065	682	487
		Neonatal	3716	160	99
		Postnatal	3533	545	381
		Postnatal vaccination	4141	458	502
	Chitse	Delivery	4984	518	207
		Consultation	4569	477	251
	Dotito	Delivery	2160	123	55
		Antenatal care	3784	951	649

Note: 1) The measurement period spans 1 November 2023 to 31 October 2024.

4.6 Attitudes towards common adaptation interventions and their feasibility

We explored healthcare workers perspective on the feasibility of common adaptation interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe. We analysed this by country and by facility as these two factors can be highly influential in terms of feasibility. The findings are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Healthcare workers perception of the feasibility of adaptation interventions

Most healthcare workers in Zimbabwe opted for opening windows as a feasible way to handle indoor hot conditions, whereas in South Africa opening windows came second after using air conditioning; likely because windows are either unopenable or too high to open, especially in the CHC. The provision of cold water along with air conditioning also emerged as feasible adaptations in Zimbabwe, although less popular than opening windows. In South Africa, healthcare workers in a community health centre were more likely to report the provision of cold water as a possible intervention compared to those working in the hospital. Notably, taking regular breaks was not a popular option in any setting. This can be due to the high workload typically seen in such facilities.

5 Conclusion

Our study used a comprehensive set of tools to triangulate findings on the impacts of heat in health facilities on healthcare workers and their work. The cross-country findings are summarised by outcomes and methods in Table 8.

Overall, we observed clear health effects related to dehydration (particularly in Zimbabwe), mental health (especially in South Africa), physical heat strain, and cognitive-related performance in both African sites. In contrast, the Swedish sites showed minimal heat-related impacts, reflecting both optimal thermal conditions and the presence of policies ensuring appropriate working environments. Across South Africa and Zimbabwe, findings were broadly consistent—particularly for physical strain and qualitative results—though Zimbabwean sites experienced higher temperatures, with many days exceeding 32 °C during data collection. The expected impact of heat on mental health in Zimbabwe was less evident, possibly reflecting limitations in the measurement instruments rather than a true absence of effect. Overall, all health domains were affected except anxiety, which may relate to sample size, measurement tools, or a genuine lack of association. Confidence in our findings is strengthened by the consistency and complementarity across methods, though our analysis of biomedical measurement was limited to urine specific gravity. Performance impacts were observed mainly in soft skills, with substantial implications for improving respectful care during labour, a very active current agenda in maternal health. Impacts on productivity were reported in all three countries.

The outcomes are interconnected in complex ways, as illustrated in the conceptual framework we developed from our findings (Figure 11).

Table 8. Map of evidence for adverse heat impact, based on findings from the baseline health worker study.

	South Africa				Zimbabwe				Sweden			
	Qualitative methods	Questionnaire	Time-motion study	Other (USG, routine data)	Qualitative methods	Questionnaire	Time-motion study	Other (USG, routine data)	Qualitative methods	Questionnaire ^o	Time-motion study	Other (USG, routine data)
Dehydration				Limited				Yes				
Psych stress	Yes	Yes			Yes	Moderate			Moderate	Pending ^o		
Wellbeing	Yes	Yes			Yes	Moderate			Moderate	Pending ^o		
Anxiety	Yes	yes			Yes	Moderate			Moderate	Pending ^o		
Cognition	Yes				Yes				Moderate	Pending ^o		
Heat strain	Yes	Yes			Yes	Yes			Moderate	Pending ^o		
Performance/ QoC	Yes	Yes	Some QOC outcomes*	Pending	Yes	Yes	Moderate*	Pending		Pending ^o		
Respectful care	Yes	Yes	Moderate		Yes	Yes	Moderate					

Notes: **Green** box indicates that the study found evidence of adverse heat impact; **Yellow** indicates that there was moderate or mixed evidence; **Orange** refers to pending, which indicates that data collection/analysis is ongoing. **Red** indicates evidence was limited. **Grey** means field is not applicable.

* only some quality of care outcomes were significantly associated with heat stress; other indicators remained unaffected

^o Questionnaire data collection for the cold season in Sweden is scheduled for later this year.

Figure 11. The links between heat and maternal healthcare workers' wellbeing and quality of care (Lange et al., 2025)

Heat directly influences staff wellbeing and health system functioning, which in turn affect quality of care, as repeatedly highlighted in our qualitative interviews. These results informed the co-design process for the HIGH Horizons interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe, which identified drinking behaviours and facility design as key domains for adaptation.

A few limitations should be considered. First, we were unable to measure or control for acclimatisation, which may have made the effects of heat appear smaller than they truly are. Second, our study included only a handful of facilities in each of the three countries, so generalisations to national-level effects cannot be made. Third, our statistical samples were relatively small, potentially affecting the power of our statistical analyses. Finally, we studied the impact of heat on quality of care from the perspective of providers and not the users of services (women, babies, fathers).

Further research is needed. Larger studies in hot LMIC settings could clarify the effects of heat on dehydration and physical strain, especially among sub-groups, and further investigate mental health outcomes. Cognitive effects, while emerging in qualitative interviews, would require dedicated studies. Studies in warmer European countries would also be valuable, including among healthcare providers working in community settings (e.g. health visitors and community midwives).

Overall, our findings have four methodological and substantive implications:

- (1) They demonstrate the robustness of interdisciplinary methods, combining thermal measurement, time-motion studies, and qualitative approaches to build a comprehensive picture of the impacts of heat on wellbeing, quality of care, and performance. Some methods—such as time-motion observation—are innovative, valuable, and potentially transferable to other settings or endline assessments. We will retain the full suite of tools, given the valuable and complementary insights revealed at baseline.

- (2) They highlight the importance of protecting health facility staff in hot environments, given the wide-ranging impacts on both their physical and mental health—for example, more frequent breaks were found to protect against dehydration.
- (3) They show the importance of context, with heat and climate change a cause of concern for healthcare providers in Sweden but having only some limited impact at present.
- (4) They demonstrate how the effects of heat on the wellbeing of healthcare workers, ultimately influence their performance and the quality of care provided, which in turn may impact maternal and child health outcomes through these indirect pathways.

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7 Appendices

7.1 Researchers involved in the study

All researchers and field workers involved in the baseline healthcare worker study are listed by country and study site in table 9.

Table 9. Research team members per study site

	South Africa (Wits RHI)	Zimbabwe (CeSHHAR)	Sweden (KI)	LSHTM	DTU
Leadership and core team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gloria Maimela, Country PI, 2023 to 2025 ▪ Shobna Sawry, Senior Research: 2024, and Country PI: 2025-date ▪ Celeste Madondo, Senior Programme Manager, 2023-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fortunate Machingura, Country PI ▪ Stanley Luchters, HIGH Horizons Study Global PI, George Mapiye, MoH lead 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nathalie Roos, KI lead, 2023-2024 ▪ Claudia Hanson, HCW study lead, 2024-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Veronique Filippi, design/coordination, Task 2.2 lead, 2023-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Jørn Toftum, DTU lead, 2023-date
Researchers and field workers for qualitative elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rose Lamola, Project Manager, 2023-date ▪ Fiona Scorgie, Senior Researcher, 2023-2024 ▪ Pascalia Munyewende Senior Researcher, 2024-date ▪ Nondumiso Mbatha, Observations, IDIs, KIIs, 2023-date ▪ Malolo Kekana, Observations, IDIs, 2023-date ▪ Mbalenhle Mvundla, Observations, 2023-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tariro Chinozvina, Observations) ▪ Concilia Mutasa, Coordinator ▪ Brian Sibanda, IDIs ▪ Leslie Nyoni, Analysis ▪ Lameck Kachena, KII 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Veronika Tirado, design in Swedish and on-site coordination, 2023-date ▪ Maria Ström, research assistant: HCW interviews, 2023-date ▪ Kajsa Ådahl, research assistant: HCW interviews, April-September 2025 ▪ Emma Bole-Feysot, research assistant: observations, June-August 2025 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Isabelle Lange, design/coordination, 2023-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪

	South Africa (Wits RHI)	Zimbabwe (CeSHHAR)	Sweden (KI)	LSHTM	DTU
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Kgomotso Mabidikama, KIIs, 2024-date 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Olof Stephansson, 2024-date 		
Researchers and field workers for quantitative elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Darshnika Lakhoo, Research Clinical, 2023-2024 ▪ Lebohang Radebe, Statistician, 2024 ▪ Mbalenhle Mvundla, Surveys, Routine data abstraction and Time-Motion Study, 2023-date ▪ Nondumiso Mbatha, Surveys, routine data abstraction and Time-Motion Study, 2023-date ▪ Nosiviwe Mnyaka, MCR, 2024-date ▪ Malolo Kekana, Surveys, 2023-date ▪ Nkhensani Maswanganyi, MCR, 2024-date ▪ Kgomotso Mabidikama, MCR and Surveys, 2024-date ▪ Jean Le Roux, Data Manager, 2024-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tariro Chinozvina, Survey administration ▪ Brian Sibanda, Survey administration ▪ Jetina Tsvaki, HCW Survey analysis ▪ Perkins Watambwa, USG Analysis ▪ Bongani Mutimutema, WOMBAT, and routine data abstraction ▪ Elizabeth Dangaiso, WOMBAT, and routine data abstraction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Veronika Tirado, survey design in Swedish, pilot survey, administration in REDCap, survey distribution/data collection, 2023-date ▪ Olof Stephansson, 2024-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nasser Fardousi, design/analysis, 2023-date ▪ Giorgia Gon, design/analysis, 2023-date 	
Researchers and field workers for thermal measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Otsile Lekabe, Data collection, 2023-date ▪ Palesa Ranamane, Data collection, 2023-date ▪ Lebohang Radebe, Statistician, 2024 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thabani Muronzie, Data collection ▪ Joshua Rusike, Data collection 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Jørn Toftum, design/data processing/analysis/reporting

7.2 Data collection participation and timing

Table 10 gives the details of the numbers of participants and timing of data collection in the cold and hot seasons for the baseline healthcare workers' study in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden.

Table 10. Numbers of participants and timing of data collection for the baseline healthcare workers' study

Data collection method	South Africa			Zimbabwe			Sweden		
	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? cold season)	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? (cold season)	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? (cold season)
Observations in health facilities	158 hours	14 November 2023 - 13 December 2023	NA	196 hours in hot season; 88 hours in cooler season	8 August - 12 September 2023	5 May - 4 June 2024	6 sessions	18-30 June 2025	NA
In-depth interviews	15 interviews	16 January 2024 - 8 February 2024	NA	24 HCWs hot season; 15 HCWs in cold season	14-18 August 2023	20 May - 1 July 2024	10 interviews	29 May - 1 August 2025	NA
Interviews with key informants	10 interviews	20 May 2024- 26 August 2024	NA	15 HCWs and community leaders	11 Nov - 21 December 2024	NA	NA	NA	NA
Survey questionnaires	109 HCWs	15 February 2024 - 23 March 2024	03 June 2024- 25 July 2024	56 HCWs	27 Sept - 24 November 2023	3-18 June 2024	NA	NA	NA
Time-motion study	196 hours in hot season; 88 hours in cooler season	8 August - 12 September 2023	5 May - 4 June 2024	101 days in hot season; 119 days in cold season 14 midwives: hot season; 12 cooler season	16 October - 9 December 2023	13 February - 4 July 2024	NA	NA	NA

Data collection method	South Africa			Zimbabwe			Sweden		
	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? (cold season)	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? (cold season)	How many?	When? (hot season)	When? (cold season)
Data Abstraction	Collected retrospectively on 26-27 June 2022	1 January 2022 - 31 May 2022	NA	Collecting retrospectively from 2019, and continues until the end project	September 2023 (continuous data collection)	NA	NA	NA	NA
Urine specific gravity	104	15 February 2024 - 3 April 2024	27 June 2024 - 10 September 2024	56 HCWs	27 September 2023 - 24 November 2023	3-18 Jun 2024	NA	NA	NA
Measurements of thermal conditions	Overall Indoor: 5 April-Still ongoing Outdoor: 22 Mar 2024-still ongoing in Stanza CHC	Ongoing	Ongoing	Indoor 19 September 2023 Outdoor started 28 September 2023, and still ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Indoor: Since 11 October 2023	July - August 2024, July - August 2025 Monitoring covered two summer seasons	December, January, February 2024, 2025, 2026 Monitoring covers three heating seasons

7.3 Supplementary tables from quantitative analyses

Table 11. Sample characteristics, Zimbabwe

ZIMBABWE	Cold season			Hot season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Age group						
20-30	3 (5.36%)			3 (5.36%)		
30-40	11 (19.64%)			12 (21.43%)		
40-50	33 (58.93%)			33 (58.93%)		
+50	9 (16.07%)			8 (14.29%)		
Name of facility						
ZW-Chitse	8 (14.29%)			8 (14.29%)		
ZW-Dotito	9 (16.07%)			8 (14.29%)		
ZW-Mt Darwin	39 (69.64%)			40 (71.43%)		
Q2-2. What is your sex?						
Female	40 (71.43%)			38 (67.86%)		
Male	16 (28.57%)			18 (32.14%)		
Other	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q2_4. What is your staff position in this hospital?						
Nurse of any grade	19 (33.93%)			11 (19.64%)		
Midwife	19 (33.93%)			20 (35.71%)		
Paediatrician, Neonatologist	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Anaesthesiologist	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
Other types of doctor (e.g., intern, medical officer)	2 (3.57%)			2 (3.57%)		

ZIMBABWE	Cold season			Hot season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Clinical associate	3 (5.36%)			0 (0.00%)		
Allied health workers such as physiotherapists	1 (1.79%)			1 (1.79%)		
Community health worker	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Cleaner	7 (12.50%)			11 (19.64%)		
Porter	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Other, please specify	5 (8.93%)			10 (17.86%)		
Q2_3. What is your highest level of education?						
Some secondary	3 (5.36%)			1 (1.79%)		
Secondary school (O&A level)	21 (37.50%)			23 (41.07%)		
National Diploma	17 (30.36%)			16 (28.57%)		
Advanced Diploma	7 (12.50%)			11 (19.64%)		
Undergraduate degree	7 (12.50%)			4 (7.14%)		
Post-graduate degree	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
Prefer not to say	1 (1.79%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_3. If you are a woman, are you pregnant or were pregnant in the past 12 months?						
Yes, pregnant	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
Yes, pregnant past 12 months	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
No	39 (69.64%)			35 (62.50%)		
Not applicable	16 (28.57%)			19 (33.93%)		
Don't know	1 (1.79%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q2_11. How long is your current/ was your last shift?		8.00 [IQR 8.00-8.00]	8.45 (2.83)		8.00 [IQR 8.00-9.00]	8.86 (1.92)

ZIMBABWE	Cold season			Hot season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Length of experience as HCW			. (.)		13.25 [IQR 7.25-15.62]	12.38 (6.79)
Length of experience in the facility			. (.)		12.08 [IQR 5.17-15.21]	10.70 (6.03)
Q3_2_1. Hypertension	15 (26.79%)			10 (17.86%)		
Q3_2_2. Diabetes	4 (7.14%)			3 (5.36%)		
Q3_2_3. Dyslipidaemia (high cholesterol or triglycerides)	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_2_4. Asthma/COPD	5 (8.93%)			4 (7.14%)		
Q3_2_6. Autoimmune disease, e.g., Lupus, rheumatoid arthritis	1 (1.79%)			1 (1.79%)		
Q3_2_7. Osteoarthritis	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
Q3_2_8. Heart disease	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.79%)		
Q3_2_9. Stroke	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_2_10. Epilepsy	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_2_11. Depression/anxiety	2 (3.57%)			1 (1.79%)		
Q3_2_13. HIV	3 (5.36%)			3 (5.36%)		
Q3_2_14. Other (please specify)	4 (7.14%)			3 (5.36%)		
None of the above	29 (51.79%)			32 (57.14%)		

Table 12. Sample characteristics, South Africa

SOUTH AFRICA	Cold season			Hot Season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Age group						
20-30	11 (13.58%)			14 (17.28%)		
30-40	25 (30.86%)			28 (34.57%)		
40-50	23 (28.40%)			18 (22.22%)		
+50	22 (27.16%)			21 (25.93%)		
Name of facility						
SA-Mamelodi	49 (60.49%)			55 (67.90%)		
SA-Stanza	32 (39.51%)			26 (32.10%)		
Q2_2. What is your sex?						
Female	80 (98.77%)			80 (98.77%)		
Male	1 (1.23%)			0 (0.00%)		
Other	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q2_4. What is your staff position in this hospital?						
Nurse of any grade	16 (19.75%)			17 (20.99%)		
Midwife	27 (33.33%)			36 (44.44%)		
Paediatrician, Neonatologist	1 (1.23%)			0 (0.00%)		
Anaesthesiologist	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Other types of doctor (e.g., intern, medical officer)	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Clinical associate	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		
Allied health workers such as physiotherapists	0 (0.00%)			0 (0.00%)		

SOUTH AFRICA	Cold season			Hot Season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Community health worker	2 (2.47%)			2 (2.47%)		
Cleaner	16 (19.75%)			11 (13.58%)		
Porter	0 (0.00%)			2 (2.47%)		
Other, please specify	19.46%			13 (16.05%)		
Q2_3. What is your highest level of education?						
Some secondary	5 (6.17%)			4 (4.94%)		
Secondary school (O&A level)	24 (29.63%)			19 (23.46%)		
National Diploma	28 (34.57%)			31 (38.27%)		
Advanced Diploma,	8 (9.88%)			8 (9.88%)		
Undergraduate degree	5 (6.17%)			6 (7.41%)		
Post-graduate degree	8 (9.88%)			9 (11.11%)		
Prefer not to say	3 (3.70%)			4 (4.94%)		
Q3_3. If you are a woman, are you pregnant or were pregnant in the past 12 months?						
Yes, pregnant	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.23%)		
Yes, pregnant in the past 12 months	3 (3.75%)			3 (3.70%)		
No	76 (95.00%)			73 (90.12%)		
Not applicable	0 (0.00%)			3 (3.70%)		
Don't know	1 (1.25%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q2_11. How long is your current/ was your last shift?		12.00 [IQR 8.00-12.00]	10.78 (3.98)		12.00 [IQR 8.00-12.00]	11.54 (5.80)
Length of experience as HCW		10.92 [IQR 4.58-16.50]	12.64 (9.11)		11.17 [IQR 4.17-15.50]	11.69 (8.37)

SOUTH AFRICA	Cold season			Hot Season		
	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)	Frequency (%)	Median [Interquartile range]	Mean (standard deviation)
Length of experience in the facility		6.33 [IQR 3.17-13.08]	8.36 (6.57)		5.25 [IQR 2.33-11.25]	7.72 (6.77)
Q3_2_1. Hypertension	11 (13.58%)			16 (19.75%)		
Q3_2_2. Diabetes	1 (1.23%)			2 (2.47%)		
Q3_2_3. Dyslipidaemia (high cholesterol or triglycerides)	1 (1.23%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_2_4. Asthma/COPD	3 (3.70%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q3_2_6. Autoimmune disease, e.g., Lupus, rheumatoid arthritis	1 (1.23%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q3_2_7. Osteoarthritis	2 (2.47%)			3 (3.70%)		
Q3_2_8. Heart disease	1 (1.23%)			0 (0.00%)		
Q3_2_9. Stroke	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q3_2_10. Epilepsy	0 (0.00%)			1 (1.23%)		
Q3_2_11. Depression/anxiety	2 (2.47%)			3 (3.70%)		
Q3_2_13. HIV	6 (7.41%)			5 (6.17%)		
Q3_2_14. Other (please specify)	3 (3.70%)			1 (1.23%)		
None of the above	56 (69.14%)			57 (70.37%)		

Table 13. Sample characteristics, Sweden

Characteristic	n (%)
Age group	
20-29	7 (10.9%)
30-39	27 (42.2%)
40-49	16 (25.0%)
50-59	7 (10.9%)
60-69	7 (10.9%)
Sex	
Female	62 (96.9%)
Male	2 (3.1%)
Highest educational level	
Upper secondary school	1 (1.6%)
Vocational college	2 (3.1%)
University (Bachelor)	21 (32.8%)
University (Master)	38 (59.4%)
University (Doctorate)	2 (3.1%)
Job titles	
Manager	4 (5.4%)
Nurse	1 (1.4%)
Midwife	47 (63.5%)
Obstetrician/Gynaecologist	8 (10.8%)
Nurse assistant	4 (5.4%)
Cleaner	1 (1.4%)
Other	1 (1.4%)
Years working in healthcare (mean, SD)	22.3 (15.6)
Years working in this unit (mean, SD)	12.2 (15.1)

Table 14. Mental health outcomes by country and season

Country	Season	WHO-5 Wellbeing Index (higher better)	Perceived Stress Scale PSS-4 (lower better)	Generalised Anxiety Disorder (lower better)
South Africa	Cold season	Median 17.50 [IQR 11.00–21.00]	Median 7.00 [IQR 4.00–8.00]	Median 4.00 [IQR 1.00–9.00]
South Africa	Hot season	Median 16.00 [IQR 10.00–20.00]	Median 7.00 [IQR 6.00–9.00]	Median 6.00 [IQR 2.00–10.00]
Zimbabwe	Cold season	Median 16.00 [IQR 11.00–18.50]	Median 7.00 [IQR 4.00–8.00]	Median 3.00 [IQR 0.50–7.00]
Zimbabwe	Hot season	Median 14.00 [IQR 9.50–19.50]	Median 7.00 [IQR 5.00–9.00]	Median 5.00 [IQR 0.00–7.00]

Figure 12. Impact of heat on mental health indicators

Note: Estimates were obtained from analysing data in each country separately.

7.4 Quality of care analysis using the time-motion study

Table 15. Outcome definitions

Outcome	Definition / Measure	Source / Guidance
Respect & Preservation of Dignity	No verbal or physical abuse observed; privacy ensured. (1= any of the tasks observed).	WHO QoC standards (privacy, dignity, mistreatment prevention).
Effective Communication	BA (birth attendant) explains procedures, seeks permission, gives advice, engages in respectful communication. Binary (1= any of the tasks observed)	WHO LCG Section 2, WHO Standards (effective communication).
Providing Support	Encourages hydration, mobility, breastfeeding, or pain management. Binary (1= any of the tasks observed).	WHO LCG supportive care section.
Taking a Break	BA takes a break during observation (sits, eats, cools, uses fan). Binary (0/1).	Time-motion tool (non-clinical tasks).
Mother Left Alone	Woman left alone in the room anytime from active pushing until birth. Binary (0/1).	WHO guidance: continuous support during labour.
Foetal & Maternal Monitoring	Evidence of required checks: • FHR at least once (every 30 min in active stage; every 5 min in second stage) • Contraction monitoring at least once. Binary (0/1).	WHO LCG Sections 3 & 5.
Complete Newborn Care	Immediate postnatal care: delayed cord clamping (≥ 1 min), skin-to-skin contact, and drying/wiping baby. Complete if all 3 present. Binary (0/1).	WHO Standards for essential newborn care.
Unrecommended Practices	Any of: fundal pressure, amniotomy, or administering uterotonic to speed labour. Binary (0/1).	WHO intrapartum recommendations (not recommended).

Table 16. Delivery sessions sample characteristics by country

	Country		Total
	South Africa	Zimbabwe	
N	253 (51.7%)	236 (48.3%)	489 (100.0%)
Shift			
1 st	210 (83.0%)	122 (51.7%)	332 (67.9%)
2 nd	43 (17.0%)	76 (32.2%)	119 (24.3%)
3 rd	0 (0.0%)	38 (16.1%)	38 (7.8%)
Complicated delivery?			
No	210 (83.0%)	201 (85.2%)	411 (84.0%)
Yes	43 (17.0%)	35 (14.8%)	78 (16.0%)
Was the woman giving birth for the first time?			
No	157 (71.0%)	108 (48.0%)	265 (59.4%)
Yes	64 (29.0%)	117 (52.0%)	181 (40.6%)
Average WBGT one hour before the sessions	19.227 (2.933)	21.530 (3.171)	20.333 (3.257)
Daily deliveries volume	23.688 (5.144)	6.119 (2.616)	15.209 (9.705)
Total number of staff in maternity	7.762 (2.681)	24.835 (3.441)	16.087 (9.078)
Midwives' total working hours before observation	2.593 (1.338)	2.470 (1.918)	2.534 (1.643)

Table 17. Association between quality of care processes and heat stress (1/2)

	Adjusted model							
	Respect and preservation of dignity		Effective communication		Emotional support		Frequency of breaks	
	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value
Average WBGT one hour before the sessions	0.86** [0.77- 0.95]	0.0040	0.94 [0.85- 1.04]	0.2447	1.03 [0.94- 1.13]	0.5583	1.08 [0.97- 1.21]	0.1473
Complicated delivery?								
No	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
Yes	1.41 [0.66- 3.01]	0.3796	1.61 [0.71- 3.65]	0.2560	0.60 [0.30- 1.20]	0.1504	0.64 [0.26- 1.59]	0.3374
Shift								
1	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
2	0.59 [0.23- 1.49]	0.2632	1.35 [0.65- 2.77]	0.4202	0.50 [0.23- 1.10]	0.0844	1.81 [0.77- 4.22]	0.1708
3	1.00		1.29 [0.37- 4.47]	0.6866	1.74 [0.43- 7.04]	0.4365	0.54 [0.06- 4.85]	0.5818
Country								
South Africa	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
Zimbabwe	0.60 [0.06- 5.78]	0.6551	3.43 [0.43-27.53]	0.2467	0.01*** [0.00- 0.05]	0.0000	0.11 [0.01- 1.07]	0.0570
Session length	1.00 [1.00- 1.01]	0.1010	1.01 [1.00- 1.01]	0.0585	1.00 [0.99- 1.00]	0.1865	1.00 [1.00- 1.01]	0.1070
Daily deliveries volume	0.94 [0.88- 1.01]	0.1083	0.96 [0.90- 1.02]	0.1642	0.97 [0.92- 1.03]	0.3115	0.97 [0.91- 1.04]	0.4161
Total number of staff in maternity	0.91 [0.81- 1.01]	0.0885	0.91* [0.83- 1.00]	0.0468	1.03 [0.94- 1.14]	0.4903	1.02 [0.92- 1.13]	0.7334
Working duration	0.94 [0.73- 1.21]	0.6480	1.14 [0.93- 1.39]	0.1992	0.90 [0.74- 1.10]	0.3174	1.15 [0.91- 1.45]	0.2321

Notes: Estimates from logistic regression. *** $p \leq 0.001$ ** $p \leq 0.01$ * $p \leq 0.05$. aOR: adjusted odds ratio

Table 18. Association between quality of care processes and heat stress (2/2)

	Adjusted model							
	Mother left alone during active stage		Did any monitoring occur if until-birth length is +30 min		Complete newborn care performed		Labour speeding happened?	
	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value	aOR [95% CI]	p-value
Average WBGT one hour before the sessions	1.09* [1.02- 1.16]	0.0119	1.03 [0.89- 1.18]	0.7012	1.04 [0.95- 1.13]	0.3813	1.03 [0.96- 1.11]	0.4485
Complicated delivery?								
No	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
Yes	1.06 [0.63- 1.77]	0.8285	2.56 [0.99- 6.64]	0.0522	0.47* [0.23- 0.96]	0.0390	2.04* [1.13- 3.66]	0.0175
Shift								
1	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
2	1.00 [0.61- 1.64]	0.9891	1.42 [0.48- 4.18]	0.5223	1.44 [0.76- 2.74]	0.2610	0.73 [0.40- 1.34]	0.3118
3	1.02 [0.47- 2.25]	0.9539	0.88 [0.08- 9.28]	0.9148	0.83 [0.28- 2.47]	0.7348	0.33 [0.10- 1.04]	0.0588
Country								
South Africa	1.00		1.00		1.00		1.00	
Zimbabwe	2.53 [0.63-10.11]	0.1907	68.26** [3.81-1222.49]	0.0041	0.02*** [0.00- 0.18]	0.0004	3.10 [0.59-16.37]	0.1835
Session length	1.00 [1.00- 1.01]	0.4165	1.01*** [1.01- 1.02]	0.0003	1.00 [1.00- 1.01]	0.1388	1.01** [1.00- 1.01]	0.0088
Daily deliveries volume	1.01 [0.97- 1.06]	0.5507	1.03 [0.94- 1.13]	0.5553	1.01 [0.95- 1.07]	0.8445	1.04 [0.98- 1.10]	0.1873
Total number of staff in maternity	1.01 [0.94- 1.07]	0.8696	0.91 [0.80- 1.03]	0.1296	1.13** [1.04- 1.23]	0.0047	0.99 [0.92- 1.07]	0.7889
Working duration	0.98 [0.87- 1.12]	0.8034	0.98 [0.75- 1.29]	0.8794	1.05 [0.90- 1.24]	0.5375	0.99 [0.84- 1.16]	0.8755

Notes: Estimates from logistic regression. *** p≤0.001 ** p≤0.01 * p≤0.05. aOR: adjusted odds ratio

7.5 Healthcare workers' study protocol

Heat Indicators of Global Health (HIGH Horizons): Monitoring, Early Warning Systems and health facility interventions for pregnant and postpartum, infants and young children and health workers

Protocol:

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Version 4.0 dated 20 November 2023

Contents

Acronyms and definitions	5
Study synopsis.....	6
1. Study partners and investigators	8
1.1 Study partners.....	8
1.2 Study investigators.....	9
2. Introduction and study rationale	10
2.1 Description of the overarching HIGH Horizons project	11
3. Overall research objectives	13
4. Methodology.....	14
4.1 Overall study design.....	14
4.3 Study population.....	17
5. Study components	18
5.1 Participant observation.....	18
5.2 In-depth interviews (IDIs).....	19
5.3 Key informant interviews.....	20
5.4 Time-motion assessment.....	21
5.5 Survey of health care workers	24
5.6 Extraction of routine information.....	28
5.7 Assessment of thermal exposures	29
6. Data management	32
6.1 Qualitative enquiry datasets.....	33
6.2 Time-motion assessment.....	34
6.3 Survey of health care workers	34
6.4 Extraction of routine data.....	34
6.5 Assessment of thermal exposure.....	34
7. Dissemination and use of data for co-design workshops	34
8. Ethical considerations	35
8.1 Informed consent.....	35
8.2 Risks.....	37

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

8.5 Review boards.....	37
8.6 Other approvals	37
9. Timeline.....	39
10. References	41
<i>Staffing required</i>	44
Appendices.....	45
Appendix 1: Participant observation in facilities	45
Areas of observation	46
Part I: Infrastructure	46
Part II: Clinical practices and patient care during labour and delivery	46
Part III: Staff activities during routine care, antenatal and postpartum care	47
Part IV: Informal conversations with staff and administration:	48
Appendix 2: Topic guide for in-depth interviews with health care workers	49
1. Profile of participant	49
2. Introductory questions	49
3. Impacts of heat in the workplace	49
4. Impact of heat on overall wellbeing and health	50
5. Adaptation	51
6. Recommended interventions.....	51
Appendix 3: Key informant interview guide	54
Appendix 4: Health worker survey questionnaire	56
Appendix 5: Building checklist	66
Appendix 6: Room checklist.....	70
Appendix 7: Clothing questionnaire	75
Appendix 8: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for participant observation component.....	76
Health Care Worker Informed Consent Form for Participant Observations.....	80
Appendix 9: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for in-depth interview component.....	83
Appendix 10: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for key informant interview component.....	87

Appendix 11: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for time-motion assessment component..... 93

Appendix 12: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for survey component 99

Appendix 13: Information sheet for patients for participant observation component 105

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Definition
ANC	Antenatal care
AT	Apparent Temperature
CHC	Community Health Care
CS	Clinical services
CSV	Comma separated values
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immuno-sorbent assay
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning Systems
GAD	General Anxiety Disorder
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCW	Health care worker
HIV/AIDS	Human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
HMIS	Health Management Information Systems
IDI	In-depth interviews
IM	Intervention Mapping
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
NCD	Noncommunicable diseases
OCPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
ODK	Open Data Kit
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PHC	Primary Health Care
PHS	Public Health Services
PIS	Participant information sheet
PNC	Postnatal care
POPIA	Protection of Personal Information Act
PSS	Perceived Stress Scale
QoC	Quality of care
SA	South Africa
STAMP	Suggested Time-motion Procedures
TB	Tuberculosis
UK	United Kingdom
WBGT	Wet-bulb globe temperature
WHO	World Health Organization
WOMBAT	Work Observation Method by Activity Timing
WP	Work package

Study synopsis

Rationale: The frequency and intensity of temperature extremes, and heatwaves have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. Accumulating evidence shows strong links to adverse human health outcomes because of heat exposure. Infants, children, pregnant women, the elderly, and manual and outdoor workers are most vulnerable. Health care workers (HCWs) are also vulnerable to heat because of long working hours and unsatisfactory working conditions in poorly ventilated structures. Existing research on occupational heat exposure focuses on outdoor and manual laborers with limited research in HCWs and limited evidence from Africa. This study forms part of a larger project, the HIGH Horizons project, looking at the impact of climate change, heat specifically, in maternal and neonatal health. The study will enable us to present detailed analyses of how heat influences the health and work activities of maternal and neonatal HCWs; to co-design interventions based on a thorough understanding of the clinical contexts; and to establish a baseline for comparison with endline findings in the evaluation of health facility heat adaptation interventions.

Importantly, the study is designed to address a highly relevant question with great importance to society, and to future research in this area. This study will be conducted across multiple sites in three countries, which will increase international representation and generalisability.

Objectives:

- (A) To explore and measure how ambient temperature influences HCWs':
 - i) Work performance and productivity
 - ii) Perceived wellbeing
 - iii) Physical health
 - iv) Quality of care
- (B) To describe current practices for reducing the impact of heat exposure on work productivity, perceived wellbeing, physical health, and quality of care
- (C) To provide empirical evidence for informing the co-design of heat facility-based adaptation interventions and the baseline data for the evaluation of the interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe
- (D) To explore the feasibility and attitudes to interventions commonly used in heat adaptation
- (E) To quantify thermal exposures in the selected health care facilities through observation and continuous monitoring of the indoor thermal environment, and through HCW personal wearables

Study design: This study encompasses mixed methods research, including a repeated measures study design, participant observation, in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, and a time motion assessment. The study will be conducted in three countries, South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe. All activities are complemented by monitoring of the thermal environment in participating health facilities.

Methods: The study consists of the following components (sample size for each component):

- Participant observation in the antenatal, labour, postnatal, and neonatal health wards (2-4 weeks per facility)

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

- In-depth interviews (3-5 HCWs in the smaller facilities and 10-15 HCWs from the larger facilities in the respective countries)
- Key informant interviews (5-15 participants per country)
- A time motion assessment (together with the measurements of heart rate, body temperatures, and number of steps taken) (3 maternity wards in total, 1 in each country – observations performed over a period of 3-5 weeks)
- A self-administered survey by health workers together with biological measures of dehydration, done in the hot season and in the cooler season (160 HCWs overall, 80 in South Africa)
- Secondary analyses of routine facility services and human resource data
- Thermal exposure measurement within facilities

Mixed-method assessments will take place in antenatal, labour, postnatal, and neonatal health clinics/wards. The facilities selected in South Africa, Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre, are found in the Tshwane district. In Zimbabwe, Chitse Clinic, Dotito Clinic and Mt Darwin District Hospital are all in Mt Darwin District in Mashonaland Central province. The site selected in Sweden is Karolinska University Hospital in the northern part of Stockholm.

Population: The study population for the participant observation, in-depth interviews, time-motion assessment, and survey comprises HCWs, aged 18 years and older, currently working in a health care facility. All sexes are eligible. The health care facilities all have dedicated maternal and neonatal health services. The study population for the key informant interviews comprises policymakers, facility managers and other stakeholders who understand potential responses to heat exposure in facilities, and the kinds of interventions that may be feasible.

Ethical considerations: All participating sites will obtain approval from relevant local ethics committees. Prior to each participant's enrolment into the study, informed consent will be obtained in accordance with local and international ethical guidelines. Participation is voluntary and consent may be withdrawn at any time. There are minimal risks associated with participation in this study. The risks are primarily around data protection, which are mitigated through data security measures to ensure confidentiality and data protection. All study data and documents will be regarded as confidential, and the anonymity of participants must be maintained. Participant identification numbers will be used to label study documents and specimens. Researchers will ensure that interruptions to patient care are kept to a minimum. If any abnormal clinical outcomes are uncovered during the study, the participant will be referred for further care.

Dissemination: Outputs from this study will support co-production activities as part of the HIGH Horizons project. We will host co-production workshops with relevant stakeholders to co-design a set of interventions to mitigate the impacts of heat on health in health care facilities in South Africa and Zimbabwe. Data collected in this study will be shared with stakeholders when co-producing interventions. Additionally, study results will be disseminated among study participants, local, provincial and national government officials, advocacy groups, and researchers to support policy changes.

Funding acknowledgments: Research that will be conducted in this study is supported by the European Union (EU) under the Environmental and Health Call, Award number: 101057843 under the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027).

1. Study partners and investigators

1.1 Study partners

Name of institution	Country	Address
Climate and Health Directorate, Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand	South Africa	22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow Health Precinct, Hillbrow, Johannesburg, 2001
Centre for Sexual Health & HIV & AIDS Research (CeSHHAR)	Zimbabwe	4 Bath Road, Belgravia, Harare
Denmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU)	Denmark	Nker Engelundsveji, Bygnin 101A, 2800
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	Department of Medicine, Solna, 17177, Stockholm
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine Royal Charter (LSHTM)	London	Keppel Street, WC1E 7HT, London

The other collaborating partners in the HIGH Horizons consortium are:

- Ghent University (UGENT) - serves as the overall project coordinator.
- Lunds Universitet (ULUND) - offers unique technologies for early warning systems (EWSs) and critical capacity in coding for tailoring the ClimApp to the target audience and optimizing its functionality.
- World Health Organization (WHO) - provides guidance on indicators and surveillance and ensures the project findings are adequately exploited at the EU and global level.
- University of Graz (UNI GRAZ) - provides support in societal impacts of climate change, social vulnerability, and inequality analysis.
- Aga Khan Health Services (AKHS) Kenya - supports the measurements of the carbon emissions in health facilities with the Aga Khan Development Network's Carbon Management Tool.

1.2 Study investigators

Name of institution	Investigators
Wits RHI, Climate and Health Directorate	Dr Gloria Maimela (Principal Investigator), Mr Craig Parker, Prof Matthew Chersich, Dr Darshnika Pemi Lakhoo, Dr Fiona Scorgie
Centre for Sexual Health & HIV & AIDS Research (CeSHHAR)	Dr Nelson Muparamoto (Principal Investigator) Thabani Muronzie, Prof Stanley Luchters
Karolinska Institutet (KI)	Dr Nathalie Roos (Principal Investigator)
London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)	Prof Veronique Filippi (Principal Investigator), Dr Giorgia Gon, Dr Isabelle Lange (international coordinating team working together with Prof Debra Jackson)
Technical University of Denmark	Prof Jorn Toftum (Principal Investigator)

2. Introduction and study rationale

The frequency and intensity of temperature extremes, high ambient temperature (above the 90th percentile), and heatwaves have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. The increase is to such an extent that current average global temperatures are reported to be 1.1°C higher than the pre-industrial period (Chersich et al., 2020; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019; Turek-Hankins et al., 2021). Crossing the heat threshold (over 1.0°C) has severely impacted natural and biological systems but pertinently accumulating evidence shows strong links to adverse human health outcomes and mortality (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019). It is also estimated that 54% of the global population will be exposed to more than 20 days of deadly heat per year by 2100 (Zhao et al., 2021).

Africa has been shown to be vulnerable to climate change and growing extreme heat events. Over the past decade, heat extremes (above 45°C) were observed in some regions of the continent such as North Africa and South Africa (Iyakaremye, 2021). Studies also show that mean temperatures in regions such as central Africa and the sub-tropics have risen at double the global rate (Almazroui et al., 2020; Iyakaremye, 2021). Machine learning and mathematical modelling techniques project an increase in frequency and intensity of extremely hot days (when maximum temperature exceeds 35°C) across the African region, which poses a great challenge because of already low disaster management, low adaptive capacities, poor land use, and existing socio-economic inequalities (Almazroui et al., 2020; Iyakaremye, 2021).

Health care workers (HCWs) are at high risk of adverse outcomes due to heat exposure and are at a higher risk of heat exposure due to poor working environments. Many public health facilities in low and middle-income settings do not have optimal structural features and have poor or no centralised air-cooling or ventilation systems. Secondly, HCWs globally may be involved in work that is exertional in nature, over long working hours, in heavy, and warm personal protective clothing, further increasing their exposure to heat. With heat exposure, physical and emotional coping capacities may become strained, leading to poor work performance, increased rates of absenteeism, and poor job satisfaction. In South Africa, evidence already shows that sub-optimal working conditions are some of the key reasons HCWs are dissatisfied with their jobs (Payne et al., 2020). Additionally, repeated exposure to extreme indoor heat is likely to lead to heat-related illness and possibly hospitalization for those who are physiologically vulnerable (such as those with chronic conditions) which may in turn further strain the health care system. HCWs in labour wards and neonatal care units are required to be quick in their response and reactions under strict guidelines (in cases of obstetrical and neonatal emergencies) otherwise the health of patients may be compromised. An added burden of extreme heat exposure to already strained HCWs – facing long working hours, occupational burnout, stressful social and environmental conditions among other issues (Myers et al., 2011; Turek-Hankins et al., 2021) - is a huge concern.

Existing research on occupational heat exposure focuses only on outdoor and manual laborers such as agricultural and factory workers, because of exposure to direct heat and a dress code that may impair heat regulation (Flouris et al 2018). Current evidence concerning other occupations and heat exposure includes a systematic review conducted on 111 studies, which shows that 35% of individuals working under environmental heat stress conditions experienced heat strain (i.e., physiological consequences, such as core body temperature >38°C, ≥1 occupational heat strain symptom, such as serum creatinine concentration of >1,2 mg/dL, heat-associated self-reported nausea or vomiting) and 30% experienced reduced productivity (defined as loss of labour time, performance, or absence from work due to

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

occupational heat strain). However, no study included, focused on heat stress conditions among HCWs globally (Flouris et al 2018).

Climate change and heat impact policies in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden are impeded by major gaps in surveillance and observational research, including for essential occupations such as HCWs.

2.1 Description of the overarching HIGH Horizons project

The work outlined in this protocol is part of a larger project looking at the impact of heat and climate change in maternal and newborn health. The HIGH Horizons project (Figure 1), over four years, involves six partners in Europe, three in Africa and one international organisation (WHO) and centres on pregnant and postpartum women, infants, and health workers, groups heavily affected by climate change (<https://www.high-horizons.eu/>). It is funded by the European Union under the Environmental and Health Call.

Figure 1. Outline of the HIGH Horizons project organised according to work packages.

The broader HIGH Horizons project has six main components organised as work packages (WPs), each with specific tasks. The WPs/tasks serve to achieve four project objectives:

1. Identify and select suitable indicators for quantifying and monitoring global, EU, and national-level health impacts of extreme heat.
2. Develop and test an Early Warning Systems (EWS) using a smartphone app to provide individualized and locally adapted heat stress warnings.
3. Identify cost-effective, integrated adaptation-mitigation interventions to alleviate heat impacts on HCWs, and to reduce carbon emissions associated with health care.
4. Support global and EU climate policies and activities on the monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of climate change on health, and the strengthening of Early Warning Systems through guidance documents, and risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis.

2.2 Contribution of this sub-study to HIGH Horizons

This study protocol falls within WP2 of High Horizons (assessment of health impacts and facilities), task 2.2 (health worker impacts: measurement). Measurement of environmental exposures in facilities and assessment of heat impacts on health workers will inform WPs 3, 4 and 5 - to develop adaptation interventions in healthcare facilities. Hence, our study will focus on documenting how working in heat stress conditions in demanding maternal and neonatal services affect the productivity, quality of care, and wellbeing of HCWs. In addition, the study explores potential interventions that might be implemented to counter the impacts of heat. Here, we aim specifically to understand:

- i) What is currently being done to reduce heat impacts? How effective are these measures and what barriers do they face?
- ii) What interventions do HCWs suggest might be done?
- iii) What are the perspectives of HCWs towards commonly used heat adaptation measures?

Overall, the study will enable us: to present detailed analyses of how heat influences the health and work activities of HCWs working in maternal and neonatal services; to co-design interventions based on a thorough understanding of the clinical contexts; and to establish a baseline for comparison with endline findings in the evaluation of health facility interventions.

3. Overall research objectives

The objectives for the multi-country (in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe) study are:

- (A) To explore and measure how ambient heat influences HCWs':
 - i. Work performance and productivity
 - ii. Perceived wellbeing
 - iii. Physical health
 - iv. Quality of care
- (B) To describe current practices for reducing the impact of heat exposure on work productivity, perceived wellbeing, physical health, and quality of care

- (C) To provide empirical evidence for informing the co-design of climate change facility adaptation interventions and the baseline data for the evaluation of the interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe
- (D) To explore the feasibility of and attitudes towards interventions commonly used in heat adaptation
- (E) To quantify thermal exposures in the selected healthcare facilities through observation and continuous monitoring of the indoor thermal environment, and through HCW personal wearables

4. Methodology

4.1 Overall study design

This study consists of mixed methods research, including a repeated measures longitudinal study design, participant observation, in-depth interviews, key informant interviews and a time and motion study. The study will be conducted in three countries, South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe. All activities are complemented by monitoring of the thermal environment in participating health facilities. In South Africa and Zimbabwe, the mixed-method study will also inform the subsequent development of a facility-based heat adaptation intervention. Some measures applied in this assessment constitute the baseline for the 'post' evaluation of an intervention study. We will compare the baseline measures with those in the endline survey. The protocol for the endline survey will be submitted in a separate ethics submission.

The study consists of the following components:

- Participant observation
- In-depth interviews with HCWs in the selected facilities
- Key informant interviews
- A time and motion assessment (together with the measurements of heart rate, body temperatures, and number of steps taken)
- A self-administered survey by HCWs (together with biological measures of dehydration), done in the hot season and again in the cooler season
- Secondary analyses of routine facility services and human resource data
- Thermal exposure measurement within facilities

The timing of each of the components is not dependent on the completion of other components. Tools for these assessments have been designed to have a standard format and content that allows for cross-country comparison of key data elements. However, some modifications have been made to the tools to include setting-specific elements where relevant. Once all data are collected, triangulation will be done across the component, and findings from analyses will be collated into a report disseminated among local stakeholders who will be involved in selecting the final adaptation and mitigation package.

We will compare the findings of each component between the different sites, to identify important differences and similarities. At a higher level, the overall conclusions drawn in each site from analysis of all the different components will be compared across sites. While some components provide unique information (e.g., thermal measurements), several interrogate the same topic, but with using different research methods. For example, assessing heat symptoms in structured interviews, and

then in in-depth interviews. Together these data provide a richer understanding of the data and allow one to explore particularly important findings in more detail.

4.2 Research setting

Study sites

Mixed-method assessments will take place in antenatal, postnatal, and neonatal health care facilities. The study will take place in one hospital in Sweden, two facilities in South Africa and three in Zimbabwe (Table 1).

South Africa:

In South Africa, the catchment areas of the two facilities are situated in Region 6 in the Tshwane district; Gauteng Province (see Fig.1 below), Regions 6 covers an area of approximately 333 km².

Figure 1. Location of the hospital and CHCs in South Africa.

Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre:

Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre (CHC) are in region 6 East of Pretoria. Stanza Bopape CHC is a primary health care facility and serves a population of 261 989. Mamelodi Regional Hospital is situated at 3.5 km from Stanza Bopape CHC and is a referral centre for patients requiring a higher level of care including pregnant women with obstetric emergencies from Stanza Bopape CHC and other surrounding feeder clinics. The hospital has a catchment population of 334 577 and offers the following services: clinical specialties in fields of Medicine, Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Paediatrics, Psychiatry, Radiology, Emergency Medical Services, Trauma, non-communicable diseases (NCDs), and clinical management of HIV/AIDS, and TB (including preventative therapy), screening and laboratory (e.g., cervical screening and colposcopy services, HIV testing (ELISA and PCR) and TB (including drug-resistant TB)).

The hottest months of the year are in the region selected for the study are usually December, January and February, and the highest, minimum, and mean temperatures are: 30 °C, 17 °C, and 23 °C, respectively. Whereas the coldest months of the year are usually June/July, and the highest, minimum, and mean temperatures are 20/21°C, 5°C, and 13°C, respectively.

Zimbabwe:

The study will take place at three public health care facilities which are within Mashonaland Central Province, Mt Darwin District. Mt Darwin District has a total area of 459 219 Hectares. The three sites are Mt Darwin District Hospital (urban), and Chitse and Dotito Rural Health Care Clinics. Mt Darwin is approximately 155 kilometres from the capital city Harare in the north-eastern direction. It borders Shamva district to the South, Mozambique to the North, Muzarabani to the West and Rushinga to the East. According to the latest census 2022 report by Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency, Mt Darwin District had a population of 240 727 with 122 706 females and 118 021 males (Population & Housing Census 2022). The district has 40 wards and people living in this area mainly survive with communal and subsistence farming and a bit of artisanal gold mining. The average temperature in the district is 24°C in summer and 14°C in winter. The hottest months in the year are usually October, November and December while the coldest months are June and July.

Mt Darwin District Hospital, Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic, Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic

Mt Darwin District hospital is a primary care and a referral facility for the district. A range of services are offered which include curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male and female ward, theatre, laboratory and pharmacy. Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic is situated 18 km from Mt Darwin Hospital. Services offered include curative, maternity related services, postnatal care, outpatient, and inpatient related services. Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic is the oldest facility in the district. It is a primary care clinic situated 28 kilometres from Mt Darwin District Hospital. The clinic is managed by a nurse in charge who oversees all departments. Services offered include curative (chronic condition screening, treatment, monitoring and follow-up, TB screening, initiation, and management), maternity-related services (antenatal care, booking follow-up visits, delivery, postnatal care), visual inspection with acetic acid and cervicography for cancer, and lastly outpatient and inpatient related services.

Sweden - Karolinska University Hospital:

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

The site selected in Sweden is Karolinska University Hospital in the northern part of Stockholm (Solna) and is a national referral centre for high-risk pregnancies and deliveries as well as regional referral centre for specialised high-risk pregnancies and deliveries.

The Karolinska University Hospital has 3700 births per year, the majority are high risk pregnancies. This is to be compared with a high volume and low risk delivery ward in a large hospital serving the south of Stockholm with 7600 births per year.

The climate in Sweden includes the four seasons, where winters are from November to February when the temperature drops below 0 degree Celsius, and summers are in general not too warm with mean temperatures of 23°C, but hot days can occur with temperatures of up to 35°C.

Table 1: Description of facilities

Name of proposed facility sites	Facility level	Number of women attending ANC (first visit) per month (average)	Number of deliveries per month (average)	Number of HCWs employed in antenatal care and delivery units (auxiliary midwives, nurses, midwives, doctors)
South Africa				
Stanza Bopape CHC	Primary health care facility	250	74	82 (77 Professional Nurses, 5 Doctors)
Mamelodi hospital	District hospital	(High risk cases from PHC)	780	108 (101 Professional Nurses, 7 Doctors)
Zimbabwe				
Mount Darwin District Hospital	District hospital (Primary care and referral for district)	205	164-180	12 midwives, 2 doctors, 14 nurses and 6 nurse aides
Dotito rural health care centre	Primary health care facility	28	25-30	5 nurses and 1 midwife whole clinic, no doctor.
Chitse rural health care centre	Primary health care facility	30	18-20	5 nurses and 1 midwife, no doctor whole clinic.
Sweden				
	Tertiary level	N/A (high risk pregnancies receiving basic ANC in a primary health care centre)	308	Auxiliary nurses, Midwives, obstetricians. Exact numbers to be confirmed (approx. 12-16 Ob/Gyn, 25 midwives and 20 auxiliary nurses)

4.3 Study population

The study population for the participant observation, in-depth interviews, time-motion study, and health worker survey comprises HCWs, aged 18 years and older, working in a health care facility in one of the study sites in South Africa, Zimbabwe or Sweden. All sexes are eligible. The health care facilities all have dedicated maternal and neonatal health services.

The following groups of HCWs will be eligible for enrolment:

- Nurse of any grade, including professional nurse, auxiliary nurse, and neonatal nurse
- Midwife
- Obstetrician /Gynaecologist
- Paediatrician/Neonatologist

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

- Other type of doctor (e.g., intern, medical officer)
- Allied health worker such as physiotherapist
- Clinical associate
- Other staff working in the ward, including cleaning staff, community health care workers, phlebotomist and porter

The specific study populations will differ across the study components.

Key Informant Interviews will be conducted among policymakers, facility managers and other stakeholders who understand potential responses to heat exposure in the facilities, and the kinds of interventions that may be feasible.

5. Study components

5.1 Participant observation

Ethnographic participant observation will be carried out in the antenatal, labour, postnatal, and neonatal wards of the selected facilities, over a period of 2-4 weeks.

5.1.1 Objective

The objective of these observations is two-fold: (1) to understand how heat and other thermal climate factors can affect HCWs' wellbeing, physical health, and productivity in the workplace (aligns with study objective A), and (2) to document existing practices in the facilities to reduce the negative effects of heat (aligns with study objective B).

5.1.2 Sampling

There is no 'sampling' in this method *per se*, but rather a field of observation, which is wide and encompasses all HCWs who deliver care, patients, visitors, and other facility staff who are present in this field (i.e., in the above-mentioned wards) or pass through it during the observation periods. However, **the main focus of the participant observation will be the HCWs**. Patients, visitors, and other facility staff will not be specifically observed; only when they interact with the HCWs being observed will their behaviour be recorded by the researcher in their notes.

5.1.3 Data collection

A trained research nurse or a qualitative social science researcher with experience in clinical settings will conduct participant observation (which includes informal conversations) at the health facility, paying attention to the work and structural environment and to people's activity in the relevant clinics or wards. Particular attention will be paid to the organisation of care in the wards; interpersonal dynamics (both amongst staff and between HCWs and patients); interaction with the built environment (points of refuge, relief, and discomfort); signs of stress; and work practices, including quality of care and respectful care. Through observations and informal conversations with staff, the researcher will also capture how health workers are reacting and responding to heat, and the coping strategies they have developed.

Observations will be undertaken for 2-4 weeks per facility, at varying shifts throughout the day and night. Wherever possible, observations will be timed to coincide with days with high temperatures, and with the warmest times of the day. An observation guide (Appendix 1) will provide structure on which aspects to observe, based on the two study objectives (A and B) that this component addresses. Based on this guidance, a journal will be kept by the observer in a format decided within

the team (written and/or audio), with the notes transcribed and fleshed out to generate 'thick descriptions', as soon as possible after each observation and typed up for analysis. Information and insights from this component will feed into the development of the topic guide for the IDIs.

At times the researcher may pose questions or engage in informal conversations with HCWs, but only at the convenience of the HCW and without interfering with the care being provided to women. HCWs will be reassured that our observations will be anonymised, are not intended to document poor practice or clinical 'errors' and will not be shared with their supervisors. Prior to the commencement of observations, the research team will meet with facility managers to explain the observation process and to reassure them that the functioning of their facility will not be unduly impacted by this research.

5.1.4 Data analysis

Using qualitative data analysis software (e.g., NVivo), transcribed fieldnotes will be open-coded by members of the research team, following a Grounded Theory approach (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Development of analytical codes will be an iterative process and will involve constant reflections and discussions within the research team until a full codebook has been developed. The codes will be developed inductively but also aligned with the central research questions. A portion of the dataset will be independently double-coded to check reliability of code allocation. Codes will then be clustered together and grouped under broader categories, from which key themes will be identified and written up in a report. This report will be read and discussed by the research team, and its contents used to inform the final topic guide for the in-depth interviews.

5.2 In-depth interviews (IDIs)

5.2.1 Objectives

The IDIs in this study are designed to align with study objectives A, B, and C. Specifically, the objectives of the IDIs are: to gain an understanding of how heat affects HCWs' work performance, quality of care, health, and wellbeing; to document HCWs' coping mechanisms and heat adaptation behaviour; and to collect descriptive data that will inform the co-design of heat adaptation interventions that are appropriate for health facility settings. Semi-structured, in-depth interviews allow the interviewer to develop a strong rapport with participants and encourage richer and more detailed responses to questions.

5.2.2 Sampling

Participants will be purposively sampled from HCWs in maternal and newborn care and will include a mix of genders, ages, and roles (midwife, obstetrician, etc.). Throughout participant enrolment, stratification of the sample according to these criteria will be monitored to ensure an even spread across genders, ages, etc. In South Africa and Zimbabwe, approximately 10-15 HCW staff in each of the larger facilities and 3-5 in the smaller facilities will be recruited for in-depth interviews, while in Sweden, 10-15 health worker staff at the hospital will be recruited. The study team will request assistance from facility managers to identify eligible staff and will then meet with these staff members to explain the study and request their participation.

5.2.3 Data collection

In-depth interviews will be conducted with enrolled HCWs using a semi-structured interview topic guide in English. Participants may be encouraged to use local languages such as isiZulu, Sesotho or Shona if that allows more free and comfortable expression. A provisional interview topic guide has been developed, based on the relevant study objectives (Appendix 2), and may be further amended

to incorporate insights from the participant observations. The finalised topic guide to be submitted to Wits HREC as an amendment.

Interviews will last approximately 1 hour. Written informed consent will be obtained from participants, and all IDIs will be recorded with a handheld digital device. The recordings will be immediately uploaded to an encrypted online repository on SharePoint that is only accessible to members of the research team. Interviewers will also be required to write extensive field notes that will be used as part of the data analysis process.

Findings from other data collection methods (time-motion assessment, survey) will be applied and probed during the IDIs, thereby allowing for triangulation of the data.

Anonymity: All participants will be assured that their information will be held confidentially, with access restricted to within the research team undertaking fieldwork and analysis. All identifying features of their interview will be masked or removed.

5.2.4 Data analysis

Interview recordings will be transcribed verbatim for analysis. Quality checks on the transcriptions will be carried out by the research team, where a sample of transcripts will be spot-checked against the audio to ensure fidelity of transcription. If a substantial portion (i.e., more than 30%) of a transcript has been translated into English, this translation will be checked through back-translation into the original language and then reviewed by a native speaker of this language. Analysis of transcripts will be an ongoing process during data collection, to ensure that early findings and insights can be used to inform the later interviews.

Qualitative data analysis software (e.g., NVivo) will be used to manage and code the data. A thematic approach to analysis will be taken, based on methods described by Braun & Clarke (2006). Researchers will develop a coding tree that will be based on core research questions and include themes that emerged throughout fieldwork, from reading the literature, and from discussions with the wider team involved in this sub-study and related work packages. Coding trees can be adapted to country contexts and reflect issues related to each setting or to the interests of researchers. Researchers will conduct a thematic analysis and produce an analysis report, and the overall qualitative findings will be applied and combined with the results from other study components to inform the development of heat adaptation interventions specific to each setting.

5.3 Key informant interviews

Key informant interviews will be held with health facility, district, and regional managers to gain contextual information central to the development of strategies and interventions to cope with high heat in each setting. Additionally, we may interview a small number of other individuals in the community and in other posts of expertise/authority identified through fieldwork as being sources of information on extreme heat adaptation strategies, HCW wellbeing, and quality of care. The interviews will focus on what is known about the impact of heat on the community and the health facility, and heat adaptations that are being undertaken in other institutions or with the community.

5.3.1 Objectives

The objectives of these interviews are to learn about key informants' perspectives on the impact and gravity of heat exposure and climate change in each setting and their opinions on the feasibility and acceptability of extreme heat adaptation strategies. Interviews will gather data on practices in the community or in other institutions that are employed for adaptation to hot temperatures –

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

information that may have implications for the design of appropriate adaptation interventions (aligned with study objective D). Findings from these interviews are intended to inform the development of the intervention in later stages of the project.

5.3.2 Sampling

Health facility management, policymakers as well as others in the health system who oversee or are involved with managing facility or district health operations, or those who have experience working in climate change adaptations or who have information about heat adaptations, and who agree to be interviewed, are eligible for enrolment. During interviews and participant observation at the facilities, the researcher may become aware of additional individuals in the community with heat adaptation experience. In this case, the researcher may contact these individuals and invite them for an interview. We anticipate that 5-15 participants will be enrolled per country. We will sample purposively to ensure enrolment of a range of different types of participants with diversity of expertise.

5.3.3 Data collection

Interviews will be conducted in a language and in a private setting convenient for the key informant (Appendix 3). The participant will receive an information sheet, be offered the opportunity to ask questions about the study, and their written informed consent will be obtained prior to the start of the interview. We anticipate that interviews will last between 45-60 minutes. As with the IDIs, the interview will be digitally recorded, with the participant's consent. Written notes will also be taken by the interviewer. The recordings will be immediately uploaded to an encrypted online repository on SharePoint that is only accessible to members of the research team. We will follow Standard Operating Procedures for data security, especially during storage and transmission of data.

Anonymity: All key informants will be assured that their information will be held confidentially within the research team undertaking fieldwork and analysis. Parts of their interview that may identify them will be masked or removed.

5.3.4 Analysis

Interview recordings will be transcribed verbatim (and translated into English, where relevant) for analysis. Quality checks on the transcriptions will be carried out by the research team, where a sample of transcripts will be spot-checked against the audio to ensure fidelity of transcription. Where a substantial portion (i.e., more than 30%) of a transcript has been translated into English, this translation will be checked through back-translation into the original language and then reviewed by a native speaker of this language. Interview transcripts will be analysed using the same methods described above for the in-depth interviews.

A process of synthesising the findings and insights from all three qualitative methods will be undertaken at their conclusion, to draw connections between common themes in the different datasets and identify key areas and findings for taking forward in the co-design of the intervention.

5.4 Time-motion assessment

5.4.1 Objectives of study component

1. To capture quality of care using instruments such as the safe birth checklist, as a means of documenting the impacts of heat on quality of care
2. To create “workflow time charts” through observing and recording the sequence of activities carried out by HCWs in labour wards, as a means of documenting how heat exposure may influence workflow

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

5.4.2 Rationale for selecting time-motion methodology

Time-motion methodology is well suited to direct observation activities conducted over time to capture workflow, interactions and disruptions in health care facilities with the aim of understanding whether these affect efficiency and quality of care provided by health care workers (Lopetgui et al., 2014; Tanzini et al, 2021). The use of time-motion studies is novel in investigating HCWs and heat exposure and will complement more classic ethnographic methods we employ in health facilities such as participant observation, informal discussions and interviews. Close observations provide an opportunity to capture the significance of such aspects as lethargy and patient interactions that may otherwise be overlooked.

5.4.3 Location and sampling

The study will be conducted in maternity wards within high-volume hospitals and community healthcare centres. We will conduct the study in three hospitals, and a community healthcare centre with approximately 800-1000 deliveries per year each (1 in Zimbabwe, 2 in SA and 1 in Sweden). A list of all eligible nurses will be accessed from department heads or relevant authorities, and recruitment activities will be conducted in labour wards (e.g., High Horizon study nurse requests to join staff meetings and present the HCW study or approach the nurses one person per time). A list of all potentially eligible nurses will be drawn up and participants randomly selected using computer generated random number sequence and enrolled into the observation study following informed consent procedures.

5.4.4 Study procedures

All the study procedures will follow Suggested Time-motion Procedures (STAMP) (Zheng et al., 2011). Here the study will comprise two main components. Firstly, we will capture/assess medical supply/instrument availability by using a survey adapted from the WHO Safe Birth Checklist (WHO SCC). The objective of this component is to check the availability and functionality of essential birth supplies in designated rooms or areas (e.g., duty rooms, labour or delivery room and the neonatal ward), and that data will be used to understand dimensions and barriers to quality of care (QoC). The data will also be used to determine whether those reflect international guidelines and signal functions for caring for mother and the newborn, and for providing comprehensive obstetric care (WHO, 2015b).

In the second component, we will use the Work Observation Method by Activity Timing (WOMBAT; Westbrook & Ampt, 2009) tool (see Fig. 2) a computerised tool to collect multiple dimensions of clinical work patterns (who, what, when and why) as well as comprehensive contextual information (patients and colleagues) and interrupted tasks. The time taken for each of the dimensions and completeness of the task is recorded on the tool. WOMBAT covers six broad work task categories, and each task is designed to cover (i) activity being undertaken (ii) other people involved in the task (iii) the method of task performance. The tool also allows researchers to add more detail to work task categories. These are also called workflow charts. When a birth attendant performs an action, the observer will record the action using a tablet. We will use continuous observation because the timing of procedures, particularly delivery itself, is typically unpredictable. If there is a case where an action has multiple dimensions that need to be recorded, the software will automatically timestamp the interval of each task together with any other additional selection. The tool allows interruptions (i.e., response to external stimuli) and multitasking (i.e., one or more tasks performed simultaneously) to be recorded with timestamps. We will aim to perform observations over a period of 3-5 weeks for each period (cool vs hot) and at different times of the day to be able to capture patterns across the shift. The number of hours of observations are based on the volume of deliveries HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

during the observation period. This process will be implemented on days with forecasted high temperatures and cooler days. The data will be captured by an observer using a tablet.

Figure 2. WOMBAT time-motion data collection tool

5.4.5 Data collection

A nurse or junior social science researcher will conduct the time-motion methods with supervision from an experienced social scientist. Wearable sensors will be used by HCWs to assess steps taken during a shift, heart rate and heart rate variability. Health workers will be able to view their heart rate and other results of their sensors. This may alter behaviours, introducing bias. Health workers will be given the devices prior to the study so that they become accustomed to them, and likely the biases will not be influenced by temperature. We will also measure the core temperatures of health workers (see details in the Assessment of thermal exposures section).

These observation-based methods are flexible, which is needed in the context of childbirth, for example, where there is a large amount of uncertainty (volume of clients, transition from one to two patients – mother and baby – and unpredictable complications) (Gon et al, 2020).

5.4.6 Data analyses

We will compare the completion of the different components of care that are observed to the recorded temperatures.

Data management and analyses will be conducted in STATA or R. Time expressed in each time category will be expressed as a proportion of total observation time. Descriptive analyses will be used to describe the outcomes, contextual variables, and potential confounders for the relationship of the study outcomes with temperature. Observational data collected by study staff will be linked with information on the number of steps performed by health workers, to investigate if there are any differences in workflow efficiency based on temperature exposures. We will determine whether

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

there is a reduction in steps at higher temperatures. We will compare all of the study data taken during the hot period with data during the cooler period. The changes in heart rate and other data collected from the sensors will also be compared across periods and used to evaluate potential causal pathways, where, for example, a reduction in activity with temperature is accompanied by an increased heart rate. We will use chi-square tests for comparing categorical data and Student's t-tests for continuous data that has a normal distribution, and Wilcoxon Rank Sum for continuous data that has a non-normal distribution.

5.5 Survey of health care workers

An electronic survey will be administered through a tablet among HCWs across the three countries (Appendix 4). It will consist of two phases, one in the hot season (November – January in SA) and one in the cooler season (June - August in SA). The survey in the hot season will be timed, where possible, to take place when the temperature is above the 25°C threshold. In total, 160 HCWs will be invited to participate twice in the survey, of which 80 will be from South Africa. We will enrol the same participants in the first and second surveys where possible. If we are unable to interview the same participant in the second round, we will recruit additional health workers to reach our target number (n=160).

5.5.1 Objectives of the survey

1. To obtain data on HCW characteristics, especially on their perceived health status and mental health
2. To document the impact of heat exposure on health worker wellbeing and work performance (study objective A)
3. To understand the perspectives of health workers towards interventions currently used to reduce heat exposure in the workplace, and views on what additional interventions might be implemented (study objectives B and D)

5.5.2 Study population

All HCWs and other staff working in the antenatal clinics, obstetric units, including labour wards, or neonatal wards or clinics. The study population consists of the following HCW cadres:

- Nurse of any grade, including professional nurse, auxiliary nurse and neonatal nurses
- Obstetrician /Gynaecologist
- Paediatrician/Neonatologist
- Other types of doctors (e.g., intern, medical officer)
- Clinical associate
- Allied health workers such as physiotherapists
- Other staff working in the ward, including community health care worker, phlebotomist, cleaning staff and porters

Inclusion criteria

Participants will be enrolled in this study only if they meet ALL the following criteria:

1. be aged ≥ 18 years
2. Be working in antenatal, labour ward or neonatal ward during the period of the study
3. willing to provide consent to participate in the study

Participants who have participated in any of the other study components will not be excluded from this component.

5.5.3 Sample size

In each of the two phases of the study, we aim to enrol 160 participants (estimated 80 participants in South Africa, 40 in Zimbabwe, and 40 in Sweden), with the number varying depending on willingness of staff to be interviewed. The sample size was determined by the maximum health workers available in the setting and resource constraints, rather than calculated based on an anticipated outcome measure.

5.5.4 Study measures

The survey will measure the HCW's wellbeing (WHO Well-being Index for Health Workers tool¹), psychological status (Cohen's perceived stress scale (Cohen, 1986; PSS-4), and General Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7), perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers perceive their health status and working conditions.

Wellbeing stress and anxiety tools mentioned above have been used and/or validated in several languages and countries and for a range of sub-populations. The tools and versions we will use are:

- A) The WHO Well-being Index for Health Workers provides a measure of self-reported mental health status. It includes the same five questions as the WHO-5², which is available in 30 languages (Topp et al, 2015).
- B) Psychological status (perceived stress scale) includes questions on general feelings and thoughts of stress over the past month, with 5 categories of responses: ("never" to "very often"). We will use the PSS-4 version (Vallejo et al, 2018).
- C) GAD-7's introductory question is "Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems?". As its name indicates it has 7 questions, each with 4 possible response categories ("not at all" to "nearly every day") (Swinson, 2006; Spitzer, Kroenke & Williams, 2006). The choice of the exact cut-off-point for establishing anxiety will depend on context (Plummer et al, 2016). The validity of GAD-7 has been assessed in South Africa (Kigoli, 2019), and will be used in this study.

Many survey questions for perceived heat stress and thermal comfort have been adapted from occupational health tools used in Hothaps (Kjellstrom, 2014) and HeatShield (Messeri, 2019) projects across different settings as well as from the Heat Strain Score index (Dehghan, 2013).

5.5.5 Study procedures

Recruitment

In South Africa, sampling of HCWs will be random, where a list of all potentially eligible health workers will be obtained from facility managers or similar, and a random selection invited to participate in the study. In Zimbabwe and Sweden, all the eligible HCW in the facilities will be invited to participate.

Enrolment procedures

¹ <https://www.measureevaluation.org/rbf/indicator-collections/structural-indicators/who-well-being-index-for-health-workers.html>

² [WHO-5 questionnaire - English \(psykiatri-regionh.dk\)](#)

Participants that have been selected will be provided with information regarding the nature of the study, study activities, the risks and benefits of participation and the approximate time it will take to complete the survey. All this information will be presented verbally during meetings with staff. All potentially eligible staff will be provided a participant information sheet (PIS). This information will clearly state that participants may withdraw from the study at any stage without any prejudice and with no obligation to give a reason. Participants will be given an opportunity to ask questions. If HCWs are interested in participating, they will sign an informed consent form prior to partaking in any study procedures. For this study, consent will be obtained in wet ink after the participant has confirmed that they have read the PIS. The informed consent procedures will be conducted by a research staff member that is trained in study procedures and has expertise in research ethics. Enrolment will be complete once the target sample size is reached.

Assignment of study identification number

Once a participant is enrolled into the study, an alphanumeric (country code, followed by facility code, followed individual number ranging from 1-200) participant identification number will be randomly generated and used to key code the participants into the data storage. This participant identification number is pseudonymised and will be unique to the participant. Participants details will be stored separately from the other study documents, with the key to linking participant identification numbers and personal identifying information stored securely by a data manager or other appropriate research staff member.

Survey procedures

The HCWs will be invited to complete a self-administered survey questionnaire on a tablet or a smartphone (using a common open-source mobile data collection platform such as ODK). The questionnaire will be in English. Data will be collected at entry to the study during the cooler time of the year, and then repeated during hotter season. Where possible, we will time the interviews with days that have high forecasted temperatures. HCWs will be invited to complete their questionnaires wherever possible at the end of a day shift.

Additionally, the participants weight and height will be measured by a research staff member using standardised techniques and instruments.

Urine specimens will be collected on the same day as the interview, at the end of the shift. The urine specific gravity, a commonly used biomedical marker for hydration status, will be measured using handheld optical refractometer on site, by a suitably trained research staff member. The device we will use is a digital hand-held urine specific gravity refractometer. Urine specimens will be discarded after testing, strictly adhering to waste procedures at the site.

If a participant chose to withdraw, a case of withdrawal will be documented. The data that has already been collected will not be deleted, unless requested so by the participant. Withdrawal or deletion of data may be required at the discretion of study staff in case of incorrect enrolment, such as in the case of a failure to meet inclusion/exclusion criteria. Any protocol violations will be reported to the ethics committee.

Data sources

There are three sources of primary data for this study component. The first source is the data obtained from participants that self-complete the survey. This will include a wet ink signed informed

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

consent form. The second data source is the urine test results, and the third source is weight and height results. These data will be linked to the same study participant using anonymised participant ID numbers.

5.5.6 Data analyses

1. General considerations

Analysis will be done using STATA or R.

2. Analysis population

The total pooled population from all three sites (South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden) will form the primary population for analysis, though exploratory site-specific analyses will also be done.

3. Descriptive analyses

Prior to the data being analysed for addressing the study objectives, the study population and data will be described to understand the main characteristics. We will, for example describe age and type of HCW in a table, by study site. We will also tabulate participant characteristics in the first and second phase of the study should there be some replacement of participants in the second round. Temperature and other environmental exposures will also be summed and presented in a table, by site and survey round.

4. Analysis of study outcomes

A primary outcome of assessment is mild-moderate hypovolaemic dehydration during a work shift, operationalised as a binary variable (yes, no, missing). Dehydration is defined as urine specific gravity >1.015. A chi-square test will compare dehydration levels between sites and cooler and hotter seasons. Multilevel linear models will be used to account for the clustered nature of the data (clustered per facility and at individual level) and the influence of confounders. The continuous thermal environment monitors inside the facilities will provide information about the actual heat exposure on each day, allowing us to assess if there is an association between the thermal exposures and any of the survey responses or hydration measurements.

Other secondary outcomes will also be assessed. We will compare, for example, the number of heat symptoms reported by participants during the study phases and all the other measures of wellbeing related to heat.

Analyses will be done using data pooled across all the three sites, but we will also assess whether there are differences between countries, and by phase in each country.

5.5.7 Limitations of the health worker survey component

Selection bias, either in the selection of study sites and participants for the study may affect internal validity. Selection bias will, however, be reduced by the selection of multiple study sites, and inviting all health workers to participate in the study in Zimbabwe and Sweden or using a random selection of eligible participants from sites in South Africa.

Most information is self-reported and there is no mechanism to verify the accuracy of information provided by the participant. Self-report can incur recall and other related biases. We aim to improve HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

the quality of the data by programming logic and validation checks into the survey and having a study staff member available if any questions arise during the completion of the survey. The use of biological measures such as urine specific gravity does help to reduce the extent of this bias.

We are comparing multiple secondary outcomes across the time periods, which incurs the problem of multiple testing and the possibility for introducing Type I errors.

There are also concerns around potential confounders due to the relatively long time lag between surveys, and systemic changes may have occurred in the work environment over that time that were unrelated to the study.

There are multiple challenges to service delivery in health facilities in South Africa. These challenges fluctuate and may vary considerably between months. It may be difficult to disentangle these issues from impacts of heat, and health workers may draw spurious links between heat exposure and some of the constraints, while the problem may be due to supply chain concerns or electricity load shedding, for example.

5.6 Extraction of routine information

Health services and human resources data will be extracted from registers and health information systems over the past 4-5 years to collect additional information on the quality of clinical care, service utilisation and, if possible, to estimate absences and reasons for absence among MNCH HCWs during and outside periods of extreme heat.

5.6.1 Data extraction

- We will seek permission from the Department of Health to access data from maternity health records. This will be done through a letter to the relevant health authorities seeking permission to access the data. The letter will include specific details on how we plan to ensure confidentiality of data obtained in compliance with the POPI Act and other relevant legislation in SA. Once approval is obtained, we will extract information retrospectively from paper-based (South Africa and Zimbabwe) and electronic (Sweden) medical registers in maternity units, human resources registers and HMIS, to measure over the past four years (2019-2023). Information to support these indicators will be sourced from individual maternal clinical records and registers that are used during labour. To access individual maternity records, we will review maternity admissions registers between 2019 and 2023, randomly select 400 file numbers and then retrieve up to 250 maternity records for review, accommodating the fact that some of the records might be misfiled or be missing.
- The following indicators of quality of care, workload and productivity will be collected:
 - use of partograph, intrapartum stillbirths, other adverse events, on administration of key procedures in antenatal or postnatal care (syphilis screening, hepatitis B vaccines), referrals to and from other facilities,
 - Service utilization data (ANC, PNC, Caesarean section, vaginal deliveries, other)
 - Providers' absences and reasons for absence, if available

Data extraction will be carried out onto a RedCap database in South Africa. The period of data extraction will include the period of data collection for this study, to take into account the effects of heat on the number of patients and its influence on quality of care (Si et al, 2019). We anticipate challenges with the quality of retrospective data – e.g., incomplete or missing data in the source documents. We will overcome this through pre-screening of the files, selecting only files that meet a minimum quality threshold – at least 80% of the required fields available for extraction.

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

5.6.2 Data analyses

The main exposures for the data analyses will be time-series recordings (daily, weekly or monthly) over several years and values of temperatures, windspeed, air humidity, and outdoor temperatures obtained for the same time points (daily, weekly or monthly) from a source such as www.tutiempo.net (Part et al, 2021). Indoor temperatures that have been obtained from procured temperature monitors placed within the facility will also be available over the study period and will be linked with the routine information we extract. We will perform linear regression analyses to determine whether there is a correlation (r statistic) between number of absences and temperature.

The potential influence of external factors such as COVID-19 will be taken into account by collecting data on the period of occurrence of key variables such lockdown and COVID-19 prevalence. We will stratify findings by COVID-19 study period to assess potential effect modification during that period. If we note patterns were considerably different over a period of lockdowns, for example, then we may exclude that data from the analysis.

5.6.3 Limitations of study component

The ability to access maternity records in public health facilities may be a challenge due to sub-optimal filing systems. Moreover, there may be data quality concerns, most especially around missing data that may impact on the information required for the study.

5.7 Assessment of thermal exposures

Thermal exposure assessments aim to measure the building's thermal environment, to make observations to characterize the building and its installations, and to examine how the buildings and their occupants can adapt to moderate their thermal exposure. Standardised indices will be used to evaluate and interpret thermal exposures. If feasible, measurement of air quality indicators could be included in the measurement framework.

5.7.1 Monitoring of the thermal environment

Indoors, humans exchange heat with the surroundings mostly through convection, radiation, and evaporation (Olesen and Madsen 1995). The building thermal environment should therefore be characterized through monitoring that includes at least the three parameters: air temperature, globe temperature, and air humidity. Globe temperature can be used to evaluate the mean radiant temperature. Ideally, measurements should include air speed, but this measurement is complicated and expensive and therefore not included in the study. Appendices 5 and 6 detail the building and room checklists that will be used to measure the thermal environments.

ISO 7726 (1998) describes the relevant parameters, requirements to instruments and standardized measurement procedures. The following description of indoor thermal exposure parameters is based on this standard.

Air temperature: The temperature of the air around the human body. The air temperature determines the heat transfer to or from the body by convection.

Globe and mean radiant temperatures: The amount of radiant heat exchanged between the body and the surroundings depends on the radiant heat fluxes exchanged by exposed body parts with the surrounding surfaces. Indoors, surface temperatures may deviate considerably, in particular with intense and prolonged solar irradiation on the building envelope and in poorly insulated buildings, creating a highly asymmetric radiant field. The mean radiant temperature can be used to evaluate the radiant heat fluxes and thus the amount of radiant heat exchanged between persons and the

enclosure. With a known air temperature (and air speed), the globe temperature can estimate the mean radiant temperature.

A simplified globe thermometer consists of a globe (ping-pong ball) in the centre of which is placed a temperature sensor (Simone et al. 2007). The temperature measured by the sensor element is an integrated measure of the radiant and air temperatures and it depends on the energy balance between the convective and radiant heat exchanges of the globe. The mean radiant temperature, and consequently the operative temperature, is not uniform in the room, but varies according to the location.

Air humidity: The air humidity influences the evaporative heat loss from a person. Under comfortable conditions, typically at temperatures below 26°C and in sedentary activity, air humidity has only a modest influence on the heat loss, but a considerable influence at higher temperatures or activity levels. Air humidity is thus a crucial parameter when assessing heat exposure.

To illustrate the configuration of a measurement device, Figure 3 shows custom-made air- and globe temperature sensors connected to a data logger. The air temperature sensor is shielded from radiation by the polished metal cylinder covering the pt-100 sensor element (the component that measures temperature). The cylinder allows the air to move around the sensor element. At the center of the ping-pong ball another pt-100 temperature sensor measures the globe temperature. The whole array of devices can be mounted on a small plate for easy installation on a suitable wall. The data logger used with this instrument has a built-in air humidity sensor.

Figure 3. Custom-made device for the measurement of air temperature, globe temperature and air humidity.

Information on the staff clothing and their activities is needed to assess heat stress with the indices wet bulb globe temperature, apparent temperature and predicted heat strain (described briefly below).

Thermal insulation of clothing: For HCW participating in the time-motion study, the clothing thermal insulation will be estimated with a short self-completed tick-off questionnaire reflecting the garments worn by the HCW (Appendix 7). This information will be used to inform the assessment of relation between temperature and health worker activity, where warm clothing can be a key factor mediating the impacts of heat. Based on tabulated values of garment insulation values, the intrinsic HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

clothing insulation will be estimated (ISO 9920-2009). See table below. Water vapour permeability of the clothing will be estimated at standard value of 0.45, unless particularly non-permeable garments are worn (apron or similar) (ISO 9920-2009).

Thermal clothing insulation	Clothing		I _{cl} (clo)
	1. Briefs, short-sleeve shirt, fitted trousers, calf length socks, shoes		0,5
	2. Underpants, shirt, fitted trousers, socks, shoes		0,6
	3. Underpants, coverall, socks, shoes		0,7
	4. Underpants, shirt, coverall, socks, shoes		0,8
	5. Underpants, shirt, trousers, smock, socks, shoes		0,9
	6. Briefs, undershirt, underpants, shirt, overalls, calf length socks, shoes		1,0
	7. Underpants, undershirt, shirt, trousers, jacket, vest, socks, shoes		1,1
Permeability	Normal clothes	0.38	

Metabolic rate (activity level): Metabolic rate quantifies the conversion of chemical into mechanical and thermal energy and gives a numerical index of the activity. In particular in hot climates, high levels of metabolic heat production associated with muscular work may aggravate heat stress, as large amounts of heat need to be dissipated, mostly by evaporation of sweat (Kerslake 2007). For HCWs participating in the time-motion study a wearable device attached to the wrist will be used to measure heart rate, heart rate variability and count the number of steps taken during a work shift.

Body core temperature: Body core temperature is a useful heat stress metric (Huizenga et al. 2004, Davie & Amoore 2010). Conventional measurement of body temperature usually involves ingestion of an electronic pill or use of a rectal thermometer, which will not be feasible in this field study. Instead, body temperature of the HCWs involved in the time-motion study will be estimated with a non-invasive sensor attached to torso with a strap or a medical patch such as the following the following core sensor: [CORE Body Temperature Sensor](https://www.corebodytemp.com/) at corebodytemp.com.

5.7.2 Observations of building and installation properties

The specification of the health care facilities and their installations will be characterized through checklists. Two checklists are appended as Appendices 5 and 6 – one for the building and one for each of the rooms where environmental measurements are made.

These specifications are also needed as input to the modeling of the effect on heat exposures and energy use of potential interventions.

Where: Measurements with the available instrumentation cannot be carried out in all rooms in a facility, and locations should be selected to represent where the staff has the longest or highest exposure, i.e., measurements should cover both critical and representative locations. When the exposed person changes work location between areas with different environmental characteristics, the evaluation or measurements should be made in each area and the sequence of time periods spent by the worker in the different areas should be recorded. These locations are likely to be rooms used for the provision of antenatal care, care of women in labour (surgical theatre, delivery unit), postnatal wards, and special care unit for newborns.

When: Measurements should be made throughout the study to cover the variability of indoor and outdoor conditions. Environmental parameters (air temperature, globe temperature, air humidity) are logged continuously at 10-15 min intervals during the period.

5.7.3 Indices to evaluate heat stress based on measurements

We use a range of heat indices to describe the heat exposure of health workers, each measure captures a different aspect of heat exposure.

Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT): ISO 7243 describes determination and assessment of thermal exposures with WBGT. WBGT is a screening method to establish the presence or absence of heat stress. If more detailed analysis of the heat exposure is necessary, the Predicted Heat Strain described below is recommended.

Without solar load as is often the case indoors in buildings, WBGT may be calculated from

$$\text{WBGT} = 0.7 \cdot t_{nw} + 0.3 \cdot t_g$$

With solar load, WBGT is adjusted for the effect of radiation:

$$\text{WBGT} = 0.7 \cdot t_{nw} + 0.2 \cdot t_g + 0.1 \cdot t_a$$

t_{nw} is the natural wet bulb temperature that can be estimated with the Stull formula from measurement of air temperature and relative air humidity (Stull 2011):

$$T_w = T \text{atan}[0.151977(\text{RH}\% + 8.313659)^{1/2}] + \text{atan}(T + \text{RH}\%) - \text{atan}(\text{RH}\% - 1.676331) + 0.00391838(\text{RH}\%)^{3/2} \text{atan}(0.023101\text{RH}\%) - 4.686035.$$

Apparent Temperature (AT): The apparent temperature of a set of meteorological conditions may be defined as equal to the air temperature at low wind speed, no extra radiation and at moderate humidity and activity (Steadman 1984).

With reasonable accuracy, the Apparent Temperature can be approximated by:

$$\text{Indoors: AT} = -1.3 + 0.92 \cdot t_a + 2.2 \cdot p_v$$

$$\text{Outdoors in the shade: AT} = -2.7 + 1.04 \cdot t_a + 2.0 \cdot p_v - 0.65 \cdot v_{10}$$

$$\text{Outdoors in the sun: AT} = -1.8 + 1.07 \cdot t_a + 2.4 \cdot p_v - 0.92 \cdot v_{10} + 0.044 \cdot Q_g$$

In which t_a is the ambient (air) temperature (°C), p_v the vapour pressure (kPa), v_{10} the wind speed measured 10 m above the ground (m/s), and Q_g the net extra radiation per unit area of body ($\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$).

Predicted Heat Strain (PHS): ISO 7933 describes a procedure for analytical evaluation and interpretation of thermal stress experienced by a person in a hot environment (ISO 7933-2004). Based on a comprehensive model of the heat transfer between the body and surroundings, the procedure evaluates thermal strain by excessive core temperature increase or water loss for a standard subject. In addition, the procedure allows determination of the exposure time during which the physiological strain is acceptable. As the procedure predicts physiological strain for standard persons it needs to be adapted if it should be used to assess thermal strain among vulnerable populations.

6. Data management

Data management will be carried out in accordance with the Data Management Plan developed for the EU and dated 30 November 2022. The data management will also meet requirements in accordance with the Protection of Personal Information Act South Africa. In accordance with this

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20 November 2023

plan, our data management has the following characteristics, which is common to all components, unless stated otherwise:

- Each participant will have a unique identification number, which will be the same in each quantitative and qualitative sub-study (possible example: country code, followed by facility code, followed individual number ranging from 1-200). This allows us to link data of individuals who participate in multiple components. All hard copies of patient identifying data will be stored in a locked cabinet.
- All of the quantitative data will be collected electronically on a tablet or smartphone and backed up as per the Wits RHI Standard Operating Procedures.
- All of the data will be analysed electronically.
- Data will be fully anonymised or pseudonyms will be used in reporting of the qualitative research, for example, when participant quotes are used.
- Each partner will store the data collected on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication.
- Data storage on local devices will be avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is necessary (e.g., the study statistician), then the data will be password protected and only include deidentified data.
- Access to data will be restricted to a limited number of study staff that have appropriate training to manage data.
- Data will not be sent by email but transferred safely using encryption or secure tools like Filesender.
- As most data are health-related, personal and sensitive, we cannot provide full open access to our datasets. As such, the datasets will not be entirely openly available, and conditions will be attached to access the data (i.e., restricted access). We will take actions to limit the restrictions, i.e., to have our datasets "as open as possible, as close as needed", by pseudonymisation/anonymisation of personal data where possible and by agreeing on a limited embargo.
- Non-personal data (e.g., environmental or ambient temperature data) will be made openly available unless sourced from a commercial source.
- Data ownership will be with the country teams in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe.
- All data will be stored in accordance with GDPR legislation and recognised data security standards. In South Africa specifically, data will be archived once study results are analysed for a minimum of six years.

Further details of data management for each study component are provided below.

6.1 Qualitative enquiry datasets

Qualitative data will be managed in the first instance by each country partner. Interview recordings will be transcribed, quality checked, and securely stored for two years after research findings are published, or for six years if the findings are not published, in accordance with South African research ethics protocols, and then destroyed. Researchers will type up fieldnotes, producing an anonymised version that can be shared only within the research team. Files will be analysed by each of the country teams of researchers and anonymised data will be securely transferred to the LSHTM server for cross-country analysis. Participant consent for sharing of anonymised outputs with project partners will be sought during data collection. Participants will be asked to consent for further

follow-up and for keeping their contact details securely on countries' respective servers for the duration of the project.

6.2 Time-motion assessment

Data on health workers behaviours captured using the computerised direct observation methods consist of electronic data linked to individual providers with unique identification numbers. Data will be rendered fully anonymous during analyses. Data generated in the course of research will be kept securely in electronic format as appropriate, in accordance with good practice in the storage of primary data, record keeping, ethical issues, GDPR legislation as well as the POPI Act in South Africa. Identifiable material will be stored separately from any observation notes and kept locked in drawers or protected computers, for example, where there are hard copy informed consent forms.

6.3 Survey of health care workers

Quantitative data from the structured interview survey will be collected electronically using an electronic platform such as ODK. Once collected, electronic data will be transferred to a secure password protected server at each site. The survey is self-administered; hence participants will enter all data directly onto a secure web data entry form. Data logic and validation checks will be configured into the survey, where possible, so that participants will receive warning messages at time of entry of inconsistent, incomplete or invalid data, to ensure quality and completeness of information. The self-reported data will not be queried for clarification or correction by study staff after electronic submission of the survey.

Each site will anonymise and clean data to ensure the confidentiality of the participants and data quality. Each site will use the data for their in-country analysis. Files will subsequently be securely transferred to the LSHTM server for cross-country analysis. Participant consent for sharing of anonymised outputs will be sought during data collection. Participants will be asked to consent for storing of their contact details securely on country's respective servers for a further 2-3 years after study completion. This is to be able to invite them to participate in evaluation studies post implementation of adaptation interventions.

6.4 Extraction of routine data

These are daily/weekly/monthly counts of aggregated data on number of events (i.e., caesarean section) extracted from registers and collected on a tablet (the list of variables is defined in Section 5.6).

6.5 Assessment of thermal exposure

Data on thermal exposure consist of time-series of temperatures and air humidities representing the entire measurement period. Data will be retrieved from the instrumentation in CSV format for further processing and analysis in statistical software as Stata or R. Data is stored on the logging devices and will be read out regularly by researchers visiting the facilities. Combined with data on clothing insulation and activity, indices for the assessment of the thermal exposure will be calculated and interpreted based on guideline values provided in the relevant standards.

7. Dissemination and use of data for co-design workshops

We will synthesize and apply the tool-specific data analysis relevant to each of the methods (e.g., statistical analysis for time in motion studies, routine data extraction and survey instruments, and thematic analysis for qualitative data). We will draw on the different data sources and identify

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

common themes, or areas where interventions might be done. Once we have identified common themes or potential interventions, we review the available data from each sub-study to identify whether the data support or points against use of the intervention. We will triangulate our data analysis and collate the assessment findings into a report, disseminated among study participants and local stakeholders such as department of health officials, facility managers, community leaders, and CHWs not participating in the study who will be involved in selecting the final adaptation and mitigation package.

The adaptation and mitigation intervention will primarily be implemented in South African and Zimbabwean facilities. The potential cost-benefits of interventions in Sweden will be assessed as there may only be marginal improvements in facility adaptation required.

Selection of the interventions will occur at each of the local health facilities or in a joint workshop in each country. We will host a full-day co-design workshop to discuss the findings of the baseline assessment reports, and to select several candidate adaptation and mitigation interventions.

The findings from the mixed-methods health worker assessment will be considered together with the assessment of indoor heat exposures. A report on the facility emissions mix based on the Aga Khan Development Network carbon emission tool will also be produced. That activity is covered by another Work Package in the HIGH Horizons project and a separate ethics submission. All of these sources of evidence will be brought together in co-design workshops hosted by the study team that will include health workers, community leaders, facility managers, and local and regional governments. Experts in thermal modelling, architecture, and emissions reductions will also attend. For example, they can contribute by modelling building-related interventions and calculating what these mean for exposure and energy use (if relevant).

The study team will use the Intervention Mapping (IM) approach (Eldredge et al., 2016; Fernandez et al., 2019), an established planning framework for developing an intervention in a stepwise manner, which has been used to guide public health interventions for decades. It involves an iterative path from problem identification to problem solving or mitigation, which will allow us to identify which interventions are to be targeted for change, and change techniques will be most effective. IM is grounded in participatory research methods to ensure that the intervention design match the context and target population needs. At heart, the study relies on a strong co-design element, where key intervention stakeholders are involved at each step. The workshops will culminate in the selection of several adaptation and mitigation interventions for thermal, emissions and cost-benefit modelling. These interventions will be tested in the next phase of the study, which will involve a separate ethics submission.

8. Ethical considerations

8.1 Informed consent

Before each participant is enrolled into the study, informed consent will be obtained in accordance with local and international ethical guidelines. The participant will be given a copy of the informed consent form, a copy of which will be retained by the research team. The informed consent form will be attached to a participant information sheet that will provide further information about the study, with an emphasis about voluntary participation. Participants will be asked to provide separate written informed consent for each of the study components. Participants can decline participation in all or some components of the study without disadvantages or repercussions. They can withdraw

their consent for study participation at any time. Appendices 8-13 include all informed consent forms for each study component.

There are several important ethical considerations regarding the participant observation activity. Principally, it is important that people know that they are being observed, what the purpose of the observation activity is, and how the data gathered through observations will be used. We will do this in several ways, tailored to each group being observed.

For **patients**, we will develop a simple, easy-to-read poster for display in the areas where the observations are taking place. The poster will explain the process of observation, the nature of data being collected, and how the privacy and confidentiality of those being observed will be maintained (for example, throughout all observations in facilities, the researcher will not observe sensitive procedures and they will position themselves in such a way as to ensure maximum privacy for the patients). The poster will also make it clear that the focus of the observation activity is actually the HCWs and not the patients. Also explained on the poster will be the fact that patients may opt out of being observed if they so wish that they have a right to decline participation, and that no negative consequences for their care will follow. It is important that patients are aware of this and feel comfortable to opt out if this is their choice, since many of have no alternative place to access their healthcare, and because there are often stark power dynamics between HCWs and patients.

To opt out of the activity, patients need to inform the researcher, who will be wearing a clearly visible, identifying badge. The researcher will then ascertain whether the patient consents to being observed (because they are in the researcher's field of vision) but does not consent to information about themselves being recorded in the observation notes for that day. In these cases, the researcher will continue with their observation but refrain from entering into the notes any information about the actions or words of the patient in question. If the patient does not consent to the researcher remaining in the room/ waiting area where the patient is visible at all, the researcher will move out of the area until that patient is no longer present.

The poster containing information for patients will be made available in appropriate local languages such as English, isiZulu and Sesotho in South Africa, and will make use of clear images to cater for illiterate patients. This poster will be submitted to Wits HREC at a later stage, as a protocol amendment. We will also inform the established community advisory boards of the study processes and procedures and emphasise that the study will not affect patient access to care.

For **HCWs** stationed in the wards where the observation is taking place, prior to the commencement of the observation activity, we will inform them collectively (in a meeting) of the purpose of the observations and what they will entail. We will explain that no personal identifying information will be collected on the individuals who are observed. HCWs will be given a chance to ask questions and express any concerns about the activity, and these will be addressed by the study team either in the same meeting, or privately if requested. It will be explained that participating in the observation activity is voluntary, and refusal to participate will have no repercussions for the individuals concerned. Written informed consent will then be obtained individually from all HCWs who agree to be observed. This consent will apply to the entire period of observation in each facility. Research staff will also be available to verbally respond to any concerns from patients and other staff in the healthcare facilities. In cases where a HCW being observed is interacting with an individual patient, the researcher will seek opportunities to verbally inform the patient why they are there and what

the observation activity is about. This explanation will draw on the information sheet that has been developed (Appendix 13) for distribution to patients to keep.

8.2 Risks

There are minimal risks associated with participation in this study. The are risks around data protection which is mitigated through data security measures to ensure participant confidentiality detailed further in the data management plan.

Participating in this study may be psychologically uncomfortable and stressful for some participants as some questions on their wellbeing and productivity may be considered personal. Participants may also be uncomfortable with the experience of being observed. These risks will be explained to the participants.

The collection of biomarkers (urine) and data on stress and anxiety may reveal staff who might benefit from clinical attention. Staff will have access to their results if they wish to have these. Staff who have gone above certain thresholds suggesting that they might benefit from clinical or mental health services will be informed and offered referral to a healthcare professional in public/private/occupational setting of the participant's choice, after discussion with the lead clinical researcher in each setting. The urine testing, and measurement of heart rate, body temperature and number of steps are unlikely to lead to physical discomfort.

The study will aim to avoid any interruptions to patient care and service delivery in the healthcare facility, by limiting the time taken to complete research components, and doing them outside of working hours where possible.

8.3 The site PI's will ensure that the trial protocol, participant information sheet, informed consent forms, and any other supporting documentation have been approved by the appropriate research ethics committee that is responsible for the study site prior to study start.

8.5 Review boards

All participating sites will obtain approval from relevant local ethics committees. The site PI's will ensure that the trial protocol, participant information sheet, informed consent forms, and any other supporting documentation have been approved by the appropriate research ethics committee that is responsible for the study site prior to study start. This protocol and accompanying ethics review committee documents cover study activities in South Africa only. The other sites will prepare a site-specific protocol and secure local ethical clearance, specifically obtained from:

- LSHTM ethics committee in the UK
- National Ethical Review Board in Sweden
- Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Witwatersrand in South Africa
- Medical Research Council in Zimbabwe
- Research Council of Zimbabwe

8.6 Other approvals

In South Africa, in addition to ethical approval, approval will be requested through National Health Research Database (NHRD) from provincial and local health departments. In addition, approvals will be requested from hospital and facility managers. Requests will include permission from management to install temperature and similar measurement devices in selected rooms in the healthcare facilities.

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

9. Timeline

For the measurement of how heat influences work, quality of care, and wellbeing, the same fieldwork will take place over a 2–3-month period during the hottest season and during a cooler 2–3-month period for comparison. In addition, we will use qualitative and quantitative methods to observe health workers across all work shifts (morning, afternoon, and night).

Project month (2022-2024)		1 Sep	2 Oct	3 Nov	4 Dec	5 Jan	6 Feb	7 Mar	8 Apr	9 May	10 Jun	11 Jul	12 Aug	13 Sep	14 Oct	15 Nov	16 Dec	17 Jan	18 Feb	19 Mar
Task 2.2.2																				
Brainstorming/ planning																				
Ethics submission countries and permission s from province and facilities	LSH TM																			
	SA																			
	Zim																			
	Swe																			
Refine tools & fieldwork prep																				
Fieldwork (rounds I and II for hotter and cooler temps)																				
Assessmen t of thermal exposure	SA																			
	Zim																			
	Swe den																			
Fieldwork cold (2-3 months)	SA																			
	Zim																			
	Swe den																			
Interim analysis	SA																			
	Zim																			
	Swe den																			
	SA																			

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Staffing required

In addition to a mixed method researcher to coordinate the study in each site and participate in the analysis, the following staff are required for fieldwork:

Study component	Staff cadre	Number	Duration	Comment
Observations and in-depth interviews	Social science researcher with experience in participant observation, ideally with clinical/maternal health background	1	2-4 weeks per facility for data collection	Preferable same social scientists will be required for a longer duration for data analysis
Time motion	Experienced social sciences researcher or staff with clinical background (e.g., nurse)	1	1 month per facility per season (cool vs hot periods)	None
Survey	Field worker, research assistant or equivalent, supported by a data manager	1	Less than 1 month for data collection per season	None
Data extraction	Research staff with clinical background	1	6 months	None
Temperature measurement	Field worker, research assistant or equivalent	1	1 month per season	None

Appendices

Appendix 1: Participant observation in facilities

Introductory note for the researcher

You will carry out participant observation in health facilities over a period of two to four weeks (depending on size and number of clinics per country), during which you will also carry out interviews and follow-up conversations.

In an introductory group meeting, staff members in the designated areas of the facility (see below) will be informed of your presence as a researcher, the aims of the study, and the purpose of your observation. Consent to participate in the observations will then be sought from all staff members attending this meeting. A poster will be developed for distribution in relevant parts of the facility, that explains the research and its principles of anonymity and confidentiality.

In the first week, you will primarily undertake observations in the facility, being sure to capture different times of the day, services of the hospital, and staff involved in care. Informal conversations are a part of this fieldwork, and you are encouraged to strike up such conversations and engage with those who approach you, while also understanding that these informal conversations should not be conducted as interviews. During this first week, identify potential informants for interviews and try to schedule times for these interviews for the following week, insofar as it is possible. You may choose to have an introductory interview in the first week with a member of staff to clarify certain practices and routines at the facility.

You should aim for a minimum of 4 hours of observation per day (6 hours/day the first week without interviews) and keep a detailed written and/or oral field journal during this time, for further elaboration and consolidation after observation hours, ideally immediately after the session has ended. If you delay completion of each day's journal, you will fall behind and it will become difficult to remember specific details.

In the second, third, and fourth weeks, participant observation continues, and interviews are conducted. Interviews build on and respond to the researcher-observed practices. Interviews will take place at the facility and in the community, in private settings that are comfortable for the participant.

This is a guide with suggestions of what to pay attention to and document during observations, with an eye to keeping the study research questions and objectives at the forefront of your mind. Not every topic needs to be written about extensively, but the listed topics are suggestions of areas that may be significant in terms of influences of and responses to heat and climate change that we may want to pay attention to, especially when comparing between hotter and cooler seasons. The guide should encourage you to remain flexible and curious about the surroundings at the facility and how people go about their work.

The following broad questions should guide the participant observation:

- Underlying sense of what the climate profile is in the location (seasonal and typical daily variations). What are people used to and what is changing?

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

- Which type of work and practices seem to be most affected by heat in this location, and in which ways?
- How are health workers affected by heat at work (well-being, productivity, quality of care)? How does heat exposure change their capacity to carry out work?
- What are HCWs and other individuals doing, or could they do, to avoid or reduce heat exposures and heat effects at work? (Includes descriptions of current preventive interventions and ideas for new interventions)

Spaces to observe:

- Maternity ward
- Labour ward
- Antenatal care clinics
- Postnatal care clinics
- Recreational, waiting and rest areas
- Follow leads to other spaces at or near the facility

Areas of observation

Part I: Infrastructure

1. Map the facility

Map the physical layout of the relevant departments in the facility, and what is done where. Document the clinical areas, staff rooms, waiting spaces and rest areas.

2. Heat and cooling (staff)

What kind of cooling mechanisms are available at the hospital (fans, air conditioning, shaded passages, cross breeze, water, etc.)? Are they working?

Do staff use these resources? Which staff? How and when?

Are there power outages? How frequent? How are they dealt with?

3. Heat and cooling (patients/visitors)

What infrastructure is available for patients/visitors, and how do they use them?

4. Existence of drinking water and refreshments (staff)

Where do facility staff hydrate, with what, and how frequently?

Is there a cost?

Are containers reusable? Recyclable?

5. Document any waste produced in relation to heat or climate change management

Part II: Clinical practices and patient care during labour and delivery

Movements during labour and delivery

In terms of care during antenatal, labour, and postnatal, pay attention to:

- Number of staff tending to patients, profiles
- Late arrivals and absences: how many and for which reasons given?
- Activity levels of staff members: energetic, active, lethargic, controlled...
- Respectful care during labour and delivery: attention, attentiveness and patience towards woman (and her companions)
- Partograph: standard practice, use of
- Hygiene practices: hand washing, disinfection – frequency, thoroughness
- Record keeping: thoroughness; are records filled out during patient visits or afterwards? Use of partograph
- Mood: collegiality, tension, stress, mutual support
- Practices related to heat avoidance/adaptation for both staff and patient
- Link with clinical aspects observed in time-motion and record extraction studies
- Attention to emergency management of labour
- Breaks: how frequently do staff members take breaks, and where? Do they take them together or alone? What do they do during breaks?
- C-sections – medical indication, does decision-making have any relation to heat factors?

Part III: Staff activities during routine care, antenatal and postpartum care

Section A: Situational set-up

1. What time do staff arrive at work, with which modes of transport? What are the heat indexes associated with the transport modes? (Are they cool, air conditioned, exposing people to the elements)?
2. Is there sufficient staff and do the planned staff arrive each day? Attention to staffing in maternity wards, operating theatre and neonatal units. Are there late arrivals and absences – how many and for which reasons given?
3. Note breaks taken by staff and what they do during them

Section B: Interpersonal relations (staff)

1. Work relations and social relations, team dynamics (cordiality, conflicts, hierarchies, mutual assistance, mutual respect, exchanges between staff about patients, exchanges with patients, type and quality of exchanges, tension, irritation)
2. Workload: possible stress, negative treatment, demotivation – and positive circumstances

Section C: Relations between staff, patients and companions in the hospital

1. Reception of patients (how are they received? Are they informed and oriented/directed? By whom?)
2. Nature of interactions/relationships [do patients and staff talk to each other? language used, use of an interpreter, topics of discussion, influence of the social level of patients in the process of their care (poor/rich, urban/rural, ethnicity, etc.)]

3. Empathy, respect and explanations given to the patient and her family – note time given and patience expressed on the part of all
4. Freedom given to the woman in relation to her preferences for giving birth (positions, right to walk, support and role of companions)
5. Relations with accompanying persons (staff attitudes towards accompanying persons, information given and requests)
6. Care and advice for the mother and the newborn (see what types of care and advice are given to the woman after childbirth, for the maintenance of the baby and for herself)
7. Care and follow-up of the patient and newborn during and after childbirth (is the patient followed up/accompanied?)

Part IV: Informal conversations with staff and administration:

- Draw on the guiding questions at beginning of this guide and the interview guide

Appendix 2: Topic guide for in-depth interviews with health care workers

Explain that this study investigates the **impact of hot temperatures on maternal and neonatal health care workers** (in terms of their personal well-being, their productivity, the working environment, and health/medical outcomes) and that we are interested in learning about what they think about this topic, and **whether and how it is significant in their professional lives and care giving**.

1. Profile of participant

- Age, gender, profession, training
- Role/position at facility
- Length of time working in total and at facility
- (BRIEFLY) Previous positions held (to get a sense of diversity of experience)

2. Introductory questions

2.1. What to you is the ideal temperature range to work in and live your day-to-day life? How so?

Probe as to whether these ideal temperature ranges vary for recreational activities and for work, and if so, why.

2.2. If you think about all the challenges that you currently face in commuting to and from work and in performing your duties at work, where would you rank heat/high temperatures in this list? Tell me why?

OR

2.2. Do you think hot weather impacts on your day-to-day life? How so?

Probe about:

- At home
- Commuting to work (e.g., how does it affect choice, costs, time of commute?)
- At work
- Other

(These are prompts to get a sense of participants' perceptions before asking specifically about these areas – i.e., to know if temperature is important to them and whether issues related to elevated heat are on their radar without direct lines of questioning. Then say that we will move to specific experiences next.)

3. Impacts of heat in the workplace

3.1. Which months are most problematic for heat in this region? Please explain. In which ways?

3.2. Are there times of the day that are more problematic for you and the health facility in terms of heat? When? In which ways are they problematic?

Probe:

- Work gets interrupted?

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- *Changes that happen in the ward?*

3.3. Can we now return to the question of how hot temperatures affect how you work: please tell me more.

Probe about effects on:

- *Productivity (ability to meet targets in an appropriate timeframe)*
- *Effort and energy-levels (ability to put the required effort and energy into work tasks)*
- *Attention (ability to pay attention to patients and colleagues and to absorb information)*

3.4. How do you think heat affects the quality of care you are able to provide to your patients? Can you give some examples of how this has happened in the past?

Probe:

- *In which ways?*
- *Care given during labour and delivery specifically?*
- *Postpartum/newborn care?*

3.5. How does hot weather affect your colleagues?

Probe:

- *Effects on their work practices? (e.g., taking frequent breaks, finishing a shift early, working slower than usual)*

3.6. How does heat affect your patients?

Probe:

- *During pregnancy*
- *Labour*
- *Post-partum*

3.7. Have you ever taken time off from work in the past because of heat? If so, why and when? If so, how many days have you taken at a time/week?

4. Impact of heat on overall wellbeing and health

4.1. Do you think hot temperatures affect your wellbeing and mental health? In which ways? Can you give specific examples?

Probe:

- *Stress levels affected?*
- *More irritable with patients?*
- *Anxiety?*
- *Other*

4.2. Do you think hotter temperatures effect your physical health? If so, in which ways?

4.3. Do you find yourself interacting differently with your colleagues or with patients when it is hot? How so? Can you give some examples?

Probe:

- *More/less patience?*
- *More/less irritation,*
- *Change in frequency or content of communication, etc.*

5. Adaptation

5.1. What do you do to find relief from the heat? Describe for me a typical day in the hot season/in a heatwave, and what actions you would take to escape the heat or reduce its effects.

Probe:

- *Drink cold water*
- *Use a fan*
- *Switch A/C on*
- *Move to a cooler part of the building, etc.*

5.2. How effective are these methods?

5.3. What are the pros and cons of the different methods you use?

5.4. Do you find yourself changing the amount of fluid you take in during hot weather? Which liquids do you like to drink when it is hot and why? Tell me about how easy/difficult it is to access them?

5.5. In your workplace, do you have access to drinking water, and how much do you have to pay for it (if at all)?

5.6. In your experience, are there any extra financial costs related to coping with hot weather?

Probe:

- *Clothing*
- *Drinking water*
- *Transport*
- *Cooling/climate control/electricity,*
- *Lost wages*

5.7. Do you know whether your employer has safety standards or a formal policy on working in hot conditions? If so, what does that policy say? Is it used in your facility? Is it helpful? How so/Why not?

6. Recommended interventions

In the last part of our interview, we would like to know what you think could be done at the facility you work at, to improve your quality of life and the quality of care you provide when it is hot.

6.1. Let's begin with the things that are within **your** control as a health care worker working in maternal health during hot temperatures. What can be improved in:

- Adjusting ventilation (e.g., open doors and windows, use fan)
- Adjusting climate control (A/C)
- Increasing fluid intake
- Improving patient awareness of the dangers of heat
- Other?

6.2. In terms of the **health system**, what recommendations can you make regarding improvements in:

- Provision of reliable AC and/or ventilation
- Building design and materials (e.g., painting roofs white, improving insulation)
- Provision of cold water for staff
- Lighter protective clothing/uniforms
- Enforcement of regular breaks
- Structuring of shifts (e.g., split shifts, earlier starts, shorter shifts)
- Staffing (e.g., increase staffing over summer)
- Other?

6.3. Could you rank the interventions for implementation by the health system, from most important to you to least important?

6.4. What do you think the barriers might be to implementing these interventions?

6.5. Finally, could you reflect on how the weather/climate in your area has changed at all over the last decade? (e.g., hotter summers, spring heatwaves, more frequent/prolonged droughts, flooding, etc.) What do you think is causing these changes?

6.6. In your view, is the health sector acting to meet the challenges of a changing climate? How significant do you think this will be for the health system in coming years?

7. Optional questions: relationships to climate change (solastalgia)

Now I would like to ask you some questions about your experiences with climate change as a whole.

7.1. What do you see is the impact of climate change on your life and environment? (If answered that they noticed climate change in question 6.5) What do these changes mean to you?

(Prompts: farming, food availability, comfort, transport/travel, habits, availability of other goods, etc)

7.2. How do you think these changes will impact those in your community/surroundings? Or those further away from home?

7.3. What emotions do you relate to your feelings about the future and the climate situation?

(Note: This is a key question to probe around.)

7.4. Do you notice a change in your health or the health of those around you, that you relate to climate change? If so, what? Who is affected and how?

7.5. Have you noticed the health sector changing in relation to climate change? If so, in which ways? Please give examples.

(Note: This question ties in with question 6.6 and can be followed up with a question asking for the

opinion of what the health sector could do in response, if this hasn't already been covered previously in the interview.)

Closing

Do you have any other comments considering temperature, work, productivity and well-being?

Thank you for your time and contribution to this work.

Appendix 3: Key informant interview guide

Profile

Job/role/position in community

Length of time in role and responsibilities held

1. Local experiences with heat (general)

Do you believe that hot temperatures and extreme heat events pose a concern to your community?

- [If yes] If so, how? In which ways? For whom? Can you please give some examples?
- Could you reflect on how the weather in your area has changed at all over the last decade, or longer? (e.g., hotter summers, spring heatwaves, more frequent/prolonged droughts, flooding, etc.) What do you think is causing these changes?

2. Health sector experiences with heat

As you know, we are carrying out some research focused on [X] health facility and the impact of heat on health worker well-being, outputs and quality of care.

- Have you heard about heat posing a problem for health workers?
- Have you heard about heat posing a problem for mothers and babies at the health facility?
 - If so, what? Please share examples.
- What do you think could be done at the facility to improve the situation in terms of high heat and your quality of life and care giving?

3. Adaptations for heat

3.1. Are you aware of actions that can be or have been undertaken to cope with extreme heat in the health facility for health workers and patients?

- If so, what are they? Who carries them out – where, since when?
- How effective do you think they are?

Interviewer: Probe after pros and cons of each measure mentioned. Probe after measures that they know of in their geographic area and elsewhere.

3.2. In terms of the health system, what do you think about the acceptability and feasibility of making the following improvements:

(Interviewer: probe in terms of feasibility and acceptability according to the informant's opinion for each one, and ask for examples, if possible)

- Provision of reliable AC and/or ventilation
- Building design and materials (e.g., painting roofs white, improving insulation)

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- o Provision of cold water for staff
- o Lighter protective clothing/uniforms
- o Enforcement of regular breaks
- o Structuring of shifts (e.g., split shifts, earlier starts, shorter shifts)
- o Staffing (e.g., increase staffing over summer)
- o Can you think of any others, now that we have proposed some examples?

3.3. Could you rank the interventions for implementation by the health system, from most important to you to least important?

3.4. What do you think the barriers might be to implementing these interventions?

3.5. In your experience, which steps would need to be undertaken to successfully institute the changes you recommended earlier? Which stakeholders should be involved, and how?

3.6. In your view, is the health sector acting to meet the challenges of a changing climate?

- o How significant do you think this will be for the health system in coming years?
- o Do you believe that this issue is adequately on the radar of decision and policy makers in [x country]? Why or why not?

4. Closing

Do you have any other comments you would like to share with us considering temperature, work, productivity and well-being?

Thank you for your time.

Appendix 4: Health worker survey questionnaire

Question number	Question	Response categories	Skip
Introduction:			
<i>Thank you for accepting to take part in the HIGH Horizons healthcare worker study. The questionnaire will take approximately 45 minutes to complete and can be done in more than one sitting preferably on the same day, towards the end of your shift. Your responses are important.</i>			
1.1	Name of country	RSA/ZIM/SWE	
1.2	Name of facility	Stanza Bopape CHC Mamelodi Hospital	
1.3	Participant ID label		
1.4	Date of starting questionnaire: Time of starting questionnaire:	[] [] / [] [] / [] [] (day/month/year) Started at: [] [] Hours [] [] minutes	
Demographic and work variables			
2.1	How old are you?	[] [] years old	
2.2	What is your sex?	[] Female [] Male [] Prefer to self-describe , please add [] Prefer not to say	
2.3	What is your highest level of education?	[] No schooling [] Primary school [] Some secondary (high school) [] Secondary school (high school) [] National diploma, [] Advanced diploma [] Undergraduate degree [] Post-graduate degree [] Prefer not to say	
2.4	What is your staff position in this hospital?	[] Nurse of any grade [] Midwife [] Obstetrician/Gynaecologist [] Paediatrician or Neonatologist [] Anesthesiologist [] Other types of doctor (e.g., intern, medical officer)	

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		<input type="checkbox"/> Clinical associate <input type="checkbox"/> Allied health workers such as physiotherapists <input type="checkbox"/> Community health worker <input type="checkbox"/> Cleaner <input type="checkbox"/> Porter <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify	
2.5	How long have you worked as a healthcare worker?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> years <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> months	
2.6	How long have you worked in this facility?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> years <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> months	
2.7	How long have you worked in your most recent role (e.g., a health facility manager; senior midwife etc)?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> years <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> months	
2.8	Do you work part-time or full-time?	<input type="checkbox"/> Part-time <input type="checkbox"/> Full-time <input type="checkbox"/> Locum/Self-employed/per shift basis	
2.9	If you have a contract, how many hours per week are you contracted to work at this facility?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> hours	
2.10	In which service/department did you spend most of your time over the past 7 days? [multi-select allowed]	<input type="checkbox"/> Antenatal clinic <input type="checkbox"/> Antenatal ward <input type="checkbox"/> Labour and delivery room <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical theatre <input type="checkbox"/> Postnatal ward <input type="checkbox"/> Neonatal ward <input type="checkbox"/> Other outpatient <input type="checkbox"/> Other wards <input type="checkbox"/> Outreach <input type="checkbox"/> Other/ not in facility	
2.11	How long is your current/ was your last shift?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> hours	
2.12	How many- breaks during your shift have you taken today, of 5 minutes or more?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> breaks	
2.13	During the last two weeks, how many of your working days were you absent (for any reason, including sick leave) from the facility?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> days of annual leave <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> days of sick leave <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> days of other leave	
2.14	Overall, from a scale of 1-10 with 10 being the highest level, how motivated overall do you feel to work in this facility?	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Health status in general			

<i>We would like to know about your health status.</i>			
3.1	Would you say that today your health in general is: Excellent, very good, good, fair or poor?	<input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Very good <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know	
3.2	Do you currently have any of the following illnesses (as diagnosed by a healthcare professional)? [multi select]	<input type="checkbox"/> Hypertension <input type="checkbox"/> Diabetes <input type="checkbox"/> Dyslipidaemia (high cholesterol or triglycerides) <input type="checkbox"/> Asthma/COPD <input type="checkbox"/> TB <input type="checkbox"/> Autoimmune disease, e.g., Lupus, rheumatoid arthritis <input type="checkbox"/> Osteoarthritis <input type="checkbox"/> Heart disease <input type="checkbox"/> Stroke <input type="checkbox"/> Epilepsy <input type="checkbox"/> Depression/anxiety <input type="checkbox"/> Other mental illness <input type="checkbox"/> HIV <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above	
3.3	Are you pregnant or were pregnant in the past 12 months [for women only to answer]?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, currently pregnant <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, was pregnant in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know	
Your wellbeing: WHO Well-being Index for Health Workers tool			
<i>For each of the five statements, please indicate whether in the last two weeks you have been feeling this way most of the time, more than half of the time, less than half of the time, only rarely, or never.</i>			
4.1	In the past two weeks, I have felt cheerful and in good spirits ...	<input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the time <input type="checkbox"/> Less than half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
4.2	In the past two weeks, I have felt calm and relaxed	<input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the time	

		<input type="checkbox"/> Less than half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
4.3	In the past two weeks, I have felt active and vigorous...	<input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the time <input type="checkbox"/> Less than half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
4.4	In the past two weeks, I woke up feeling fresh and rested....	<input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the time <input type="checkbox"/> Less than half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
4.5	In the past two weeks, my daily life has been filled with things that interest me...	<input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the time <input type="checkbox"/> Less than half of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Never	

Your stress level: PSS-4 (Perceived Stress Scale 4)

The questions in this scale ask about your feelings and thoughts during the last month. In each case, you will be asked to indicate how often you felt or thought a certain way. Although some of the questions are similar, there are differences between them and you should treat each one as a separate question.

5.1	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/> Very often	
5.2	In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle- your personal problems?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/> Very often	
5.3	In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/> Very often	
5.4	In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes	

		<input type="checkbox"/> Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/> Very often	
Your anxiety level: GAD-7 (Generalised Anxiety Disorder)			
<i>How often have you been bothered by the following over the past 2 weeks?</i>			
6.1	Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.2	Not being able to stop or control worrying	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.3	Worrying too much about different things	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.4	Trouble relaxing	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.5	Being so restless that it's hard to sit still	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.6	Being easily annoyed or irritable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
6.7	Being afraid as if something awful might happen	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half of the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day	
Adapted heat strain score index			
7.1	During your work, the level of physical activity you engage in can be described as:	Very light similar to resting (0) Light (1) Moderate (2) Hard (3) Very hard (4)	
7.2	The air movement in my workplace can best be described as:	No air movement (0) Light air movement (1)	

		Moderate air movement (2) Strong air movement (3) Very strong air movement (4)	
7.3	The sunlight in your workstation can be described as:	<input type="checkbox"/> Full shadow (-1) <input type="checkbox"/> Sun and shadow or mild light (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Full sun or intense light (1)	
7.4	The ventilation in my workplace can best be described as:	<input type="checkbox"/> Active and high ventilation (-1) <input type="checkbox"/> Appropriate ventilation no additional ventilation is required (0) <input type="checkbox"/> Inadequate ventilation (1) <input type="checkbox"/> No ventilation (2)	
7.5	How much of your time is spent in a hot environment, in a shift?	<input type="checkbox"/> Less than 2 hours (-1) <input type="checkbox"/> 2-4 hours (0) <input type="checkbox"/> 4-6 hours (1) <input type="checkbox"/> More than 6 hours (2)	
7.6	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, how did the temperature in your workplace feel?	Cool (0) Temperate (1) Warm (2) Hot (3) Very hot (4)	
7.7	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, how did the air humidity feel in your workplace?	Dry (0) Slightly humid (1) Moderately humid (2) Very humid (3) Extremely humid (4)	
7.8	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, how much sweating did you experience on the hottest day of the past week on a scale of 0-4? <i>Zero represents no sweat, and 4 severe sweat.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	
7.9	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, the level of fatigue that I experience at work can be described as:	<input type="checkbox"/> I'm not tired at all (0) <input type="checkbox"/> I'm a little tired (1) <input type="checkbox"/> I'm tired (2) <input type="checkbox"/> I'm exhausted (3) <input type="checkbox"/> I'm so exhausted I desire to have a break (4)	
7.10	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, how thirsty were you when you are at work?	<input type="checkbox"/> I don't get thirsty (0) <input type="checkbox"/> I get a little thirsty (1) <input type="checkbox"/> I get thirsty (2) <input type="checkbox"/> I get very thirsty (3)	

		[] I get so thirsty that my mouth and throat get dry and they can't be wet with saliva (4)	
7.11	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, how comfortable were you at work?	[] Comfortable (0) [] Slightly uncomfortable (1) [] Uncomfortable (2) [] Very uncomfortable (3) [] So uncomfortable I want to quit my job (4)	
7.12	Thinking about the hottest day in the past week, did you feel that you were suffering from symptoms of heat stress (thirst, sweating, thermal discomfort, headaches, feeling tired, other symptoms?)	[] Yes [] No [] Unsure	
7.13 7	Have you ever experienced heat stroke in your workplace? <i>Symptoms of heat stroke include: confusion, altered mental status, slurred speech; loss of consciousness; hot, dry skin or profuse sweating; seizures; very high body temperature</i>	[] Yes (3) [] No (0) [] Unsure	
Perceptions of heat's influence on quality of care			
8.1	During the hot season, does heat exposure reduce your daily or hourly work input?	[] Yes [] No [] Don't know	
8.2	<i>When you think about the last heatwave that occurred in your area, have you observed any of the following during the heatwaves?</i>		
8.2.1	Reduction of productivity per health care worker?	[] Never [] Rarely [] Often [] Every time [] Unsure	
8.2.2	Increase in the number of medical errors by healthcare workers?	[] Never [] Rarely [] Often [] Every time [] Unsure	
8.2.3	Poorer communication with patients?	[] Never [] Rarely [] Often [] Every time [] Unsure	

8.2.4	Poorer communication between health care workers?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.5	Patients in less clean environment?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.6	Drugs (e.g., oxytocin) becoming less effective?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.7	Equipment faultier?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.8	Increased electricity cuts?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.9	Increased clinical workload?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.10	Providers less likely to follow guidelines?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.11	Supply chain interruption?	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
8.2.12	Heightened irritability	<input type="checkbox"/> Never <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Every time <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	
Current heat adaptations			
9.1	Does your workplace have a formal policy about working in hot conditions?	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/> unsure	

9.2	If yes, do you use the formal policy about working in hot conditions?	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/> unsure <input type="checkbox"/> n/a	
9.3	If no/unsure, do you think that such a policy may be useful?	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/> unsure	
9.4	<i>Could you please rate the availability of the following heat adaptation measures in your clinic/ward?</i>		
9.4.1	Availability of shading devices to reduce direct sunlight? i.e. blinds, curtains, overhangs,, verandah etc	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
9.4.2	The availability of water for staff or patients in the wards?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
9.4.3	The availability of cold refrigerated water for staff or patients in the wards?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
9.4.4	The availability of functioning air conditioning?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
9.4.5	The availability of fans?	<input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Rarely <input type="checkbox"/> Never	
9.4.6	The number of trees in the immediate proximity (<5 meters) outside the ward/clinic?	<input type="checkbox"/> Many trees all the way around <input type="checkbox"/> Some trees in certain areas <input type="checkbox"/> Few trees <input type="checkbox"/> No trees	
9.4.7	The availability of spaces (indoors or outdoors) to cool down for yourself or your patients when it is too hot?	<input type="checkbox"/> Many spaces that are always available <input type="checkbox"/> Many spaces that are often available <input type="checkbox"/> Few spaces that often available <input type="checkbox"/> Few spaces that are rarely available <input type="checkbox"/> No spaces available	

9.4.8	Which of the following ways could be used to lower temperature in your ward/clinic during hot weather:	<input type="checkbox"/> Opening windows more often to increase ventilation during hot weather <input type="checkbox"/> More regular breaks <input type="checkbox"/> Lighter protective clothing <input type="checkbox"/> Air-conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Cold water available for staff <input type="checkbox"/> More shading in the ward <input type="checkbox"/> Another option (please explain in a few words)	
10.1	Date of ending questionnaire:	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> / <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> / <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> (day/month/year)	
10.2	Time of ending questionnaire:	Started at: <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> Hours <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> minutes	

Appendix 5: Building checklist

It may be difficult to retrieve all the information contained in the checklist. Try to be as precise as possible, but feel free to skip questions where information is not available.

00. GENERAL INFORMATION

Building: _____

Address: _____

Date _____

Time _____

Inspector(s): _____

01. BUILDING REGISTRATION

General building characteristics

1. Year of construction _____
2. Year of last major renovation _____
3. Gross floor area _____ m²
4. Net floor area _____ m²
5. Number of floors below grade _____
6. Numbers of floors above grade
(including ground floor) _____

Space usage

7. Activity category of each floor (office, foyer/reception, retail, vacant, residential, assembly, multi-use, laboratory, storage, food services, mechanical, parking, other)

<u>Floor Designation</u>	<u>Primary Activity</u>	<u>Secondary Activity</u>	<u>Comments</u>
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____

Site information

8. Site Characterization (check most representative)

- | | | | |
|-------------------|--------------------------|----------------------|--------------------------|
| Urban/Industrial | <input type="checkbox"/> | Suburban/Industrial | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Urban/Residential | <input type="checkbox"/> | Suburban/Residential | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Urban/Commercial | <input type="checkbox"/> | Suburban/Commercial | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Rural/Near Urban | <input type="checkbox"/> | Rural/Commercial | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Rural/Agricultural

Rural/Industrial

Building facility information

9. Type of ventilation in the building (check all that apply)

- Natural ventilation, manual window opening
- Natural ventilation, automatic window openers
- Exhaust air system
- Exhaust and supply air system
- Exhaust and supply air system with heat recovery
- Other (specify) _____
—

In case of mechanical ventilation system:

- Filter replacement schedule _____
- Temperature controlled
- CO₂ controlled
- Manually controlled
- Ventilation time/schedule _____
- Not possible to determine

10. What primary heating system is present in the building?

- Air system (heating coil – electrical)
- Air system (heating coil – water)
- Radiators
- Floor radiant heating
- Other, please specify _____
—

11. What primary cooling system is present in the building?

- No cooling
- Individual room air conditioners
(fan coil units)
- Central system with cooling
- Other, please specify _____
—

Building envelope characterisation

12. Façade

- Brick
- Concrete
- Wood
- Asbestos cement
- Other (specify) _____
—

13. Exterior wall construction (inside)

- Concrete
- Brick
- Wood
- Other (specify) _____

14. Interior walls construction

- Concrete
- Brick
- Gypsum boards
- Wooden boards
- Other (specify) _____
—

15. Which type of insulation is there in the building, if any?

- Exterior
- Interior
- In cavity wall
- Other (specify) _____

THE END

Room checklist

It may be difficult to retrieve all the information contained in the checklist. Try to be as precise as possible, but feel free to skip questions where information is not available.

00. GENERAL INFORMATION

Building _____

Address: _____

Date _____

Time _____

Inspector(s) _____

01. ROOM IDENTIFICATION

Room identification

Floor: _____

Room number/name: _____

Other relevant information (Please be elaborate): _____

Measurement equipment identification

Measurement device installed in room:

Other relevant information:

Other measurement equipment installed in office (e.g. Hobo loggers or other):

What:

Number or other ID:

Other relevant information:

Other 1:

Other 2:

Floor plan with indication of placement of measurement equipment:

(Remember to draw a compass with the orientation and placement of measurement equipment)

02. ROOM DESCRIPTION

General characteristics

1. Main orientation (of windows) North, South, East, West, Northeast, Northwest, Southeast, Southwest

2. Estimated net floor area _____ m²

3. Estimated ceiling height _____ m

4. Suspended ceiling Yes, plenum height: _____ cm No _____

5. Room usage

Windows

6. Number of windows to the exterior: _____
7. Number of operable windows: _____
8. Total area of external windows: _____ m²
9. Percentage of operable windows: _____ %
10. Window shading (overhangs, window treatments, shades) Yes: _____ No
11. Percentage of windows with shading elements _____ %

Lighting

12. Which type of lighting is used?

- LED
- Incandescent
- Fluorescent
- Other (specify) _____
-

Ventilation

13. Total number of supply air devices _____

14. Supply air device type

		Comments
Linear ceiling diffusers	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Sidewall diffusers	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
High sidewall grilles	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Floor registers	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Perforated ceiling panels	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Square or round ceiling diffusers	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Floor or near-floor diffusers	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Low sidewall grilles	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Fan coil units or unit ventilators	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Slots around ceiling luminaires	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____

No supply air devices

15. Total number of return air devices _____

16. Return air device type

		Comments
Ceiling grilles	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Ceiling slots	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Low sidewall or floor grilles	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Slots around ceiling luminaires	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
High sidewall grilles	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>	_____
No	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Additional space conditioning equipment

- 17. Number of space heaters observed in test space _____
- Number of space heaters in use _____
- Number of humidifiers observed in test space _____
- Number of humidifiers in use _____
- Number of dehumidifiers observed in test space _____
- Number of dehumidifiers in use _____
- Number of desk fans observed in test space _____
- Number of desk fans in use _____
- Other (specify) _____

- No

THE END

Appendix 7: Clothing questionnaire

This questionnaire is designed to collect information about the clothing worn by healthcare workers in order to estimate their insulation value.

1.1	Name of country	<input type="checkbox"/> Zimbabwe <input type="checkbox"/> South Africa <input type="checkbox"/> Sweden
1.2	Name of facility (when South Africa is selected)	<input type="checkbox"/> Stanza Bopape CHC <input type="checkbox"/> Mamelodi Hospital
2.	Work wear	<input type="checkbox"/> Scrub top and trousers (theatre blue scrubs) <input type="checkbox"/> Lab coat <input type="checkbox"/> Gloves <input type="checkbox"/> Face mask <input type="checkbox"/> Goggles or face shield <input type="checkbox"/> Hats or bouffant cap <input type="checkbox"/> Isolation gown <input type="checkbox"/> Apron <input type="checkbox"/> Compression stockings <input type="checkbox"/> N95 mask or powered air-purified respirator
3.	Undergarments	<input type="checkbox"/> Men's brief <input type="checkbox"/> Panties <input type="checkbox"/> Bra <input type="checkbox"/> Shirt (no sleeve) <input type="checkbox"/> T-Shirt (short sleeves) <input type="checkbox"/> T-Shirt (long sleeves)
5.	Socks and stockings	<input type="checkbox"/> Thin calf-length socks <input type="checkbox"/> Thick calf-length socks <input type="checkbox"/> Thin ankle socks <input type="checkbox"/> Pantyhose
6.	Footwear	<input type="checkbox"/> Sandals <input type="checkbox"/> Shoes, thin soles <input type="checkbox"/> Shoes, thick soles <input type="checkbox"/> Boots, calf-length <input type="checkbox"/> Boots, knee-length <input type="checkbox"/> Trainers

INFORMATION SHEET FOR HEALTH CARE WORKERS – Participant Observation Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name and surname is _____ (insert name). I am a _____ (insert designation) at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. We are conducting a research study to investigate the effect of indoor heat on the physical health and mental wellbeing of health care workers (HCWs). We invite you to participate in our study.

What you should know about this research study:

- Before agreeing to participate, we are giving you this participant information sheet and consent form so that you may read about the purpose, risks, and benefits of this research study.
- You have the right to refuse to take part, and you have the right to agree to take part now and change your mind later.
- Whatever you decide, it will not affect your regular work.
- Please review this consent form carefully. Ask any questions before you make a decision.
- Your participation is voluntary.
- Thank you for reading this information. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a consent form.
- If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask me.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being invited to take part in a study that examines how heat affects HCWs' physical and mental wellbeing, their productivity, and the quality of care provided. This study focuses only on HCWs working in maternity and newborn care. The results from this study will be used to design an intervention to improve conditions in health facilities when it is very hot. This, in turn, will improve working conditions and health outcomes for HCWs. The study is being conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden.

Why am I being asked to participate in this research study?

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a HCW:

- Aged 18 years and above
- Working full-time at Stanza Bopape Community Healthcare Centre (CHC) or Mamelodi Hospital
- Working in antenatal, maternal, labour or neonatal wards/clinics
- Able and willing to consent to provide data for the study

PROCEDURES AND DURATION

We are seeking your consent today for the **Participant Observation** component of the study. This component involves observation of a set of activities or group of people as they go about their work and other daily activities. Researchers in our study team wish to observe you and other HCWs in your work environment, focusing on how you are affected by the heat. Their observations will also take note of what you and other HCWs are currently doing to stay cool and how much the facility building allows staff and patients to escape the heat.

These researchers will be present in the antenatal, maternal, labour, and neonatal wards/clinics at different times of the day and on different days of the week. They will move around these spaces and do their best to not get in your way or interfere with the duties you carry out as a HCW. Occasionally, the researchers will take written notes about what they are observing.

Your privacy and confidentiality will be protected throughout, and no personal identifying information will be collected on any patients who are observed in this activity. Your name will not be used when we publish our findings in reports or academic articles, nor will it be shared with your colleagues or supervisors. We may share the anonymous information collected during the observations with stakeholders in government and with our research partners in Sweden, Zimbabwe and the UK. No photographs or videos will be taken of any individuals who are observed.

We want to reassure you that our observations are **not** about monitoring staff performance or identifying errors in the care you provide. If our researchers observe gross lapses in professional behaviour, however, they may discuss this with you personally afterward. .

If you do not wish to be observed, you have the right to ‘opt out’ of these observations. Opting out means that while the observer will continue to be present in the facility, they will not observe you specifically or write down any notes about your activity. No one except the researchers will know that you have opted out of observations.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The most important risk is breach of confidentiality, but this risk is low as we will use security measures to protect your personal data. An additional risk of participating in this study is that you may be anxious that you are being evaluated, which may make you feel uncomfortable. Our researchers have been trained in creating a supportive environment, without interfering with your regular work. Informal conversations will only be held when these do not interfere with your work schedule. It is important to know that you can stop your participation in this study at any time, without any consequences.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There are no direct benefits or reimbursement from participating in these observations. The results will be used to inform the development of an intervention to improve working conditions at health facilities in the hot season. We hope that this intervention will be beneficial for other HCWs like you. You will not need to pay anything to take part in the study.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your data will be collected, processed, and stored according to the South African Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) of 2013. To protect your confidentiality, no personal identifiers will appear in any presentations, reports and publications that make use of this observation data. All electronic data will be protected by security access codes. We will use a unique participant identification (ID) number instead of your name when storing and analysing your data. Any written information will be kept under lock and key in a cabinet and kept separately from any information that identifies you (such as this consent form). After study completion, files/information will be kept securely at the project office for a period of 6 years after all analysis and publications are complete and will then be destroyed. Your anonymous data may be stored electronically for longer than 6 years for use in other studies if you agree.

Who may see, use or share the information collected during this study about you?

The researchers involved in this study have access to this information. Organizations that may look at and/or copy your research records for ethical, research, quality assurance, and data analysis include:

- Wits Human Research Ethics Committee
- London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Ethics Committee

Additionally, we may share your anonymous information with researchers for use in other research studies if you agree to this. The information will be labelled with a unique code, and we will not share your name.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

It is your decision whether to take part in this study or not. Taking part in this study is completely voluntary. You may stop your participation in the study at any time without penalty. No matter what decision you make, there will be no negative consequences for you in any way.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been submitted to the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee, and this committee has granted written approval.

If you have study questions, or a study related problem?

If you have any questions about your participation in this study, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20November 2023

076 397 1986 If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact Prof. Paul Ruff at the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, at 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

Thank you for taking the time to consider partaking in this study.

Health Care Worker Informed Consent Form for Participant Observations

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS

Before you sign this form, please ask any questions on any aspect of this study that is unclear to you. You may take as much time as necessary to think it over.

For Researcher:

Did the participant raise any questions? YES/NO

If Yes, what were they?

Statement of Consent:

Please indicate your response by adding your initials next to the corresponding statements

Statement	Initial
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that the researchers will always wear clothes/badges that make it clear that they are not a member of staff at the facility.	
I agree to be observed as part of the participant observation for this study.	
I understand that all the information collected during the study will be treated with the strictest confidentiality and will only be used for scientific research purposes.	
I understand that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.	
I agree for my contact details to be stored so that the research team may contact me to participate in future research activities related to this study.	
I agree for my information to be shared, processed and transferred anonymously with other researchers, and in trusted data repositories and, where relevant, beyond the juridical borders of South Africa.	
I (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.	

POPIA Compliance

In accordance with the provisions of the **Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013** (as amended), I hereby consent:

- a) To my personal information (hereinafter 'data') being collected, processed, shared and stored in accordance with the research protocol as approved by the WITS Human Research Ethics Committee (Medical);
- b) To my anonymised data being shared, processed and transferred by third parties and between third parties, and where relevant beyond the jurisdictional borders of South Africa;
- c) To all findings and results flowing from my anonymised data being broadly shared and published on the conclusion of the research

PARTICIPANT CONSENT:

Participant's name and surname (Print)	Participant's signature	[] [] / [] [] [] [] / [] [] [] []	[] [] : [] []
		<i>d d m m m y y y y</i>	<i>Time</i>

STUDY STAFF:

Study staff name and surname conducting consent (Print)	Study staff's signature	[] [] / [] [] [] [] / [] [] [] []	[] [] : [] []
		<i>d d m m m y y y y</i>	<i>Time</i>

WITNESS (if applicable):

Witness name and surname (Print)	Witness's signature	[] [] / [] [] [] [] / [] [] [] []	[] [] : [] []
		<i>d d m m m y y y y</i>	<i>Time</i>

INFORMATION SHEET FOR HEALTH CARE WORKERS – In-depth Interview Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name and surname is _____ (insert name). I am a _____ (insert designation) at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. Together with colleagues at Wits RHI, we are conducting a research study to investigate the effect of indoor heat on the physical health and mental wellbeing of health care workers (HCWs) and on productivity and the quality of care provided. We would like to invite you to participate in our study.

What you should know about this research study:

- Before agreeing to participate, we are giving you this participant information sheet and consent form so that you may read about the purpose, risks, and benefits of this research study.
- You have the right to refuse to take part, and you have the right to agree to take part now and change your mind later.
- Whatever you decide, it will not affect your regular work.
- Please review this consent form carefully. Ask any questions before you make a decision.
- Your participation is voluntary.
- Thank you for reading this information. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a consent form.
- If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask me.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being invited to participate in a study that seeks to understand how ambient heat in the workplace impacts on HCWs' physical and mental wellbeing, their productivity, and the quality of care provided. Results from these interviews will help us to design an intervention to improve health facilities' adaptation to heat and thereby improve working conditions and health outcomes. The study is being conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden.

Why am I being asked to participate in this research study?

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a HCW:

- Aged 18 years and above
- Working full-time at Stanza Bopape Community healthcare Centre (CHC) or Mamelodi Hospital
- Working in antenatal, maternal, labour or neonatal ward/clinic
- Able and willing to consent to provide data for the study

PROCEDURES AND DURATION

The specific component of the study for which we are seeking your consent today is the **In-depth Interview** component. In the South African site in Tshwane, we will be interviewing up to 20 HCWs in this component.

If you agree to take part in this study, you will be interviewed individually by a researcher trained to carry out qualitative interviews. During the interview, we will ask about your experiences of how heat affects you and other HCWs in the workplace, specifically, how it affects your health and wellbeing, work performance, and quality of care provided. We will also ask about your coping strategies when temperatures are high, and your perspectives on what can be done in health facilities to keep staff and patients cool. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested to know more about your experiences and ideas. We expect that the interview will take approximately 1 hour.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The most important risk is breach of confidentiality, but this risk is low as we will use security measures to protect your personal data. An additional risk of participating in this study is that you may be anxious that you are being evaluated, which may make you feel uncomfortable. Our researchers have been trained in creating a supportive environment, without interfering with your regular work. Informal conversations will only be held when it is conducive for you with limited interruption of the work schedule.

Participation is entirely voluntary. It is important to know that you can stop your participation in this study at any time, without any consequences. You can also choose to skip a question if you do not feel at ease.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There are no direct benefits to participating in this study. It is expected that the results will inform the development of an intervention intended to improve working conditions at health facilities. You will not need to pay anything to take part in the study. You will be reimbursed R400 for your refreshment costs, time and inconvenience.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your data will be collected, processed, and stored according to the South African Protection of Personal Information (POPI) Act of 2013. To protect your confidentiality, no personal identifiers will appear in any verbal presentations, reports and publications that make use of this interview data.

All electronic data will be protected by security access codes. We will use a unique participant identification (ID) number instead of your name when storing and analyzing your

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

data. Any written information will be kept under lock and key in a cabinet and separately from any information that identifies you (such as the consent form). After study completion, files/information will be kept securely at the project office for a period of 6 years after all analysis and publications are complete for this study and then will be destroyed. Your de-identified data may be stored electronically for a longer than 6 years for use in other studies if you agree. No identifiable information will be shared with your colleagues or facility managers.

Who may see, use or share the information collected during this study about you?

The researchers that are involved in this study have access to this information. Organizations that may look at and/or copy your research records for ethical, research, quality assurance, and data analysis include:

- Wits Human Research Ethics Committee
- London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Ethics Committee

Additionally, we may share your de-identified information with researchers for use in other research studies if you agree to this. The information will be labelled with a unique code, and we will not share your name.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

It is your decision to take part in this study or not. Taking part in this study is completely voluntary. You may stop your participation in the study at any time without penalty. No matter what decision you make, there will be no negative consequences to you in any way.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been submitted to the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee, and this committee has granted written approval.

If you have study questions, or a study related problem?

If you have any questions about your participation in this study, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za
076 397 1986

If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact Prof. Paul Ruff at the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, at 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

Thank you for taking the time to consider partaking in this study.

Health Care Worker Informed Consent Form for In-depth Interview

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS

Before you sign this form, please ask any questions on any aspect of this study that is unclear to you. You may take as much time as necessary to think it over.

For Researcher:

Did the participant raise any questions? YES/NO

If Yes, what were they?

Statement of Consent:

Please indicate your response by adding your initials next to the corresponding statements

Statement	Initials
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that the researchers will always wear clothes/badges that make it clear that they are not a member of staff at the facility.	
I agree to take part in an In-depth Interview for this study.	
I understand that all the information collected during the study will be treated with the strictest confidentiality and will only be used for scientific research purposes.	
I understand that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.	
I agree for my contact details to be stored so that the research team may contact me to participate in future research activities related to this study.	
I agree for my information to be shared, processed and transferred anonymously with other researchers, and in trusted data repositories and, where relevant, beyond the juridical borders of South Africa.	
I (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.	

POPIA Compliance

In accordance with the provisions of the **Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013** (as amended), I hereby consent:

- d) To my personal information (hereinafter 'data') being collected, processed, shared and stored in accordance with the research protocol as approved by the WITS Human Research Ethics Committee (Medical);
- e) To my anonymised data being shared, processed and transferred by third parties and between third parties, and where relevant beyond the jurisdictional borders of South Africa;

To all findings and results flowing from my anonymised data being broadly shared and published on the conclusion of the research

[Appendix 10: Participant information sheet and informed consent form for key informant interview component](#)

INFORMATION SHEET FOR KEY INFORMANTS – Key Informant Interview Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name and surname is _____ (insert name). I am a _____ (insert designation) at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. Together with colleagues at Wits RHI, we are conducting a research study to investigate the effect of indoor heat on the health and wellbeing of health care workers (HCWs) and on productivity and the quality of care provided. We would like to invite you to participate in our study.

What you should know about this research study:

- Before agreeing to participate, we are giving you this participant information sheet and consent form so that you may read about the purpose, risks, and benefits of this research study.
- You have the right to refuse to take part, and you have the right to agree to take part now and change your mind later.
- Whatever you decide, it will not affect your regular work.
- Please review this consent form carefully. Ask any questions before you make a decision.
- Your participation is voluntary.
- Thank you for reading this information. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a consent form.
- If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask me.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being invited to participate in a study that seeks to understand how HCWs in maternity and newborn care are affected by ambient heat in the workplace. We want to understand the impact of heat on their physical and mental wellbeing, their productivity, and the quality of care provided, as well as how health facilities may be adapted to cope with rising temperatures caused by climate change. Results from these interviews will help to inform our design of an intervention to improve health facilities' adaptation to heat and thereby improve working conditions and health outcomes. The study is being conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden.

Why am I being asked to participate in this research study?

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are:

- Familiar with information on heat adaptation strategies, HCW wellbeing, and quality of care in healthcare facilities
- Aged 18 years and above
- Able and willing to consent to provide data for the study

PROCEDURES AND DURATION

The specific component of the study for which we are seeking your consent today is the **Key Informant Interview** component. In the South African site in Tshwane, we will be interviewing up to 15 key informants, including health facility, district and regional managers, and selected community members with knowledge and/or experience in this area.

If you agree to take part in this study, you will be interviewed individually by a researcher trained to carry out qualitative interviews. During the interview, we will ask about contextual information central to the development of strategies and interventions to cope with heat in health settings. We will also invite you to share your views on the impact of heat on the community and on health facilities, as well as your knowledge of heat adaptations that are being undertaken in other institutions or with the community. We expect that the interview will take approximately 45-60 minutes.

Participation is entirely voluntary. It is important to know that you can stop your participation in this study at any time, without any consequences. You can also choose not to answer a question if you do not feel at ease.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The most important risk is breach of confidentiality, but this risk is low as we will use a number of security measures to protect your personal data. There may be a time inconvenience for you if the interview exceeds the expected duration.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There are no direct benefits to participating in this study, but it is expected that the results will inform the development of an intervention intended to improve working conditions at health facilities. You will not need to pay anything to take part in the study. You will be reimbursed R400 for your refreshment costs, time and inconvenience.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your data will be collected, processed, and stored according to the South African Protection of Personal Information (POPI) Act of 2013. To protect your confidentiality, no personal identifiers will appear in any verbal presentations, reports and publications that make use of this interview data.

All electronic data will be protected by security access codes. We will use a unique participant identification (ID) number instead of your name when storing and analyzing your data. Any written information will be kept under lock and key in a cabinet and separately from any information that identifies you (such as the consent form). After study completion, files/information will be kept securely at the project office for a period of 6 years after all analysis and publications are complete for this study and then will be destroyed. Your de-

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

identified data may be stored electronically for a longer than 6 years for use in other studies if you agree. No identifiable information will be shared with your colleagues or facility managers.

Who may see, use or share the information collected during this study about you?

The researchers that are involved in this study have access to this information. Organizations that may look at and/or copy your research records for ethical, research, quality assurance, and data analysis include:

- Wits Human Research Ethics Committee
- London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Ethics Committee

Additionally, we may share your de-identified information with researchers for use in other research studies if you agree to this. The information will be labelled with a unique code, and we will not share your name.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

It is your decision to take part in this study or not. Taking part in this study is completely voluntary. You may stop your participation in the study at any time without penalty. No matter what decision you make, there will be no negative consequences to you in any way.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been submitted to the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee, and this committee has granted written approval.

If you have study questions, or a study related problem?

If you have any questions about your participation in this study, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za
076 397 1986

If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact Prof. Paul Ruff at the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, at 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

Thank you for taking the time to consider partaking in this study.

Informed Consent Form for Key Informant Interview

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS

Before you sign this form, please ask any questions on any aspect of this study that is unclear to you. You may take as much time as necessary to think it over.

For Researcher:

Did the participant raise any questions? YES/NO

If Yes, what were they?

Statement of Consent:

Please indicate your response by adding your initials next to the corresponding statements

Statement	Initials
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I agree to take part in a Key Informant Interview for this study.	
I understand that all the information collected during the study will be treated with the strictest confidentiality and will only be used for scientific research purposes.	
I understand that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.	
I agree for my contact details to be stored so that the research team may contact me to participate in future research activities related to this study.	
I agree for my information to be shared, processed and transferred anonymously with other researchers, and in trusted data repositories and, where relevant, beyond the juridical borders of South Africa.	
I (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.	

POPIA Compliance

In accordance with the provisions of the **Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013** (as amended), I hereby consent:

- f) To my personal information (hereinafter 'data') being collected, processed, shared and stored in accordance with the research protocol as approved by the WITS Human Research Ethics Committee (Medical);
- g) To my anonymised data being shared, processed and transferred by third parties and between third parties, and where relevant beyond the jurisdictional borders of South Africa;
- h) To all findings and results flowing from my anonymised data being broadly shared and published on the conclusion of the research

INFORMATION SHEET FOR HEALTH CARE WORKERS – Time-motion Study Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name and surname is _____ (insert name). I am a _____ (insert designation) at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. Together with colleagues at Wits RHI, we are conducting a research study to investigate the effect of indoor heat on the physical health and mental wellbeing of health care workers (HCWs) and on productivity and the quality of care provided. We would like to invite you to participate in our study.

What you should know about this research study:

- Before agreeing to participate, we are giving you this participant information sheet and consent form so that you may read about the purpose, risks, and benefits of this research study.
- You have the right to refuse to take part, and you have the right to agree to take part now and change your mind later.
- Whatever you decide, it will not affect your regular work.
- Please review this consent form carefully. Ask any questions before you make a decision.
- Your participation is voluntary.
- Thank you for reading this information. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a consent form.
- If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask me.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 4.0 dated 20 November 2023

You are being invited to participate in a study that seeks to understand the impact of ambient heat on HCWs' working environments, their physical and mental wellbeing, their productivity, and on the quality of care provided. This study focuses only on HCWs working in maternity and newborn care. The results from this study will help to design a program that can improve health facilities' adaptation to heat and thereby improve working conditions and health outcomes. The study is being conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden.

Why am I being asked to participate in this research study?

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a HCW:

- Aged 18 years and above
- Working full-time at Stanza Bopape Community healthcare Centre (CHC) or Mamelodi Hospital
- Working in antenatal, maternal, labour or neonatal ward/clinic
- Able and willing to consent to provide data for the study

PROCEDURES AND DURATION

The specific component of the study for which we are seeking your consent today is the **Time-motion assessment** component. Time-motion assessment is a method of collecting data on clinical work patterns through observation of activities that HCWs do as they go about their work or engage in other daily activities.

In this study component, we wish to observe you and other HCWs in your work environment, focusing on how heat affects your workflow. We will assess your work task activities, people involved in the task, the time taken to complete tasks, and the methods of the task performance, as well as interruptions to your work and multitasking. We will also ask you to wear two non-invasive sensors; one that will be attached to your wrist to measure the number of steps that you take in your shift and your heart rate and one that will be put around your chest to measure your core body temperature. You will be able to view your heart rate and other results of the sensors if you wish. We will give you the sensors before the start of the observations, so that you can get used to them. You will return the sensors at the end of the study period. Finally, we will record the type of clothing that you are wearing while participating in the assessment, as this may also affect your body temperature.

We will perform these observations over a period of 3-5 weeks, and for two time periods – once when the temperature is cool and once when it is hot. Observations will be carried out at different times of the day so that we may capture activity patterns across the shift.

Researchers trained to carry out these assessments will be stationed in the antenatal, maternal, labour, and neonatal wards/clinics at different times of the day and on different days of the week. They will move around these spaces but remain unobtrusive, and as far as possible, their observations will not interfere with the duties you carry out as a HCW. The researchers will take notes on a tablet or other electronic device about what they are observing.

It is important to be clear that our observations are **not** intended to monitor staff performance or to identify errors in the care you provide. Information gathered during the observations will not

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

be shared with your supervisors, but anonymous information may be shared with relevant stakeholders in government and with our research partners in Sweden, Zimbabwe, and the UK. The primary purpose of collecting this observation data is to inform our development of an intervention that will be tested in another component of the study.

Your privacy and confidentiality will be protected throughout, and no personal identifying information will be collected on any individuals who are observed in this activity. No names will be collected or published in our reports or academic articles. No photographs or videos will be taken of any individuals who are observed.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The most important risk is breach of confidentiality, but this risk is low as we will use security measures to protect your personal data. An additional risk of participating in this study is that you may be anxious that you are being evaluated, which may make you feel uncomfortable. Our researchers have been trained in creating a supportive environment, without interfering with your regular work. Informal conversations will only be held when it is conducive for you with limited interruption of the work schedule. It is important to know that you can stop your participation in this study at any time, without any consequences.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There are no direct benefits or reimbursement from participating in these observations. It is expected that the results will inform the development of an intervention intended to improve working conditions at health facilities. You will not need to pay anything to take part in the study. At the end of the observation period, you will be reimbursed R400 for your time and inconvenience.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your data will be collected, processed, and stored according to the South African Protection of Personal Information (POPI) Act of 2013. To protect your confidentiality, no personal identifiers will appear in any verbal presentations, reports and publications that make use of this observation data. All electronic data will be protected by security access codes. We will use a unique participant identification (ID) number instead of your name when storing and analyzing your data. Any written information will be kept under lock and key in a cabinet and separately from any information that identifies you (such as this consent form). After study completion, files/information will be kept securely at the project office for a period of 6 years after all analysis and publications are complete for this study and then will be destroyed. Your de-identified data may be stored electronically for a longer than 6 years for use in other studies if you agree. No identifiable information will be shared with your colleagues or facility managers.

Who may see, use or share the information collected during this study about you?

The researchers that are involved in this study have access to this information. Organizations that may look at and/or copy your research records for ethical, research, quality assurance, and data analysis include:

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

- Wits Human Research Ethics Committee
- London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Ethics Committee

Additionally, we may share your de-identified information with researchers for use in other research studies if you agree to this. The information will be labelled with a unique code, and we will not share your name.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

It is your decision to take part in this study or not. Taking part in this study is completely voluntary. You may stop your participation in the study at any time without penalty. No matter what decision you make, there will be no negative consequences to you in any way.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been submitted to the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee, and this committee has granted written approval.

If you have study questions, or a study related problem?

If you have any questions about your participation in this study, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za
076 397 1986

If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact Prof. Paul Ruff at the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, at 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

Thank you for taking the time to consider partaking in this study.

Health Care Worker Informed Consent Form for Time-motion Assessment

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS

Before you sign this form, please ask any questions on any aspect of this study that is unclear to you. You may take as much time as necessary to think it over.

For Researcher:

Did the participant raise any questions? YES/NO

If Yes, what were they?

Statement of Consent:

Please indicate your response by adding your initials next to the corresponding statements

Statement	Initials
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that the researchers will always wear clothes/badges that make it clear that they are not a member of staff at the facility.	
I agree to be observed as part of the time-motion assessment for this study.	
I understand that all the information collected during the study will be treated with the strictest confidentiality and will only be used for scientific research purposes.	
I understand that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.	
I agree for my contact details to be stored so that the research team may contact me to participate in future research activities related to this study.	
I agree for my information to be shared, processed and transferred anonymously with other researchers, and in trusted data repositories and, where relevant, beyond the juridical borders of South Africa.	
I (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.	

POPIA Compliance

In accordance with the provisions of the **Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013** (as amended), I hereby consent:

- a) To my personal information (hereinafter 'data') being collected, processed, shared and stored in accordance with the research protocol as approved by the WITS Human Research Ethics Committee (Medical);
- b) To my anonymised data being shared, processed and transferred by third parties and between third parties, and where relevant beyond the jurisdictional borders of South Africa;

To all findings and results flowing from my anonymised data being broadly shared and published on the conclusion of the research

INFORMATION SHEET FOR HEALTH CARE WORKERS – Survey Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name and surname is _____ (insert name). I am a (insert designation) at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. Together with colleagues at Wits RHI, we are conducting a research study to investigate the effect of indoor heat on the physical health and mental wellbeing of health care workers (HCWs) and on the productivity and the quality of care provided. We would like to invite you to participate in our study.

What you should know about this research study:

- Before agreeing to participate, we are giving you this participant information sheet and consent form so that you may read about the purpose, risks, and benefits of this research study.
- You have the right to refuse to take part, and you have the right to agree to take part now and change your mind later.
- Whatever you decide, it will not affect your regular work.
- Please review this consent form carefully. Ask any questions before you make a decision.
- Your participation is voluntary.
- Thank you for reading this information. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to complete a consent form.
- If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask me.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being invited to participate in a study that seeks to understand the impact of ambient heat on HCWs' working environments, their physical and mental well-being, their productivity, and the quality of care provided. This study focuses on HCW working in maternity and newborn care and will be carried out twice – once during a hotter period and once during a cooler period. The results from this study will help to design a program that can improve health facilities adaptation to heat and thereby improve working conditions and health outcomes. The study is being

HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe version 3.0 dated 04 October 2023

conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden. In South Africa, a minimum of 80 HCWs will participate in the study.

Why am I being asked to participate in this research study?

You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a HCW:

- Aged 18 years and above
- Working full-time at Stanza Bopape Community Healthcare Centre (CHC) or Mamelodi Hospital
- Working in antenatal, maternal, labour, or neonatal ward/clinic
- Able and willing to consent to provide data for the study

PROCEDURES AND DURATION

If you agree to take part in this study, you will be expected to participate in an anonymous survey and urine collection.

- 1) You will be requested to participate in an anonymous survey asking about your wellbeing in relation to your work at the facility which will last approximately thirty to forty-five minutes. If you are still at the same healthcare facility, you will be invited to complete the same survey twice, once in the hot season and once in the cold season. We will store your contact details to be able to contact you to participate in future surveys.
- 2) You will be requested to provide a urine sample to check for urine osmolarity, a commonly used biomarker for hydration status. This will be done at the end of a shift, on the day that you complete the survey.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

The most important risk is breach of confidentiality, but this risk is low as we will use security measures to protect your personal data. An additional risk of participating in this study is that you may be anxious that you are being evaluated, which may make you feel uncomfortable. Our researchers have been trained in creating a supportive environment, without interfering with your regular work. It is important to know that you can stop your participation in this study at any time, without any consequences. You can also choose to skip a question if you do not feel at ease. There are no risks to urine collection. If we find any abnormalities in your urine, or results from the survey, we will notify and refer you for further care if required.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There are no direct benefits to participating in this study. It is expected that the results will inform the development of an intervention intended to improve heat-related working conditions at health facilities. You will not need to pay anything to take part in the study. You will be reimbursed R400 for your refreshment costs, time, and inconvenience.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your data will be collected, processed and stored according to the South African Protection of Personal Information (POPI) Act of 2013. To protect your confidentiality, no personal identifiers will appear on the surveys, urine specimens or in any verbal presentations, reports and

publications. All your data will be protected by security access codes. We will use a unique participant identification (ID) number instead of your name when storing and analysing your data. Any written information will be kept under lock and key in a cabinet and separately from any information that identifies you (such as this consent form). After study completion, files/information will be kept securely at the project office for a period of 6 years after all analysis and publications are complete for this study and then will be destroyed. Your de-identified data may be stored electronically for a longer than 6 years for use in other studies if you agree. No identifiable information will be shared with your colleagues or facility managers.

Who may see, use or share the information collected during this study about you?

The researchers that are involved in this study have access to this information. Organizations that may look at and/or copy your research records for ethical, research, quality assurance, and data analysis include:

- Wits Human Research Ethics Committee
- South African National Health Research Ethics Council (NHREC)
- London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine Ethics Committee

Additionally, we may share your de-identified information with researchers for use in other research studies if you agree to this. The information will be labelled with a unique code and we will not share your name. You will mark your decision at the end of this form.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

It is your decision to take part in this study or not. Taking part in this study is completely voluntary. You may stop your participation in the study at any time without penalty. No matter what decision you make, there will be no negative consequences to you in any way.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been submitted to the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee, and this committee has granted written approval.

If you have study questions, or a study related problem?

If you have any questions about your participation in this study, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za
076 397 1986

If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact Prof. Paul Ruff at the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, at 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP.

Thank you for taking the time to consider partaking in this study.

Health Care Worker Informed Consent Form for Survey

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS

Before you sign this form, please ask any questions on any aspect of this study that is unclear to you. You may take as much time as necessary to think it over.

For Researcher:

Did the participant raise any questions? YES/NO

If Yes, what were they?

Statement of Consent:

Please indicate your response by adding your initials next to the corresponding statements

Statement	Initials
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that the researchers will always wear clothes/badges that make it clear that they are not a member of staff at the facility	
I agree to participate in a confidential survey .	
I agree to submit a urine sample and provide the result to the study team.	
I understand that all the information collected during the study will be treated with the strictest confidentiality and will only be used for scientific research purposes.	
I understand that I may, at any stage, without prejudice, withdraw my consent and participation in the study.	
I agree for my contact details to be stored so that the research team may contact me to participate in future research activities related to this study.	
I agree for my information to be shared, processed and transferred anonymously with other researchers, and in trusted data repositories, and where relevant beyond the juridical borders of South Africa.	
I (of my own free will) declare myself prepared to participate in the study.	

POPIA Compliance

In accordance with the provisions of the **Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013** (as amended), I hereby consent:

- c) To my personal information (hereinafter 'data') being collected, processed, shared and stored in accordance with the research protocol as approved by the WITS Human Research Ethics Committee (Medical);
- d) To my anonymised data being shared, processed and transferred by third parties and between third parties, and where relevant beyond the jurisdictional borders of South Africa;

To all findings and results flowing from my anonymised data being broadly shared and published on the conclusion of the research.

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PATIENTS – Participant Observation Component

Title of the research study: HIGH Horizons Health Care Worker Study in South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe

Sponsor: European Union

Principal Investigator: Dr Gloria Maimela

Institution: Wits RHI

Email: gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za

Contact number: 076 397 1986

Hello, my name is Dr Gloria Maimela, I am a Researcher at the Wits RHI Climate and Health Directorate. Together with colleagues at Wits RHI, we are conducting a research study about how heat affects the physical health and mental wellbeing of health care workers in maternity and newborn care, as well as their productivity and the quality of care provided. Results from this study will help us to design a program to help make health facilities cooler in the hot season, and thereby improve working conditions for health care workers and health outcomes for patients. The study is being conducted in Zimbabwe, South Africa and Sweden.

As part of the study, we will be carrying out **Participant Observation**. This is a method of collecting research information through observing a set of activities or group of people as they go about their work or engage in other daily activities.

Researchers trained to carry out such observations (and wearing easily identifiable badges) will be present in the antenatal, maternal, labour and neonatal wards/clinics at different times of the day and on different days of the week. They will move around these spaces and try to stay out of the way as much as possible. Occasionally, the researchers will take written notes about what they are observing.

These researchers will be observing the health care workers as they administer care in these wards/clinics, rather than the patients. In the process, however, some aspects of health care worker-patient interaction may be observed. Researchers will not observe sensitive procedures (e.g. a patient undergoing a vaginal examination).

Your privacy and confidentiality will be protected throughout, and no personal identifying information will be collected on any individuals who are observed in this activity. No names will be collected or published in our reports or academic articles. No photographs or videos will be taken of any individuals who are observed. Information gathered during the observations will only be shared with relevant stakeholders in government and with our research partners in Sweden, Zimbabwe and the UK.

If you do not wish to be observed, you have the right to ‘opt out’ of these observations, and it will not affect the care you receive in this facility.

To opt out, simply tell the researchers and they will respect your decision. No one except the researcher will know that you have opted out of the observations.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study has been approved by the University of Witwatersrand, Human Research Ethics Committee. If you have study questions, or a study related problem, please contact:

Dr Gloria Maimela
Wits RHI
22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow, Johannesburg 2100
gmaimela@wrhi.ac.za
076 397 1986

If you have any questions concerning this study or consent form beyond those answered by the investigator, including questions about the research, your rights as a research participant or research-related injuries; or if you feel that you have been treated unfairly and would like to talk to someone other than a member of the research team, please feel free to contact the University of Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee, via email to Prof. Clement Penny at clement.penny@wits.ac.za or by calling during office hours: 011 717 2301.

YOU WILL HAVE A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET TO KEEP

Thank you for considering participation in this study.